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Table of Contents

Abstract (summary of deliverable):	3
Methodology:	3
RESULTS	6
1. Results and Analysis of Online Surveys:	6
a. Demographic description of survey sample	6
b. Understanding the Needs and Priorities of SHs.....	9
c. Training Focus Areas and Knowledge Exchange platform preferences by SHs: ..	26
2. One-on-One Interviews.....	28
2.1. INDUSTRY SH INTERVIEWS.....	29
2.2. ACADEMIA SH INTERVIEWS:	37
2.4. Civil Society SH Interviews	55
3. Face-to Face Workshop: WORLD Cafe Event.....	57
4. PANEL DISCUSSION at ILSI Europe Symposium:.....	68
5. SH engagement on concerns in food safety extracted from workshop organized by FIAB:	71
6. Interactive Questionnaires at In-person workshops and online webinars SH engagements:	72
STRENGTHS and WEAKNESS recognized from the above reported SH Engagements:	75
NEXT STEPS and Conclusions:	75

Abstract (summary of deliverable):

The stakeholder (SH) engagements conducted as part of Work Package 2 (WP2) for the CATALYSE project aimed to understand the barriers and levers for SH in terms of implementing innovative food safety applications, knowledge exchange, and education and training to develop relevant content for the upcoming Work Package (WP). These engagements also aimed to identify and select focus areas in food safety for CATALYSE to ensure a more impactful and resource-efficient approach. Additionally, they set the basis for sustainable, long-lasting engagement by establishing a list of SH participants for the CATALYSE platform and the Community of Practice (CoP) to foster connections, experience sharing, and contributions to the project's success.

The SH engagements also contributed to communication efforts regarding CATALYSE (in collaboration with WP8). This comprehensive approach, based on the "5Ws and 1H" model outlined in the SH Engagement Strategy (D2.1), established a strong foundation for WP3 (Database of Knowledge and Innovative Solutions for Food Safety), WP4 (Setting up the CoP and Chapters), WP5 (Deploying the CATALYSE CoP), and WP6 (Education and Training), thereby paving the way for the project's successful contribution to food safety innovation.

The engagement activities took place between months 1 (M1) and 12 (M12) of the project timeline, using various data collection formats such as online surveys, one-on-one structured interviews, in-person workshops (including world café events and interactive workshops), and webinars. These engagements highlighted the need for enhanced knowledge in microbiological food safety, chemical food safety, allergen food safety, food safety culture and definitions, risk communication and management, packaging innovations, hygienic design, AI applications in food safety, and regulatory understanding and simplification.

SH identified "sources of contamination," "predictive models," "new technology in risk prevention," "technology for identifying microorganisms," and "AI tools in food safety" as key innovations facilitating improvements in food safety. Consistently across interactions, "pathogen control" remained the most critical concern in food safety discussions.

The results of these SH interactions pave the way for the CATALYSE project to design the focus areas that will become the building blocks of the CoP. This report presents the preliminary conclusions from the various engagement strategies, serving as the foundation for a future version of the report that will specify the refined conclusions to support the CoP's development.

Introduction

The CATALYSE project recognizes the vital role of SH engagement in addressing the complex challenges of food safety and innovation. This document provides an in-depth overview of the methodologies, activities, and strategies employed to foster collaboration with key actors across the food sector. By involving diverse SH—spanning industry, academia, public authorities, and civil society—this report lays the groundwork for building a robust foundation of shared knowledge, practical solutions, and collective action.

This report presents the results of SH engagement activities conducted during the first 12 months of the project. The main objective of this work is to identify the needs, priorities, and innovations in food safety, enabling the development of effective strategies for knowledge exchange, implementation of innovative solutions, and the establishment of a Community of Practice (CoP). Through surveys, one-on-one interviews, in-person workshops, and online webinars, valuable data has been collected and analyzed in the present report.

Methodology

WP2, in coordination with all project partners, defined key SH groups in the food sector for each dimension, namely as:

- Academia and/or Research Institutes
- Food Industry
- Policymakers, Public Authorities, Government
- Civil Society

Specific networks, organizations, and individuals within each group of interest were identified. The SH engagements were organized through various interaction channels based on the EFGA Engagement Toolkit, *“Methods, Tips, and Best Practices to Design Effective Participatory Processes”*.

The SH engagement interactions followed six concepts specified in the Strategic and Innovation Plan for Food Safety published by Flanders Food (<https://www.flandersfood.com/en/world-class-food-production/food-safety>), which are transversal themes reflected in each action. The six concepts are:

1. [Understanding](#) - Create understanding and appreciation of food safety
2. [Tech-enabled](#) - Incorporate technology into a food-safe work environment
3. [Farm to fork risks](#) - Make food safety more sustainable and connected
4. [Trend risks](#) - Create support for demand-driven food safety problems
5. [Pathogen control](#) - Monitor the presence and growth of pathogenic microorganisms
6. [Clean production](#) - Monitor hygiene to control food safety

Each interaction provided a different level of detail on the same topics specified (Table 1) and the Engagement Strategy adapted and achieved milestones are described in Table 2.

Table 1. Aim of various SH Engagement Strategies

SH Engagement Strategy	Aim of specific SH engagements		
	Understand Needs/Priorities	Collect Information on Innovations	Gather insight on Training focus for CoP
Online Survey	✓	✓	✓
One-on-One Interviews	✓	✓	✓

Webinars	✓	x	✓
Face-to-Face Workshops	✓	✓	✓

Table 2. SH Engagement Goals Achieved

Engagement Strategy	Target Goal	Achieved engagement activities
Online Survey	100 Survey Responses	113 responses collected
One-on-One Interviews	80 Interviews	85 accomplished interviews
Webinars	4 webinars	4 webinars conducted
Face-to-Face Workshops	4 workshops	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - World Cafe at IAFP conference Geneva, CH - Interactive Workshop at IUFOST conference in Remini, IT - Interactive Workshop with a round table discussion at Synergy Days in Barcelona, ES - Pitch Platform for innovations with an interactive session at EFFoST conference in Brugges, BE - Panel Discussion at ILSI Europe Annual Symposium in Copenhagen, DK

We began with SH Engagements with Online Surveys beginning from March until October 2024. The ultimate target goal was to achieve 100 survey responses, with each consortium partner requested to collect 8 survey responses. Online surveys (Annex 1) were conducted with 113 varied SH in the field of food sector. Apart from English language, the exact survey was distributed in different languages including Spanish (Annex 2), German (Annex 3), Ukrainian (Annex 4), Portuguese (Annex 5), Italian (Annex 6), and Finnish (Annex 7). The survey began with a demographic set of questions that helped us to understand and enhance the analysis of these survey responses.

Meanwhile, WP2 partners with all the consortium finalized the structure of one-on-one Interviews questionnaire, after which ILSI Europe delivered an online training session on 27th and 28th March 2024, for CATALYSE members on interview guidelines and expected outcomes, as well as explaining the strategy in-depth of the entire SH Engagement Activities for 2024. This training ensured that interviews would be conducted in a harmonious way to reach the goal of 80 interactions, each member was instructed to conduct minimum 3 interviews. The one-on-one interviews were actively conducted by all consortium partners with internal and external SH.

In addition, three in-person workshops were conducted. This included a world café format workshop at IAFP European Symposium 2024, an interaction at IUFOST 22nd World Congress of Food Science and Technology and ended these workshops with a brainstorming session at Synergy Days 2024. Furthermore, 2 in-conference sessions were organized within the session programs of EFFoST International Conference 2024 and ILSI Europe Annual Symposium. Below

timeline chart (Figure 1) depicts an informative yet visual structuring of CATALYSE’s SH Engagement during 2024.

Figure 1. Timeline chart for SH Engagements during 2024.

GENERAL RESULTS

1. Results and Analysis of Online Surveys

a. Demographic description of survey sample

The survey was consented to and only moved forward on acceptance by the SH, it was voluntary and anonymous. From the 113 responses, a total of 53% answering the survey questionnaire were women, 45% were men, 1% chose ‘other’ gender option, and 1% preferred not to mention it. The SH answering the questionnaire also belonged to different age groups (Table 3).

Table 3. SH Age Diversion for Online Surveys

Age Group (years)	SHs (%)
31-45 yrs	41
46-60 yrs	41
>60 yrs	11
20-30 yrs	6
Prefer not to say	1

The above responses tell us that equal and maximum number of SH belonged to the age of 31-45 (41%) and 46-60 (41%). In addition, most of the respondents were from Switzerland, followed by Finland, Italy, Slovakia, and Spain. These countries provided the majority of insights for the country-level food safety assessment. The lowest number of responses came from North Macedonia, Czech Republic, Sweden, Germany, France, and Austria.

Figure 2. Respondents reference countries.

The following categories of SH filled the surveys to give us a deeper understanding of the responses.

Table 4. SH category diversion for online surveys

SH Category	Total SHs (%)
Industry	57
Academia/ Research Institute	24
Policymaker / Public Authority	12
Other	4
Civil Society	3

As depicted in Table 4, the highest proportion of SH who took part in the survey responses were Industry with a total of 57%, followed by Academia/Research Institute, Policymaker / Public Authority, Civil Society and Other. In the category of 'other', participants mentioned that they belonged to 'non-profit organization'; 'distribution'; 'hospitality'; and 'grocery store'. In addition, of the 57% of participants from to the food industry, they indicated belonging to the business categories specified in Table 5.

Table 5. Business Subdivisions of Participants from the Food Industry

Industry SH Domain:	Total SHs (%)
Food / Ingredients / Equipment Processor	62
Primary Producers	11
Laboratory Services	9
B2B Consultancy	6
Food Safety Technology Provider	6
Other	5
Non-profit Organization	1
Logistics Company	0

The SH that belonged to policymaker / public authority category, were asked to specify their domain of action (Table 6), we received a considerable number of responses from National, Regional risk management responsible in European member states.

Table 6. Policymaker / Public Authority SH Categorization

Policymaker / Public Authority SH Domain*	Total SHs (%)
Public Authorities / authorities responsible for (national, regional) risk management in the Member States	53
Policymakers / national level (e.g. Ministry) and possibly also international level (e.g. European Commission)	18
Public Authorities / authorities responsible for risk assessment in the Member States	17
Public Authorities / international authorities: EFSA, ECHA, EMA, ...	12
Other	0

*The categorization of these options was consulted with CATALYSE consortium member The Finnish Food Authority, their expertise as gave us the advantage of asking the right question.

The participants were asked about their primary role within specific food categories. The majority reported working with dairy products, processed foods, and ingredients (Table 7).

Table 7. SH's Primary Roles within Specific Food Groups.

Food Categories of primary work	Total SHs (%)
Fresh fruits and vegetables	10
Grains and cereals	10
Dairy products	19
Beverages	9
Meats and Poultry	10
Fish and Seafood	7
Processed and packaged foods	13
Ingredients	11
Plant-based Foods	9
Other	2

b. Understanding the Needs and Priorities of SHs

One of the main goals of CATALYSE survey was to identify which needs of our potential CoP and to define the key topics of interest we should focus on. To achieve this, the questionnaire included questions regarding participants’ levels of concern about control measures in food safety related to:

- 1) pathogenic and spoilage microorganisms and their applications,
- 2) chemical risks and their applications
- 3) allergen risks and their applications.

In all the cases, the concern levels were categorized by High Concern; Medium Concern; Low Concern; Very Low Concern.

Figure 3. Concern Levels for control measures of pathogenic and spoilage microorganisms.

Figure 4. Gender diversion for control measure concerns of pathogenic and spoilage microorganisms.

The above two graphical representations analyze concerns regarding control measures in food safety related to pathogenic and spoilage microorganisms. Figure 3 reveals that 45% of respondents express "high concern," the largest proportion, followed by 32% with "medium concern," 19% with "low concern," and only 4% indicating "very low concern." This highlights that higher levels of concern dominate perceptions of food safety risks associated with harmful microorganisms. Moreover, Figure 4 provides a gender-specific breakdown. Women exhibit the highest proportion of "high concern," surpassing men in this category, emphasizing their greater sensitivity toward food safety risks. Interestingly, both genders follow a similar trend, with "medium concern" and "low concern" being the next most selected categories, while "very low concern" remains minimal. Overall, the data underline significant awareness and concern about food safety, particularly among women.

Finally, SH expressed their concerns through an open ended- answer on specifying their concerns, as summarized below:

Consumer Safety Concerns

- Foodborne Illnesses: The risk of illness caused by pathogenic microorganisms, such as *Salmonella*, *E. coli*, and *Listeria*.
- Product Recall: The negative impact of product recalls on businesses and consumer trust.
- Food Waste: Inefficient control measures can lead to increased food waste.
- Consumer Education: The need to educate consumers about food safety practices and the risks associated with improper handling and storage.

Regulatory and Technological Concerns

- Regulatory Framework: The need for clear and effective regulations to address food safety challenges.
- Technological Advancements: The development of innovative technologies for rapid detection, prevention, and control of microorganisms.
- Knowledge Transfer: The importance of transferring scientific knowledge and best practices to industry and consumers.

Figure 5. Concern Levels for Control Measures in chemical risks and their applications

Figure 6. Gender Divergence in control measure concerns for chemical risks

The above two graphical representations examine concerns regarding control measures in food safety related to chemical risks and their implementation. The pie chart (Figure 5) shows that 41% of respondents express "medium concern," making it the most common level of concern, followed by 26% with "high concern," 24% with "low concern," and only 9% reporting "very low concern." This indicates that most individuals are moderately to highly concerned about chemical risks in food safety. The bar chart (Figure 6) provides a gender-based analysis. Women report the highest proportion of "high concern," surpassing men, which highlights a heightened level of awareness or sensitivity toward chemical risks among women. For both genders, "medium concern" is the next most common category, followed by "low concern." However, men report a slightly higher percentage of "very low concern" than women. This data suggests that chemical risks in food safety elicit significant concern, particularly among women, with a notable emphasis on moderate to high levels of awareness and apprehension.

Unidentified and Emerging Threats:

- Inadequate Monitoring: Concerns exist regarding unidentified chemical risks and limited focus beyond basic hygiene checks.
- Emerging Contaminants: Microplastics, environmental pollutants, and novel chemicals in food (e.g., from packaging) pose growing threats.
- Mycotoxins: Specific fungal toxins like aflatoxins present a high risk in certain sectors like dairy.

Regulatory and Technological Needs:

- Legislation and Resources: Stronger regulations, improved coordination, and sufficient resources are needed for control and detection.
- Rapid Detection Methods: Faster and more effective testing methods are crucial for identifying chemical risks.

- Knowledge Transfer: Research findings and best practices need to be effectively communicated to industry and consumers.

Consumer Safety Concerns:

- Long-Term Health Effects: Potential impacts on reproductive health, endocrine disruption, and genotoxic effects raise concerns.
- Chemical Residues: Contamination from pesticides, heavy metals, cleaning agents, and packaging migration remains a concern.
- Balancing Benefits and Risks: Judicious use of food additives requires balancing potential benefits against known risks.

Industry Challenges:

- Knowledge Gap: Limited technical knowledge, especially among small and medium-sized enterprises, hinders effective risk management.
- Emerging Issues: The dynamic nature of chemical risks requires continual adaptation of control measures.

Applications in Food Safety:

- Cleaning Products: The proper selection and use of food-safe cleaning products are essential for preventing contamination.
- Food Contact Materials: Concerns exist regarding contaminants migrating from packaging materials into food.

Figure 7. Concern levels for Control Measure with Allergens and their applications

Figure 8. Gender diversion for concerns in control measures for allergens and applications

Figure 7 and 8 present a comparative analysis of perceived concerns regarding food safety control measures with allergens, categorized by gender. The pie chart on the left depicts the distribution of concern levels across all respondents, with a notable dominance of "High Concern" (32%). This indicates a significant awareness of the potential risks associated with food allergens. The bar graphs on the right further break down this data by gender, revealing some interesting insights. While both men and women share similar concern levels for "Very Low Concern" and "Low Concern" measures, there's a notable divergence in the "Medium Concern" and "High Concern" categories. Women exhibit a slightly higher level of concern in these areas compared to men. This suggests that women might be more vigilant to potential allergen-related risks in food safety practices.

Consumer Safety and Protection:

- **Transparency and Labeling:** The need for clear and accurate allergen labeling to ensure consumer safety.
- **Cross-Contamination:** The risk of unintentional allergen transfer during production and preparation.
- **Novel Foods:** The introduction of new food products may bring additional allergen challenges.

Industry Challenges:

- **Regulatory Framework:** The lack of clear and consistent regulations, especially regarding allergen thresholds and management.
- **Technical Knowledge:** Limited understanding of allergen risks and control measures among food producers, particularly SMEs.
- **Detection Methods:** The need for reliable and sensitive detection methods to identify and mitigate allergen risks.
- **Supply Chain Management:** Effective management of allergen risks throughout the entire supply chain.

Consumer Awareness and Education:

- **Consumer Understanding:** The need to educate consumers about allergen risks and how to avoid them.
- **Dietary Restrictions:** The growing number of consumers with food allergies and intolerances requires increased vigilance.

Overall, the responses emphasize the importance of a comprehensive approach to allergen management in the food industry, including robust control measures, clear labeling, and effective consumer education.

When compared with all the above control measure concerns, SH consider pathogenic and spoilage microorganisms to be considered as the highest “high concern”, followed by allergen risks and then chemical risks in control measures towards food safety (Figure 9).

Figure 9. High Concern comparison for control measures in food safety.

The next category of questions revolved around the level of concern for rapid detection methods in pathogenic and spoilage microorganisms, chemical risks and allergen risks.

Figure 10. Concern levels in Rapid Detection Methods for pathogenic and spoilage microorganisms

Figure 11. Gender Divergence for concerns in rapid detection methods of pathogenic and spoilage microorganisms

Figure 10 indicates a relatively high level of concern among SH regarding rapid detection methods for pathogenic and spoilage microorganisms. A significant portion (31%) express a high level of concern, while 22% have a medium level of concern. This suggests that rapid detection methods are considered crucial for ensuring food safety. In Figure 11, both men and women express a high level of concern regarding rapid detection methods, with women showing slightly higher levels. Although men dominating “medium concern” in this category than women.

This survey question was followed with open-ended responses highlight several key areas for improvement in rapid detection methods for pathogenic and spoilage microorganisms:

Field of Application:

- Supply Chain Management: Portable and in-line control methods are needed to ensure efficient and safe food handling throughout the supply chain.
- Cheese Production: Rapid, accredited methods are required specifically for cheesemaking applications.
- Perishable Foods: Improved methods for detecting pathogens like Listeria in perishable foods are in high demand.
- Laboratory and Home Use: Simple, reliable systems for both laboratory and at-home use are desired.
- Production Lines: Faster detection methods for production lines are crucial to optimize food safety and production efficiency.
- Pasteurized Products: Rapid detection methods for Listeria in pasteurized products like butter are needed.
- Pre-Harvest and Post-Harvest Stages: Early detection methods for identifying potential contamination risks are important.

Technical Considerations:

- Specificity and Reliability: Improved methods with high specificity and reliability are crucial to minimize false positive and negative results.
- Detection Levels and Quantification: Methods with sufficient sensitivity for accurate detection and quantification of microorganisms are desired.
- Cost-Effectiveness: Balancing affordability with effectiveness is critical, particularly for small and medium-sized enterprises.
- Ease of Use: Simple and user-friendly methods are essential for widespread adoption across different user groups.
- Data Accuracy and Interpretation: Rapid tests should provide reliable data with clear interpretation tools for non-experts.
- Rapid Enrichment Methods: Development of faster enrichment methods to overcome the limitations associated with current approaches is a priority.
- Emerging Pathogens and Variants: Detection methods capable of identifying new and emerging pathogens are necessary.

Validation and Implementation:

- Standardization and Accreditation: Rigorous validation and accreditation processes are needed to ensure the reliability and acceptance of rapid methods.
- Knowledge Transfer: Effective communication and training programs are crucial for promoting the proper use and interpretation of rapid tests.

Figure 12. Control levels for rapid detection methods for chemical substances.

Figure 13. Gender diversion for concerns of rapid detection methods of chemical substances.

The above charts suggest that while there's a moderate level of concern about rapid detection methods for chemical substances, the highest proportion of SH (36%) express a medium level of concern, Figure 12. This suggests a general awareness of the importance of rapid detection methods but perhaps a lack of specific knowledge or understanding about their capabilities and limitations. The Figure 13 suggests that women may perceive a greater risk associated with chemical contaminants in food and may advocate for stronger regulatory measures and improved detection methods.

SHs identified several key areas for improvement in rapid detection methods for chemical risks in food safety:

- **Increased Sensitivity:** Lower detection thresholds are needed to identify even minute levels of contaminants.
- **Faster Detection:** Rapid methods are crucial to minimize product recalls and economic losses.
- **Improved Specificity:** Reducing false positives and negatives is essential to ensure accurate results.
- **User-Friendly Methods:** Simple and easy-to-use methods are needed for wider adoption, especially in small-scale operations.
- **Standardization:** International standardization would facilitate global trade and regulatory compliance.
- **Cost-Effectiveness:** Affordable methods are essential for widespread implementation.
- **Addressing Emerging Contaminants:** Rapid methods should be adaptable to detect new and emerging chemical risks.

Figure 14. Concern levels for rapid detection methods of allergen compounds

Figure 15. Gender Diversion for rapid detection method concerns for allergen compounds

The Figure 14 indicates a relatively high level of concern among SHs regarding rapid detection methods for allergenic substances. A significant portion (28%) express a high level of concern, while 26% have a medium level of concern. In Figure 15, both men and women express a high level of concern regarding rapid detection methods, with women showing a slightly higher level. On contrary, men tend to have a slightly higher proportion of "low concern" responses. The open-ended responses highlight several key areas for improvement in rapid detection methods for allergens in food safety:

Field of Application:

- Cheese Production: SHs expressed interest in rapid detection methods specifically for cheese, considering the potential impact of proteolysis on allergen content.
- Food Production: Improved methods are needed throughout the production chain, including analysis of incoming raw materials and finished products.
- Restaurants and Personal Use: Simple, reliable, and cost-effective rapid tests for use in restaurants and by consumers at home are highly desired.
- Labeling: While effective labeling remains crucial, rapid tests can be a valuable tool for verification and consumer confidence.

Technical Considerations:

- Reliability and Accuracy: SHs emphasize the need for reliable, accurate, and validated rapid tests with clear interpretation guidelines.
- Standardization: Standardization of rapid tests across the EU is seen as essential for consistency and regulatory compliance.
- Cost-Effectiveness: Affordable methods are crucial for widespread adoption, particularly for small and medium-sized enterprises.
- Quantitation: Quantitative methods that measure allergen protein levels are desired to improve risk assessment and management.
- Emerging Allergens: Rapid tests should adapt to emerging allergens, particularly those from novel plant-based ingredients.

When compared with all the above rapid detection method concerns, SHs consider pathogenic and spoilage microorganisms to be considered as the highest “high concern”, followed by allergen risks and then chemical risks in control measures towards food safety, see below Figure 16.

Figure 16. High concern comparison for rapid detection methods in food safety

Figure 17. Concern levels for Hygienic design recommendations and best shared practices.

Figure 18. Gender diversion for concerns in hygienic design recommendation and best shared practices.

The pie chart in Figure 17 indicates a moderate level of concern among SH regarding hygienic design recommendations and best shared practices. A significant portion (34%) express a high level of concern, while 30% have a medium level of concern. This suggests that participants recognize the importance of implementing hygienic design principles and best practices to ensure food safety. In Figure 18, both men and women express a high level of concern, with women showing a slightly higher level. Key Areas of concern and suggestions towards hygienic design and best shared practices:

Prevention as a Priority

- SHs emphasized the importance of prevention as the cornerstone of food safety, particularly in reducing microbiological risks.

Technological Advancements

- There is a call for technological evolution to modernize facilities and equipment. Outdated infrastructure, especially in small and medium enterprises (SMEs), is seen as a barrier to hygienic design.

Accessibility and Clarity of Guidelines

- Clear, accessible, and multilingual guidelines are deemed essential. Free resources for assessing equipment modifications and best practices were highlighted as a critical need.

Industry-Specific Requirements

- Concerns specific to certain sectors, such as the chocolate and cheese industries, were noted. For instance, chocolate production requires equipment designed for ease of cleaning and maintenance, while dairy producers seek shared best practices and guidance on microbiological risks like *Listeria monocytogenes*.

Knowledge Transfer and Training

- Education and training were seen as quick-win solutions to improve compliance with hygienic design principles. This includes training for both skilled and unskilled workers to address workforce shortages.

Retail and Consumer-Focused Innovations

- Suggestions included innovative retail solutions, such as compartmentalized shopping carts for separating raw and ready-to-eat foods and insulated bags for cold storage during shopping.

Barriers to Implementation

- Financial constraints, especially among SMEs, were cited as a significant barrier. Additionally, some SHs felt there had been little progress in hygienic design development in recent years.

Cross-Contamination Prevention

- Design improvements were suggested to minimize chemical and microbiological cross-contamination risks across the food supply chain, from primary processing to consumer handling.

Education and Outreach

- Effective communication of hygienic design principles through consulting services, courses, and information dissemination was emphasized. Also, SH stressed the importance of translating research into practical, actionable recommendations.

Figure 19. Concern levels for food supply chain traceability and transparency

Figure 20. Gender diversion for concerns in food supply chain traceability and transparency

The pie chart (Figure 19) for supply chain traceability and transparency reveals that most respondents express medium (38%) or high concern (31%), while a smaller proportion indicates low (21%) or very low concern (10%), highlighting the significance of this issue. The bar chart (Figure 20) further disaggregates these concerns by gender. Among women, medium and high concerns dominate, while low and very low concerns are minimal. Men show a similar trend, but the proportion of medium concern appears slightly lower compared to women, and high concern is prominent. These results indicate that while gender differences exist, both groups share a predominantly cautious stance on food supply chain transparency.

As depicted in Figure 21, concerns about materials used in packaging innovations are led by medium concern at 43%, the highest across the three categories. Low concern accounts for 22%, with high concern (25%) being notably higher than in the previous charts. Only 10% express very low concern, reflecting heightened sensitivity toward packaging materials. Women show heightened medium and high concerns compared to men, whose responses are more evenly distributed but with a slightly larger proportion expressing low concern (Figure 22).

Figure 21. Concern levels for packaging innovations in relation to materials.

Figure 22. Gender diversion for concerns in packaging innovations in relation to materials.

For Process of Packaging: In Figure 23, Concerns are distributed with medium concern dominating at 39%, followed by low concern at 30%. A smaller percentage of respondents indicate high concern (17%) and very low concern (14%), suggesting a moderate level of worry about packaging processes. From Figure 24, among women, medium concern is most significant, with notable high concern compared to men. Men share a similar trend but have slightly higher proportions in the low concern category.

Figure 23. Concern levels for packaging innovations in relation to process of packaging

Figure 24. Gender diversion for concerns in packaging innovations in relation to process

When asked about concerns in active packaging as depicted in Figure 25, medium concern is again the largest category at 41%, while low concern follows at 28%. High concern is relatively lower (11%), and very low concern accounts for 20%. This indicates a slightly reduced overall level of worry compared to the process of packaging. From Figure 26, women express higher medium and low concerns compared to men, who show more balanced distribution across all categories, with medium and low concerns being the most prominent.

Figure 25. Concern levels for packaging innovations in relation to active packaging

Figure 26. Gender Diversion for concerns in packaging innovations in relation to active packaging

Furthermore, these food safety SHs when asked about AI and big data usage revealed a low adoption rate of big data and AI tools, with only 14% reporting usage, as shown in figure 27. To gain further insight, SH were asked to elaborate on their responses. Key findings from their comments are summarized below:

Figure 27. Use of AI data/tools by SHs

SHs Using AI and Big Data:

Applications Reported:

- Use of tools such as ChatGPT, Google Gemini, SAS Visual Analytics, and Power BI for trend identification, predictive modeling, and risk analysis.
- Applications in horizon scanning, forecasting models, genomics and metagenomics, and non-destructive product analysis.
- AI’s role in quality control, hygiene monitoring, and supply chain traceability was noted as enhancing efficiency and safety.
- Python was mentioned as a programming tool, highlighting its role in data analysis and AI model development for food safety applications.

Future Directions:

- Interest in expanding digitalization to enable broader AI and big data integration.
- Companies are exploring partnerships (e.g., AIBIO-UK hub) and leveraging Python and other technologies to build custom tools for their unique needs.

SHs Not Using AI and Big Data:

Reasons for Non-Use:

- Knowledge Gaps: Limited understanding of AI tools, including Python applications, and their potential benefits in food safety.
- Lack of Resources: Barriers include the absence of suitable tools, trained personnel, and organizational infrastructure.
- Perceived Irrelevance: Some SHs feel AI and big data are not directly applicable to their specific roles or organizational objectives.
- Skepticism: Concerns about AI’s reliability, alignment with regulatory requirements, and long-term impact on workflows.

Interest in Learning:

- Many respondents expressed interest in learning about AI tools, including Python-based applications, to better understand their relevance to food safety.
- Specific areas of curiosity include risk identification, data processing efficiency, and global data accessibility.

Key Observations:

- AI adoption is at an early stage in the food safety sector, with most organizations in exploratory or preparatory phases.
- Tools like Python are increasingly recognized as valuable for developing predictive models, analyzing large datasets, and creating tailored solutions for food safety challenges.
- SHs see promise in AI and big data's ability to enhance efficiency, automate processes, and identify risks, but challenges related to implementation, knowledge gaps, and regulation need to be addressed.

Recommendations:

- Educational Initiatives: Focus on training programs to improve understanding of AI and Python applications in food safety.
- Pilot Projects: Showcase the practical benefits of AI through small-scale, industry-specific implementations.
- Collaboration: Facilitate partnerships between AI experts and food safety professionals to co-develop solutions tailored to industry needs.

Organizational-Level Food Safety Satisfaction

Respondents were asked to rate their satisfaction with food safety within their respective organizations on a scale of 1 (least satisfied) to 10 (highly satisfied). The average satisfaction score was **8,04** indicating a generally high level of confidence in organizational food safety practices.

Country-Level Food Safety Satisfaction

For food safety at the national level, the average satisfaction score was **7,45**, slightly lower than the organizational level. This result suggests that while SHs perceive food safety within their organizations as robust, there may be broader systemic challenges or variations in national food safety frameworks.

The higher satisfaction score at the **organizational level (8,04)** compared to the **country level (7,45)** indicates a greater confidence in internal organizational food safety systems relative to national frameworks.

Other concerns:

After that, SH were asked about other concerns in food safety innovations, 39% expressed diverse concerns about consumer education, regulatory processes and emerging risks. The key concerns identified from the open-ended responses are summarized as follows:

Regulatory Hurdles and Risk Assessment:

- **Overly stringent regulations:** Concerns about overly cautious regulatory frameworks that hinder innovation and the development of potentially beneficial products.
- **Inconsistent risk assessments:** Unequal risk assessments by regulatory authorities, particularly regarding traditional and novel foods.
- **Lack of clear guidelines:** Insufficient clarity in regulatory guidelines for emerging technologies and novel food ingredients.
- **Time-consuming approval processes:** Lengthy approval processes that delay market entry for innovative products.

Food Safety and Quality Assurance:

- **Emerging risks:** Concerns about emerging risks such as antimicrobial resistance, new diseases, and climate change-related impacts on food safety.
- **Food fraud and adulteration:** Risks associated with intentional mislabeling, substitution, or contamination of food products.
- **Quality control challenges:** Difficulties in ensuring quality and safety, especially in complex global supply chains.
- **Limited testing methods:** Lack of affordable and rapid testing methods to assess food safety and quality.

Consumer Safety and Education:

- **Consumer awareness and education:** Need for improved consumer education on food safety practices, including storage, preparation, and consumption.
- **Allergenicity and intolerance:** Growing concerns about food allergies and intolerances, especially in relation to novel food ingredients.

- Microbial safety: Risks associated with microbial contamination, particularly in fermented foods and products made with new raw materials.

Sustainability and Ethical Considerations:

- Sustainable practices: Balancing food safety with sustainable practices, such as regenerative agriculture and reduced plastic packaging.
- Ethical sourcing and production: Ensuring ethical and sustainable sourcing of ingredients and production methods.
- Impact on biodiversity: Potential impact of food innovations on biodiversity and ecosystem health.

Technological Advancements and Innovation:

- Adoption of new technologies: Slow adoption of advanced technologies in the food industry, hindering innovation.
- Data-driven decision-making: Need for improved data-driven approaches to food safety management and risk assessment.
- Predictive modeling: Development of predictive models to anticipate and mitigate emerging food safety risks.

Training about food safety topics:

Figure 28. SH response to need of training

The majority of SH (98%) expressed a strong belief in the value of attending training to enhance the safety and quality of food products in their areas (Figure 28). When asked to specify which topics should be prioritized in food safety training, several key themes emerged, emphasizing both foundational knowledge and the integration of modern tools and technologies. Below is a summary of these responses:

Foundational Knowledge and Skills

- Basic food safety principles: basic concepts like HACCP, GHP, and GMP. Foodborne pathogens (growth conditions, control measures).
- Educating consumers (labeling, handwashing).
- Hygiene and sanitation: Proper handwashing, cleaning, and disinfection techniques.
- Allergens management.
- Traceability: Implementing effective systems to track food products.

Emerging Issues and Technologies

- Climate change: impact of climate change on food safety risks and mitigation strategies.
- Novel foods and ingredients: Evaluating the safety of new food products and ingredients.
- Food fraud and adulteration: Recognizing and preventing.
- AI tools and machine learning: Utilizing for predictive modeling, risk assessment, and quality control.
- Sustainability and ethical sourcing: Balancing food safety with sustainable practices and ethical sourcing.

Regulatory Compliance and Risk Management

- Regulations: Keeping up-to-date with national and international food safety regulations.
- Risk assessment and management: Conducting and implementing effective strategies.
- Crisis management: Developing plans for responding to food safety crises.

We followed the survey by asking to select 5 areas from the observed innovations or solutions that address critical needs and shall be adopted more frequently by SH. The responses received had a strong emphasis is placed on pinpointing contamination sources along the food chain (Table 8). The responses are focused on enhancing food safety, reducing waste, and promoting sustainability. Key innovations include advanced detection methods, improved hygiene practices, novel preservation techniques, upcycling food waste, sustainable production, and leveraging AI and nanotechnology. Below are the responses received:

Table 8. Innovations recognized by SHs

Survey Question: Please select 5 areas where you have recently observed innovations or solutions that address critical needs and need to be adopted more frequently/by more SHs	
INNOVATIONS OBSERVED	Nº of times selected
Identifying the sources of contamination along the food chain	62
Up-cycling Food Waste into valuable resources	41

Developments in monitoring and detecting hazards along the food chain (e.g. use of sensors, rapid detection methods for pathogenic microorganisms, mycotoxins, chemical contaminants, etc.)	39
New technologies for hazards and risk prevention	35
New cleaning processes and hygiene procedures applying modern solutions	34
Alternatives to conventional preservation methods	25
New and alternatives ingredients or solutions improving the safety of the final product (e.g. plant/ microorganisms/protein sources/ precision fermentations)	23
New alternative food matrices (e.g. insects, in vitro-meat, food-by-products)	23
Contribution to the Whole Genome Sequencing (WGS) for the safety of food productions	22
Predictive and modelling tools (e.g., Developing predictive toxicology, predictive microbiology)	22
Artificial intelligence tools for improving food safety control in food chain	22
Better understanding and mitigation of antibiotic-resistant bacteria	21
Innovation in food packaging solutions and labelling for reduction/prevention of food waste and promotion of sustainability	20
Digital solutions to increase food chain transparency, safety and traceability	19
Novelties on hurdle technology applied to food productions	16
New analytical methods and regulatory needs for new food matrices	12
New standards and logistics applied to food productions	11
New solutions for safe storage and transport systems	9
Application of nanotechnologies to food productions	5
In silico and in vitro methods applied for sustainable safe food systems	4
Other	2

c. Training Focus Areas and Knowledge Exchange platform preferences:

In the third section of the survey (c), the SH were asked about training formats and materials beyond traditional classroom settings, the most selected formats were webinars and symposiums (Figure. 29).

Figure 29. Type of knowledge exchange platforms/initiatives

Online Learning:

- Online courses with multimedia elements (videos, infographics, images) were highly favored.
- Self-directed learning options like online self-study modules and eLearning platforms were also desired.
- Access to existing online training resources was requested.

Concise Information Delivery:

- Participants valued concise summaries, policy briefs, and risk profiles for efficient needs assessment.
- Electronic information delivery (e.g., PDFs) was preferred.

Interactive Learning:

- Serious games and real-time strategy approaches emerged as engaging training methods.

Additional Formats:

- Video tutorials, webinars, telepresence sessions, and applied in-person training sessions were also mentioned.

User-Focused Materials:

- Educational materials specifically designed for the target audience were desired.

This data suggests a strong preference for flexible, accessible, and user-friendly training materials. Online learning with multimedia elements and concise information delivery are key aspects, along with interactive and engaging formats.

We concluded the survey asking which are the topics to prioritize for training and courses (Table. 9).

Table 9. Topics selected by SHs for prioritization of training and courses.

What topics would you prioritize for training/courses?	
TOPICS	Nº of times selected
Emerging Risks	45
Food Safety Regulations and Compliance	42
Food Safety Culture	41
New tools for monitoring and detecting hazards	40
Food Microbiological Analysis and Techniques	38
Quality Control in Food Production	34
Interpretation of hazards, risks, probability, severity	29
Food Fraud	29
Sanitation and Hygiene Design in Food Processing	27
HACCP and process validation: Tools for monitoring and detecting hazards	26
Processing Environment Monitoring	25
Food Labeling and Packaging Compliance	25
Study of digital solutions and their potential in improving food safety	25
Allergen Management Best Practices (FAO/WHO Reports 2022)	20
New and alternative solutions/technologies for improving the final products (nanotechnologies, new ingredients, natural antimicrobial substances)	19
Quantitative Microbiological Risk Assessments (QMRA)	16
Qualitative Sampling and Testing: Methods & Statistics	13
Quantitative Microbiology	7
Horizon Scanning	5
Insurance and Food Safety	5
Other	4

2. One-on-One Interviews

A total of 85 SHs were interviewed from all four identified groups (industry, academia, public authority/ policymaker and civil society). These interviews were only conducted once the

Figure 30. SH diversion for one-on-one interviews

Figure 31. SH age diversion from one-on-one interviews

CATALYSE SH engagement Consent Forms were signed, these consent forms were collected through Microsoft Forms via a link/QR code (Annex 8).

The industry dominantly contributed to these interviews with 49%, while academia contributed 24% to these interviews, 20% were public authorities and 7% civil society as shown Figure 30. We also asked SH’s age groups, 45% were between 46-60 years age, followed by 40% in between 31-45 years old, 10% from >60 years in age, and only 5% between the age of 20-30 years old (Figure 31).

2.1. INDUSTRY SH INTERVIEWS

The industry SH one-on-one structured interview questionnaire is attached as Annex 9. In the demographic questionnaire for the consented interviews, 55% interviewee were women and 45% accounted to be men as shown in Figure 32. About age group, Figure 33 show dominated age group between 31-45 years (43%) and 46-60 years (43%).

Figure 32. Industry SH interview: gender diversion

Figure 33. Industry SH interviews: Age group diversion

We further asked to specify their food industry domain, and a dominating category were selected to be Food/Ingredient/ Equipment processor, followed by non-profit organization, B2B consultancies as represented in graph below in Figure 34.

Figure 34. Industry domain of Industry SH interviewed

The main challenges faced by food safety SH in developing innovative solutions, based on industry interviews:

Challenges:

- Financial Constraints:
 - Limited resources for R&D and implementation of advanced technologies (e.g., AI, blockchain).
 - SMEs struggle to compete with larger companies due to financial limitations.
- Regulatory Complexity:
 - Difficulty navigating constantly changing and inconsistent regulations across countries.
 - Slow and unclear approval processes for new technologies and ingredients.
 - Regulations may not keep pace with innovation, hindering implementation.
- Resistance to Change:
 - Traditional practices and cultural resistance to adopting new methods.
 - Lack of awareness of current trends and innovations among some decision-makers.
- Human Resources:
 - Shortage of qualified food safety professionals.
 - Limited training and education for workers, especially in new technologies.
 - Lack of collaboration between industry, academia, and startups.
- Other Challenges:
 - Complex supply chains pose traceability and contamination risks.
 - Consumer awareness of food safety issues can be low.
 - Balancing cost-effectiveness with innovation and safety.
 - Emerging contaminants and the need for rapid response solutions.

Overall, overcoming these challenges requires a multifaceted approach involving industry, government, and academia. By investing in innovation, streamlining regulations, and promoting collaboration, we can ensure a safer and more sustainable food supply chain.

Industry SH Suggestions and Solutions:

- Harmonization and Simplification of Regulations: Implementing clearer, unified regulations across the EU would streamline food safety practices.
- Improved Communication and Collaboration: Increased dialogue between SH (EFSA, member states, producers, cheesemongers) can lead to better information sharing and a more collective approach.
- Education and Training Programs: Investing in training for all levels of the food chain, from producers to cheesemongers, is crucial for building awareness and knowledge.

- **Financial Incentives:** Creating financial incentives, such as grants or tax breaks, can encourage SMEs to adopt innovative food safety solutions.
- **Focus on Practical Resources:** Developing easily accessible resources like SOPs (Standard Operating Procedures) and low-cost solutions can greatly benefit SMEs.
- **Support SMEs:** Develop resources and guidance specifically for small and medium-sized enterprises.

Here's a breakdown of the most promising food safety innovations discussed:

Rapid Detection Methods:

- Faster and cheaper ways to detect pathogens like bacteria and contaminants.
- Technologies like PCR (polymerase chain reaction) and NIR (near-infrared spectroscopy) are being explored.
- Portable testing tools for on-site quality control.

Advanced Traceability:

- Blockchain technology for real-time tracking of food origin and movement throughout the supply chain.
- This helps identify contamination sources quicker and minimize recall impact.

Data Analytics and AI:

- AI-powered analysis predicts potential risks, improves contamination detection, and identifies factors affecting food spoilage.
- Combining AI with data from sensors and IoT devices enables proactive measures.

Intelligent Packaging:

- Packaging with built-in sensors monitor temperature or chemical changes, indicating potential spoilage.
- This adds an extra layer of safety for consumers.

Other Promising Innovations:

- **Biotechnology:** Producing new protein sources, like lab-grown meat, to address growing protein demand.
- **CRISPR:** Gene editing for potential applications in agriculture, but requires careful regulation.
- **Non-thermal Pasteurization:** Using low-temperature methods to preserve food quality while reducing spoilage.
- **Hygienic Design:** Improved equipment design for easier cleaning and reduced contamination risk.

Challenges and Considerations:

- **Cost:** Implementing some innovations can be expensive, especially for small producers.
- **Regulations:** New technologies like CRISPR may require clear regulations to ensure safety.
- **Education and Training:** Workforce needs proper training to understand and utilize new technologies effectively.
- **Consumer Awareness:** Public education is needed to build trust in new food safety measures.

Overall, the future of food safety with advancements in rapid detection, intelligent systems, and data-driven approaches. Collaboration among SHs is crucial to navigate costs, regulations, and ensure wider adoption of these innovations.

Figure 35. Industry SH interviews Barrier Ranking

We asked c SHs to rank six identified based on perceived importance which are the primary barriers to innovation in food safety that they as SHs encounter and have impact. The results are as depicted in Figure 35:

1. **Costs (Barrier C)** - Ranked as the most critical (1st) barrier, indicating financial constraints as the primary challenge in food safety.
2. **Regulation (Barrier B)** - Considered the 2nd most significant barrier, highlighting issues related to regulatory compliance and complexity.
3. **Resistance to Change (Barrier F)** - Ranked 3rd, suggesting that cultural or organizational inertia is a notable obstacle.
4. **Lack of Awareness (Barrier D)** - Placed 4th, pointing to insufficient knowledge or understanding of food safety practices.
5. **Lack of Collaboration (Barrier A)** - Ranked 5th, underlining the need for improved cooperation among SHs.
6. **Lack of Dissemination to Small/Traditional Producers (Barrier E)** - Identified as the least critical (6th), although still a notable challenge.

Based on the provided responses, the key challenges in adopting and implementing innovative food safety solutions include:

Resource Constraints:

- Time and Personnel: Allocating sufficient time and personnel to research, implement, and maintain new food safety technologies.

- **Financial Limitations:** Investing in innovative solutions can be costly, especially for smaller businesses.

Technological Limitations:

- **Lack of Advanced Analytical Tools:** Difficulty in detecting emerging contaminants like microplastics.
- **Challenges in Authenticity Tracking:** Limited methodologies for verifying the origin and authenticity of food products.

Regulatory Hurdles:

- **Complex and Varying Regulations:** Different regulations across countries can hinder the adoption of innovative solutions.
- **Slow Approval Processes:** Time-consuming procedures for approving new technologies and ingredients.

Practical Implementation Challenges:

- **Small-Scale Production Constraints:** Limited resources and expertise for small producers to implement advanced food safety practices.
- **Human Factor:** Ensuring consistent adherence to food safety protocols and addressing issues like hygiene and training.

Knowledge and Awareness:

- **Lack of Information and Training:** Limited access to information and training on food safety best practices, particularly for small producers and food handlers.

Overcoming these challenges requires a collaborative effort involving industry, regulators, and researchers. By sharing knowledge, investing in research, and streamlining regulations, it is possible to accelerate the adoption of innovative food safety solutions.

Response summary of Knowledge Exchange Preferences and Challenges by Industry SHs:**Preferred Learning Methods:**

- **Short, accessible formats:** People favor information delivered in ways that are easy to access and consume, like webinars, newsletters, and short articles. Online options are preferred for geographically dispersed learners or those with limited travel budgets.
- **Interactive elements:** Q&A sessions with experts and opportunities to ask questions are valued.
- **Practical application:** Learning is best retained when combined with practical skills. Hands-on training workshops are a popular choice.
- **Offline options:** Some learners prefer printed materials (books, articles) or in-person conferences and seminars.

Challenges in Accessing Knowledge:

- **Information overload:** Filtering through a vast amount of information and identifying reliable sources can be difficult.
- **Accessibility issues:** Paywalled content, language barriers, and limited internet access in some regions pose obstacles.
- **Specificity:** Finding information tailored to a specific business or production method can be challenging.

- **Timing constraints:** Seasonal businesses face limited availability for training during peak times.
- **Lack of awareness:** Some individuals may not be aware of available resources or how to access them.

Additional points:

- Industry associations can be a valuable source of information and networking.
- Refreshing existing knowledge through regular training is important for food safety professionals.

Food Safety Knowledge Exchange Needs Summary

This interview segment highlighted a variety of preferences for food safety knowledge exchange. Here's a breakdown of the key findings:

Preferred Platforms:

- **Variety is Key:** There's no one-size-fits-all solution. People prefer a mix of online and offline resources.
- **Digital Platforms:** Popular options include online databases, websites, mobile apps, webinars, and e-learning courses.
- **Social Learning:** Interactive platforms fostering discussions and knowledge sharing among peers are highly valued.
- **Offline Learning:** In-person visits, conferences, and hands-on training in pilot plants are crucial for practical learning.

Content Preferences:

- **Focus on Application:** People want real-world examples, case studies, and best practices to understand how to implement food safety knowledge.
- **Targeted Information:** Content tailored to specific industries and roles is beneficial.
- **Accessibility:** Short, mobile-friendly content allows busy professionals to access information on the go.
- **Regulation Updates:** Regular updates on EU regulations and their impact are important.
- **Scientific Knowledge:** Scientific data and studies are valuable for some users.

Additional Considerations:

- **EU Platform Improvement:** Participants suggested improvements to the EU's knowledge exchange webpage.
- **Micro-credentials:** Short, focused online training modules are popular for gaining specific skills.
- **Targeting:** Platforms should consider demographics and preferred learning styles when designing content.
- **Smaller Producers:** Personalized approaches and financial support for implementing innovations are crucial for them.

Key Skills and Knowledge:

- **Technical Expertise:**
 - Microbiology
 - Food Science and Technology

- HACCP Principles
- Regulatory Knowledge
- **Soft Skills:**
 - Communication Skills
 - Problem-Solving
 - Data Literacy
 - Innovation Skills
- **Practical Skills:**
 - Understanding of Production Processes
 - Quality Control Techniques
 - Sensory Evaluation

Additional Needs:

- **Consumer Education:**
 - Teaching children about basic food science and healthy eating habits.
 - Dispelling misconceptions about processed foods.
- **Bridging the Gap:**
 - Fostering collaboration between regulatory experts and engineers.
 - Promoting understanding between scientists and food industry professionals.
- **Continuous Learning:**
 - Staying updated on the latest food safety trends and technologies.
 - Encouraging a culture of lifelong learning.

In conclusion, food safety professionals need a combination of technical skills, soft skills, and practical experience. They should be well-versed in regulatory requirements, understand the latest scientific advancements, and be able to communicate effectively with a diverse range of SHs.

Collective responses for Food Safety Training Gaps and Needs**Key Findings:**

- **Repetitive basic knowledge training:** Many workers already have a basic understanding of food safety but lack training on more specific topics.
- **Difficulties applying theory:** Training often doesn't translate well to real-world situations in different production facilities.
- **Lack of hygiene understanding:** Workers may not fully understand the importance of hygiene practices and their impact on safety.
- **Limited access to training:** SMEs (small and medium-sized enterprises) often struggle to find affordable and accessible training resources.
- **Language barriers:** Training materials and communication may not be available in relevant languages for all food industry workers.

Needs:

- **Training on specific topics:** Workers need training that goes beyond basic hygiene and covers specific pathogens, product handling, and regulations.
- **Practical application:** Training should be designed to help workers apply knowledge in their specific workplaces.
- **Focus on hygiene:** Increased emphasis on the importance of hygiene practices and their impact on food safety.

- **Accessible training resources:** Develop affordable and accessible training materials (online and offline) for SMEs.
- **Multilingual resources:** Training materials and communication should be available in various languages.

Summary of Effective Educational Resources and Training Formats

Desired Features:

- **Basic knowledge for SMEs:** Cater to the needs of SMEs with basic knowledge training materials.
- **In-house and adaptable training:** Offer in-house training programs tailored to specific worker roles within a company.
- **Variety of formats:** Provide training in various formats like online courses, short videos, one-pagers, and webinars.
- **Connection to practical application:** Ensure a clear link between theoretical knowledge and everyday work practices.
- **Offline and online options:** Combine both online and offline learning methods for better understanding and retention.
- **Focus on cheese defects:** Develop training materials specifically for cheesemongers on identifying safe and unsafe product changes.

Summary of Best Practices for Reaching Small Producers

Effective Strategies:

- **Utilize existing networks:** Leverage professional organizations and regional associations to reach small producers.
- **Simple and clear communication:** Develop clear, concise, and easy-to-understand training materials.
- **Local outreach:** Implement local physical presence or collaborate with local organizations for better reach.
- **Practical resources:** Provide practical guides and access to experts for specific needs of small producers.
- **Financial incentives:** Offer financial assistance or subsidized training programs for SMEs.
- **Multilingual support:** Offer training materials and communication channels in relevant languages.

Summary of Expected Impact of the CoP (Community of Practice)

Potential Benefits:

- **Improved food safety culture:** Promote a culture of food safety awareness and best practices.
- **Knowledge sharing and innovation:** Facilitate knowledge exchange and adoption of innovative food safety solutions.
- **Improved communication and collaboration:** Enhance communication and collaboration across the food sector.
- **Increased access to resources:** Provide SMEs with better access to training resources and expert support.
- **Stronger food safety network:** Build a cohesive food safety community for knowledge sharing and problem-solving.

- **Dissemination of best practices:** Encourage the spread of best practices in food safety throughout the industry.

Challenges:

- **Reaching small producers:** Difficulties in effectively reaching and engaging the smallest producers within the industry.
- **Language barriers:** Overcoming language barriers to ensure all food industry workers have access to information.
- **Sustainability:** Ensuring the long-term sustainability and effectiveness of the CoP initiative.

Overall, the CoP has the potential to significantly improve food safety practices across the industry, especially for SMEs. By addressing the identified training gaps and utilizing effective outreach strategies, the CoP can empower food producers with the knowledge and resources they need to ensure safe and high-quality food products.

2.2. ACADEMIA SH INTERVIEWS:

The one-on-one SH interviews could only go forward if the interviewee had signed the official engagement consent forms. The responses were 100% ‘yes’ for the indication of signed consent forms prior to commencing with the interview. The Academia SH interviews are attached as Annex 10. The graphs provide a demographic breakdown of academia SH interviewees based on gender and age. The gender division chart indicates that 60% of the participants are women, while 40% are men, showing a higher representation of female SHs. The age distribution graph reveals that the majority of participants fall into the 46-60 years age group, comprising 45% of the total respondents. This is followed by the 31-45 years group, which accounts for 35%, while the 20-30 years and >60 years age categories represent 15% and 5%, respectively. These results highlight a predominance of middle-aged individuals and a balanced gender representation among the respondents (Figure 36 and 37).

Figure 36. Gender Diversion for Academia SHs responding to one-on-one interviews

Figure 37. Age Group Diversion for Academia SHs responding to one-on-one interviews

Summary of Challenges and Obstacles in Food Safety Innovations responded by academia SHs:

Key Challenges:

- **Funding:** Limited financial resources hinder research and development, especially for small-scale projects.
- **Knowledge Gaps:** Lack of understanding in areas like genetics, emerging contaminants, and consumer behavior.
- **Regulatory Hurdles:** Complex and ever-changing regulations can slow down the adoption of new technologies and practices.
- **Industry Resistance:** Food industry reluctance to adopt new solutions due to cost, complexity, and fear of consumer backlash.
- **Communication and Collaboration:** Ineffective communication and collaboration between academia, industry, and regulatory bodies.
- **Scaling Up:** Difficulty in translating laboratory-scale innovations to industrial settings.
- **Consumer Acceptance:** Ensuring consumer acceptance of new technologies and food products.
- **Global Challenges:** Addressing global issues like antibiotic resistance and climate change impact on food safety.

Obstacles:

- **Lack of standardized methods:** Difficulty in comparing and validating different food safety methods.
- **Limited knowledge sharing:** Inefficient communication and collaboration among SHs.
- **Complex regulatory landscape:** Varying regulations across countries and regions.
- **Consumer perceptions:** Misconceptions and fears about new technologies and food processing methods.
- **Cost and resource constraints:** Limited financial resources and human capital.
- **Technical challenges:** Difficulty in developing and implementing reliable and cost-effective technologies.

Overcoming these challenges requires:

- **Increased collaboration:** Fostering stronger partnerships between academia, industry, and regulatory bodies.
- **Shared knowledge and resources:** Sharing expertise and resources to accelerate innovation.
- **Standardized methods:** Developing standardized protocols for testing and validation.
- **Consumer education:** Raising awareness about the benefits of food safety innovations.
- **Regulatory flexibility:** Adapting regulations to facilitate innovation while ensuring safety.
- **Investing in research and development:** Supporting research to address emerging food safety challenges.
- **Risk assessment and management:** Implementing robust risk assessment and management strategies.
- **Data-driven decision-making:** Utilizing data analytics to identify trends and inform decision-making.

By working together, SH can address these challenges and drive innovation in food safety, ultimately ensuring a safer and more sustainable food supply.

The interview identified several challenges hindering progress in food safety innovation:

- **Lack of awareness:** Startups and small producers need accessible networking and training opportunities.
- **Dissemination of knowledge:** Training courses and direct engagement are needed to encourage innovation.
- **Resistance to change:** Traditional producers need to be involved and offered solutions addressing their specific problems.
- **Excessive regulations:** Collaboration is needed to advocate for regulations fostering innovation, not hindering it.
- **Competition in food safety:** Collaboration is crucial to share best practices and prevent outbreaks.
- **Cleaning and hygiene:** Competence and education are critical for effective cleaning practices.
- **Food chain transparency:** Traceability throughout the chain is necessary to identify and address contamination points.
- **Knowledge exchange:** Improved communication and collaboration among researchers, academia, and industry is essential.

Proposed solutions:

- **Networking events:** Make knowledge sharing accessible online, locally, and with cost-coverage.
- **Training programs:** Offer relevant training and incentives to encourage innovation.
- **Collaborative problem solving:** Engage traditional producers to identify their challenges and tailor solutions.
- **Industry collaboration:** Advocate for regulations promoting innovation and transparency.
- **Sharing best practices:** Encourage open communication and sharing of best practices on food safety solutions.
- **Hygiene training:** Prioritize training and education for cleaning personnel.
- **Chain-wide traceability:** Implement controls and communication throughout the food chain.
- **Knowledge transfer:** Create "transfer departments" to bridge the gap between research and industry application.

The interview highlights the importance of a collaborative approach to food safety. By sharing knowledge, fostering innovation, and creating transparent food chains, SHs can work together to ensure safe and sustainable food production.

Current Food Safety Concerns:

- **Rapid detection of microorganisms and allergens:** Traditional methods can be slow and cumbersome.

- **Preservatives:** Synthetic chemical preservatives raise health concerns, prompting a need for safer alternatives.
- **Microplastics and emerging contaminants:** New knowledge about these contaminants necessitates improved detection and mitigation strategies.
- **Hygienic design and cleaning:** Current practices may not be sufficient to prevent contamination in complex equipment.
- **Consumer acceptance of new technologies:** Some novel food safety techniques face resistance from consumers.

We asked civil society SHs to rank six identified based on perceived importance which are the primary barriers to innovation in food safety that they as SH encounter and have impact. The results are as depicted in Figure 38. The barrier ranked as most important is "C. Costs", indicating that financial constraints are perceived as the primary hindrance to food safety implementation. This is followed by "D. Lack of Awareness" as the second-ranked barrier, highlighting the importance of education and knowledge dissemination. "E. Lack of Dissemination to Small/Traditional Producers" ranks third, suggesting a significant need for targeted communication and support for smaller SHs. The fourth-ranked barrier is "B. Regulation", pointing to challenges associated with compliance and regulatory frameworks. "A. Lack of Collaboration" is identified as the fifth-ranked issue, reflecting the need for improved SH cooperation. Finally, "F. Resistance to Change" is ranked sixth, indicating that while resistance exists, it is perceived as the least critical barrier. Overall, the data emphasizes financial and knowledge-related challenges as the most pressing concerns for food safety improvements.

Figure 38. Innovation Barriers Ranked by Academia SHs during one-on-one interviews

Promising Innovations Observed:

Rapid Detection Methods:

- Whole genome sequencing (WGS) for faster outbreak investigation and root cause analysis.
- Point-of-use diagnostics for on-site pathogen and contaminant detection.

Advanced Monitoring and Control:

- Smart packaging with real-time monitoring capabilities.

- Biosensors for continuous monitoring of food quality parameters.
- Artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning for predictive risk modeling.

Alternative Preservation Techniques:

- High-Pressure Processing (HPP) for extending shelf life without harsh heat treatments.
- Controlled release packaging to deliver precise amounts of preservatives.
- Bacteriophages (viruses that target specific bacteria) as biocontrol agents.

Improved Hygiene and Design:

- Robotic cleaning systems for consistent and thorough sanitation.
- Hygienic design principles for easier cleaning and reduced contamination risk.
- Big data analytics to identify and address hygiene weaknesses.

Collaborative Food Safety Culture:

- Improved communication and knowledge sharing between SHs.
- User-friendly educational methods for industry personnel.
- Collaborative data science efforts to identify emerging risks.

Challenges and Opportunities:

- Validation and integration of new technologies: Ensuring compatibility with existing systems is crucial.
- Consumer education and acceptance: Building trust in new food safety practices is essential.
- Cost-effectiveness: Making innovations affordable for widespread adoption.

The food industry is witnessing a surge in promising innovations addressing food safety challenges. By embracing these advancements and fostering collaboration, SHs can ensure a safer and more sustainable food supply for all.

The summary of academic SH interviews emphasizes the importance of rapid detection methods, advanced monitoring, alternative preservation, improved hygiene, and a collaborative food safety culture. Challenges remain in validation, consumer acceptance, and cost-effectiveness, requiring focused efforts. The report highlights the potential of AI, big data, and user-friendly technology for food safety.

Summary of Food Safety Knowledge Exchange and Training Needs:**Knowledge Exchange:**

- **Preferred Methods:** Participants prefer a variety of methods including scientific literature, conferences, workshops, online resources (webinars, newsletters, email lists), and social media (with reservations).

- **Challenges:** Information overload, difficulty filtering reliable and relevant information, lack of clear communication between academia and industry.
- **Desired Platforms:** Centralized information platforms, curated databases, thematic webinars, podcasts (research-focused and industry-focused).

Training:

- **Desired Formats:** Interactive formats are preferred, including short videos, case studies, simulations, blended learning (online & in-person), gamified learning, and mobile applications.
- **Content Needs:** Training should be tailored to specific roles and sectors. Key content areas include:
 - Food safety regulations and standards
 - Food microbiology
 - Innovation and communication skills
 - Practical skills for food handling and hygiene
 - Risk assessment and mitigation strategies
- **Gaps and Needs:**
 - Training for top management
 - Media training for researchers to improve knowledge communication
 - Increased awareness of specific risks (e.g., packaging materials)
 - Training for small and medium-sized companies
 - More practical training for researchers
 - Lifelong learning opportunities
 - Communication and information exchange between academia and industry

Overall Themes:

- Importance of accessible, engaging, and interactive training formats.
- Need for clear communication and knowledge transfer between researchers and industry professionals.
- Requirement for training tailored to specific roles and sectors.
- Importance of lifelong learning and continuous improvement in food safety practices.

Additional Notes:

- The level of complexity of training materials should be adapted to the target audience.
- Multi-lingual resources are needed to reach a wider audience.
- Platforms should offer ongoing support, refresher courses, and track user progress.

Recommendations to reach Small Producers:

- **Key Challenges:** Lack of awareness, limited resources, time constraints.
- **Effective Strategies:**
 - **Multi-channel communication:** Utilize traditional (newspapers, radio) and digital (social media, email) channels.
 - **Local Partnerships:** Collaborate with agricultural extensions, farmers' markets, and industry associations.

- **Accessible Resources:** Develop easy-to-understand training materials in local languages.
- **Hands-on Learning:** Organize workshops and training sessions in convenient locations.
- **Mentorship Programs:** Connect experienced CoP members with small producers for guidance.
- **Success Stories:** Highlight examples to encourage participation.
- **Incentives:** Offer benefits like access to shared resources or discounted services.

Expected Impact of CoP:

- **Improved Food Safety Practices:** Increased knowledge and implementation of best practices.
- **Enhanced Innovation Adoption:** Streamlined pathway for translating research into practice.
- **Knowledge Dissemination:** Sharing of best practices and national expertise across borders.
- **SH Collaboration:** Fostering communication and collaboration among producers, consumers, and policymakers.
- **Capacity Building:** Equipping individuals and organizations with the necessary knowledge and skills.

Key Success Factors:

- **Active Member Participation:** Strong engagement is crucial for achieving the CoP's goals.
- **Targeted Communication:** Tailoring messages and resources to specific audiences.
- **Focus on Practical Application:** Providing actionable solutions and promoting knowledge translation.
- **Continuous Evaluation:** Regularly assessing impact and adapting strategies for optimal results.

Overall, the CoP has the potential to significantly improve food safety practices by raising awareness, facilitating innovation adoption, and fostering collaboration across the food system.

2.3. Public Authority SH Interviews

The one-on-one SH interviews could only go forward if the SH had signed the official engagement consent forms. The responses were 100% ‘yes’ for the indication of signed consent forms prior to commencing with the interview. The public authority / policymaker interview questionnaire is attached as Annex 11. The graphs provide demographic insights into public authority SH interviewees based on **gender** and **age group**. In the gender division graph, **71%** of the interviewees are women, while **29%** are men, with no respondents identifying as "Other" or choosing "Prefer not to say." This reflects a significant gender imbalance, with a dominant representation of female SHs. The age group distribution indicates that the majority of respondents (**53%**) fall within the **46-60 years** category, followed by **35%** in the **31-45 years** range. Additionally, **12%** of the SHs are aged **>60 years**, and there are no participants from the **20-30 years** age group. These findings highlight a predominantly middle-aged and female representation among public authority SHs.

Figure 39. Gender Diversion for Public Authority/ Policymakers responding to one-on-one interviews

Figure 40. Age group diversion for Public Authority/Policymakers respondents

Figure 41 illustrates the specific domains of public authority to which the SHs belong, divided into five categories. The two largest segments, each comprising 33%, represent SHs in "Public Authorities responsible for risk management" and those in "Public Authorities responsible for risk assessment" within Member States. A smaller proportion of SHs, 19%, are categorized under "Other", indicating varied roles not specified in the main categories. 10% of the respondents

Figure 41. Specific domain specified by public authority SHs

belong to "Policymakers at the national and international levels", including ministries and entities such as the European Commission. The smallest segment, at 5%, includes SHs from "Public Authorities at international levels" such as EFSA, ECHA, and EMA. These findings highlight a concentration of SHs in national-level risk management and assessment roles, with limited representation from policymakers and international public authorities. Some respondents responded to 'other' domain specified in Table 10. All interviewed SHs indicated the names of their present/past working institutions mentioned in Table 11.

Table 10. 'OTHER' domain answered by public authority SHs

<i>"Other" domain answers were:</i>
<i>"Developer of educational programs for the government representatives";</i>
<i>"Risk assessor in national level";</i>
<i>"Official Control Laboratory of Central Authority";</i>
<i>"Although we are not the designated competent authority, we lead on the management and prevention and data collection"</i>

Table 11. Present/Past work institutions of Public Authority SHs responds:

Indication of Institution the public authority SH (interviewee) belongs to:
Ex-Hungarian food safety officer
ANSES
FAO
QFTP (Ukrainian-Swiss program)
Training Center of the State Research Institute for Laboratory Diagnostics and Veterinary and Sanitary Expertise
EFSA
UK Food Standards Agency
Croatian Agency for Agriculture and Food
Finnish Food Authority
National Food Chain Safety Office (Hungary)
Food safety and vet (BLV)
FSVO Federal Food Safety and Veterinary Office
UK Health Security Agency
Food Standards Scotland

Response Summary of PUBLIC AUTHORITY/ POLICYMAKERS SH Concerns, Challenges, and Obstacles in Food Safety:

Disruption and Misalignment Between Policy, Innovation, and Market Dynamics:

Policy-Innovation Gaps: Current policies often move faster than industries can adapt, creating misalignment. Long-term sustainability goals (e.g., climate change,

circular economy) are disconnected from immediate market demands and industrial readiness.

Pacing Issues: Policies need to account for the time required for industries to adopt innovations, avoiding exacerbating the gap between policy and practice.

Destructive vs. Incremental Innovation: Disruptive innovations, like GMOs, tend to outpace regulatory frameworks, while incremental innovations in agriculture (e.g., gradual adoption of sustainable practices) occur more slowly.

Knowledge Gaps and Lack of Industry Readiness:

Inadequate Understanding: Manufacturers and producers often lack understanding of critical concepts like microbiological criteria, traceability, sampling methods, and regulatory frameworks, which hampers compliance and safety.

Competence Issues: Small businesses, particularly SMEs, often lack the technical expertise, resources, and guidance to implement food safety practices effectively.

Insufficient Innovation Uptake: Financial constraints and lack of incentives prevent industries from adopting preventative measures or new technologies, often leading to higher costs when problems arise later.

Challenges in Risk Assessment and Regulation:

Data Gaps: Insufficient data on contaminants (e.g., mycotoxins, microplastics, nanoplastics), chemical interactions, and the impact of climate change hinders effective risk assessment.

Slow Legislative Adaptation: Regulation often lags behind scientific and market developments, as seen with novel foods and food fraud. Bureaucratic processes delay the recognition of new methods and technologies.

Resource Constraints: Regulatory bodies face shortages of funding, staff, and expertise, limiting their ability to enforce compliance, conduct inspections, and support innovation.

Food Safety Hazards

Chemical and Microbiological Contaminants: Persistent issues include pesticides, zoonoses (e.g., listeria, salmonella), antimicrobial resistance, and emerging threats like microplastics and climate change-related contamination.

Food Fraud: Fraudulent activities (e.g., ingredient or origin mislabeling) present unique challenges due to the lack of regulatory frameworks for detection and prosecution.

Novel Foods: The rapid emergence of trends (e.g., edible insects) outpaces the ability of researchers and regulators to ensure safety.

Public and Practitioner Education

Low Awareness: Both consumers and practitioners often lack understanding of basic food safety practices (e.g., kitchen hygiene, cross-contamination prevention).

Misinformation: Social media accelerates the spread of new food trends, often bypassing proper safety vetting.

Training Gaps: Training initiatives fail to reach those most in need, such as small operators and unregulated producers.

Systemic Challenges in Implementation

Economic and Financial Barriers: The high costs of compliance, combined with narrow profit margins, discourage investment in innovative safety solutions.

Fragmented Communication: Poor collaboration between academia, industry, and regulators hinders the development and implementation of solutions.

Complex Supply Chains: Globalization has increased supply chain complexity, amplifying risks from contamination and traceability challenges.

Specific Challenges Highlighted by SHs

Operational Inefficiencies: Outdated methods and lack of modernization within laboratories and inspection systems lead to inconsistencies in safety testing.

Human Resource Issues: Low salaries, high turnover, and inadequate training in government agencies and inspection services undermine effective oversight.

War and Crises: In conflict zones, infrastructure damage, power outages, and disrupted supply chains further complicate food safety efforts.

Recommendations for Addressing Food Safety Challenges

Policy Alignment and Strategic Planning:

- Integrate sustainability and innovation goals into actionable, paced strategies.
- Strengthen connections between regulators, industries, and academic researchers.

Education and Training:

- Provide targeted training for SMEs and underrepresented sectors.
- Raise public awareness about food safety practices and risks.

Enhanced Regulation and Monitoring:

- Streamline regulatory processes to adapt quickly to novel foods and emerging risks.
- Improve funding and staffing for regulatory bodies to ensure consistent enforcement.

Encourage Collaboration:

- Foster cross-sector communication to align one-health approaches with industry needs.
- Build trust between industry and regulators to promote data sharing and innovation.

Investment in Research and Innovation:

- Focus research funding on critical areas like mycotoxins, antimicrobial resistance, and sustainable practices.
- Support small-scale, focused international projects to bridge specific knowledge gaps.

By addressing these systemic issues through collaborative and well-paced initiatives, SHs can improve food safety outcomes across industries and regions.

Key Challenges in Advancing Food Safety

Economic Barriers

- **Funding Prioritization:** While financial resources exist, they are often misaligned with priorities. Economic crises amplify funding constraints, particularly for SMEs.

- **Rising Costs:** The increasing costs of implementing food safety measures discourage investment, especially for smaller operators.

Regulatory Rigidities

- **Inflexible Legislation:** Outdated and slow-to-adapt regulations hinder innovation and prevent the adoption of alternative methods.
- **Complex Processes:** Legislative updates and implementation are often delayed by bureaucratic inefficiencies and political constraints.
- **Lack of Clarity:** Industry operators face difficulties understanding legal requirements, limiting compliance and engagement.

Resistance to Change

- Cultural and behavioral inertia among producers, especially traditional and small-scale operators, slows the adoption of new technologies.
- Skepticism toward innovative practices persists, fueled by inadequate communication of their cost-effectiveness and benefits.

Insufficient Collaboration and Communication

- Fragmented communication channels between regulators, industry, and researchers result in inconsistent knowledge sharing and duplication of efforts.
- Lack of trust, particularly between small operators and large institutions, inhibits cooperative initiatives.
- The absence of a structured, centralized system for information dissemination leads to gaps in awareness and action.

Capacity Limitations

- **Workforce Deficiencies:** There is a shortage of skilled staff in regulatory bodies and industry.
- **Knowledge Gaps:** Operators, especially SMEs, often lack the expertise and training needed to meet food safety requirements.
- **Limited Research:** Insufficient resources and time restrict research into emerging threats and innovative solutions.

Facilitators of Progress:

Policy and Economic Incentives

- **Subsidies and Grants:** Redirecting financial tools to incentivize sustainable and innovative technologies in agriculture and food production.
- **Tax Incentives:** Offering fiscal benefits to companies implementing advanced food safety measures.
- **Risk-Based Approaches:** Simplifying regulations to focus on high-risk areas, reducing compliance burdens for low-risk operations.

Collaboration and Networking

- **Building Networks:** Dedicated platforms like FSRN and PATH-SAFE facilitate SH engagement, knowledge sharing, and coordinated responses.

- **Engaging SMEs:** Regional and local associations can bridge trust gaps and provide targeted support.
- **Involving Experts Early:** Collaboration with industry representatives and scientific communities during policy formulation enhances feasibility and compliance.

Effective Communication Strategies

- **Targeted Outreach:** Tailored training programs for small operators, available in multiple languages, ensure inclusivity.
- **Simplified Messaging:** Using everyday language and practical examples helps bridge information asymmetry between experts and non-experts.
- **Centralized Dissemination:** Establishing a central authority for clear, consistent communication reduces confusion and enhances alignment across SHs.

Education and Capacity Building

- **Training Programs:** Continuous education for industry operators, regulators, and service providers builds competence and confidence in food safety systems.
- **Consumer Awareness:** Promoting the benefits of safe products over informal market alternatives fosters demand for higher standards.
- **Investing in Human Resources:** Allocating resources to recruit, train, and retain skilled professionals addresses workforce shortages.

Promoting Cultural and Behavioral Change

- **Highlighting Benefits:** Clear demonstrations of cost savings, efficiency, and long-term gains from adopting food safety innovations.
- **Incentivizing Change:** Rewarding producers and operators who adopt sustainable and safe practices encourages broader uptake.
- **Learning from Indigenous Practices:** Embracing traditional and sustainable methods as a foundation for modern systems.

Innovative Solutions and Research

- **Funding Research:** Increasing support for applied research to tackle emerging food safety challenges.
- **Leveraging Technology:** Encouraging digital tools and data analytics to enhance risk assessments and monitoring systems.

Most Promising Innovations:

1. Biotechnology and Bioengineering

- Lab-grown meat and alternative protein sources to meet rising protein demands.
- Bioengineered microorganisms for environmental clean-up (e.g., microplastics).
- CRISPR for agricultural advancements, though requiring regulatory clarity.

2. Data and AI-Driven Solutions

- AI and large language models for data analysis in food production and safety.
- Big data tools for tracing contamination, improving food authenticity, and preventing obesity and cardiovascular diseases.
- 3. Advanced Genomics and Microbiology**
 - Whole Genome Sequencing (WGS) for pathogen surveillance, outbreak tracing, and root cause analysis.
 - OMICS technologies (e.g., NGS) for big data generation and analysis in food systems.
- 4. Sustainable and Consumer-Focused Solutions**
 - Smart packaging to monitor product conditions during transport.
 - Urban gardening and organic production for localized food sustainability.
 - Microbiome research to enhance health benefits through food.
- 5. Innovative Food Safety Tools**
 - Rapid testing methods for microbiological safety, such as STEC-specific tests.
 - Multi-component chromatographic analyses for drug residues.
 - Traceability systems using IT solutions for better collaboration among SHs.
- 6. Education and Cultural Change**
 - Food safety education integrated into school curriculums.
 - Promoting food safety culture with a focus on transparency and strategic thinking.

We asked public authority SH to rank six identified based on perceived importance which are the primary barriers to innovation in food safety that they as SHs encounter and have impact (Figure 42). The barrier “C. Costs” retains its position as the most critical barrier (1st), highlighting the significant financial challenges in implementing food safety measures. “D. Lack of Awareness” is ranked as the 2nd most important barrier, emphasizing a continued need for improved education and awareness regarding food safety practices. The 3rd ranked barrier, “B. Regulation”, reflects ongoing concerns related to regulatory compliance and frameworks. “A. Lack of Collaboration” holds the 4th position, pointing to the necessity for better coordination among SHs. “F. Resistance to Change”, ranked 5th, signifies an existing but relatively moderate challenge to adapting new food safety measures. Finally, “E. Lack of Dissemination to

Small/Traditional Producers” is identified as the 6th ranked barrier, suggesting that while it remains an issue, it is perceived as the least critical compared to others.

Figure 42. Innovation barrier ranking recognized by Public Authority/ Policymaker responding to one-on-one interviews

Needs to Facilitate Uptake of Innovations:

Regulatory and Governance Support

- Clear and adaptive regulations to align with innovations like CRISPR and lab-grown meat.
- Simplified legal frameworks for better compliance and reduced resistance.

Capacity Building and Training

- International expertise to train local SHs, creating a knowledge cascade.
- Education programs for inspectors, producers, and the public to reduce fear and improve cooperation.

Financial and Technical Resources

- Funding for infrastructure, tools, and consumables to implement innovations.
- Grants to develop educational content and incentivize innovation uptake.

Technology Development

- Pipelines to manage and analyze big data with advanced AI tools.
- Access to cutting-edge equipment for rapid testing and WGS-based surveillance.

Collaborative Efforts

- Peer support networks for local authorities to exchange best practices.
- Encouraging data sharing across industry and government for enhanced problem-solving.

By addressing these needs, the adoption of transformative innovations in food safety can be significantly accelerated.

Knowledge Exchange Preferences:**Preferred Methods for Receiving Information**

- Regular newsletters (monthly or bimonthly) with clickable links to articles or websites.
- Networking events, conferences, and online tools for sharing knowledge.
- Printed materials (flyers, pamphlets) and infographics for quick understanding.
- Video presentations and in-person learning sessions for practical demonstrations.
- Offline training sessions and classroom-based education programs.

Challenges in Accessing Relevant Knowledge

- Overwhelming amount of information, making it hard to track or prioritize.
- Limited understanding of scientific or regulatory materials, especially for small businesses.
- Language barriers (e.g., lack of English proficiency) and inconsistent information delivery.
- War-related disruptions: security concerns, staff turnover, and technical issues like power outages.
- Financial and human resource limitations for training and expert hiring.

Valuable Knowledge Exchange Platforms/Initiatives

- Online platforms combining courses, webinars, and Q&A forums tailored to specific audiences (e.g., processors, lab specialists).
- Public-private partnerships and centralized document-sharing systems for collaborative solutions.
- Interactive workshops, peer-to-peer learning, and international symposiums.
- Hands-on lab training or researcher exchanges for practical skills.
- Social media campaigns for general public awareness and digital tools like AI for interactive learning.

Education and Training requirements:**Skills and Knowledge Needed for Food Safety Professionals**

- Basic food science, technology, and hygiene principles.
- Microbiology for hazard identification and risk assessment.
- Data literacy and skills in emerging technologies like biotech and AI.
- Soft skills, such as communication and collaboration, and a deep understanding of food safety legislation.

Training Gaps and Unmet Needs

- Lack of understanding among producers about regulatory standards and risk assessment processes.

- Limited cooperation between businesses and regulatory authorities for training initiatives.
- Insufficient resources (grants, funding) for organizing training programs and developing expert-led content.
- Deficiency in training materials tailored for different sectors and scales of operation (e.g., small businesses).

Effective Formats and Content for Future Training Programs

- A hybrid approach combining theoretical knowledge (self-paced courses, webinars) with hands-on practice.
- Tailored materials for specific audiences, such as short infographics or posts for general consumers and sector-specific training for professionals.
- Physical meetings or dedicated facilities for practical demonstrations.
- Online platforms offering flexible, self-learning resources with certificates for motivation.

The SHs emphasize the need for accessible, tailored, and collaborative approaches to knowledge exchange and training. Addressing challenges like resource constraints, language barriers, and sector-specific needs can enhance the effectiveness of food safety innovations and education initiatives.

Best Approaches for CoP to Engage Small Food Producers**Leverage Associations and Networks**

- Collaborate with associations to act as intermediaries for sharing knowledge and tools.

Localized Outreach

- Provide in-person training through local associations, especially for older generations, and use community-based groups for more localized engagement.

Simplified Communication

- Use easy-to-understand materials like webinars, newsletters, and infographics, with translations and clear language.

Digital Tools

- Utilize online platforms and social media to reach younger producers with digital content.

Targeted Information

- Distribute relevant, sector-specific information through associations to avoid overwhelming small producers.

Economic and Regulatory Support

- Offer financial support and guidance through associations to help small producers with regulations and best practices.

By partnering with associations and offering tailored, accessible support, the CoP can effectively engage small producers.

Expected Impact of the CATALYSE CoP**Increased Awareness and Adoption of Innovations**

- CATALYSE is expected to raise awareness of food safety and sustainability, particularly in relation to climate change and emerging technologies.
- Promotes openness and willingness among SHs to adopt innovative practices.

Enhanced Communication and Collaboration

- Facilitates better communication between food safety professionals, industry, and policymakers, fostering collaboration.
- Increases industry awareness of new technologies, regulations, and challenges, particularly regarding the dairy sector and food safety innovations.

Improved Policy and Regulation

- Encourages the development of new policies and regulations related to food safety and sustainability.
- Focus on harmonizing official control practices across EU countries and ensuring consistent practices.

Better Information Sharing and Access

- Promotes the dissemination of best practices and scientific advancements, creating platforms for sharing information.
- Provides a centralized location for accessing key information, improving efficiency in the sector.

Support for Small Producers

- Empowers small producers by increasing their access to reliable information, promoting collaboration with associations, and addressing specific challenges.
- Implements models like Agroscope for better communication and support within local agricultural communities.

Long-Term Impact and Market Growth

- CATALYSE is expected to generate a critical mass of businesses producing compliant products, thus reducing food safety incidents.
- Encourages ongoing improvement and knowledge sharing, creating
- a sustainable market for technical advice and innovation.

In sum, the CoP aims to drive positive change by enhancing awareness, communication, and collaboration, while supporting small producers and contributing to policy development.

2.4. Civil Society SH Interviews

The one-on-one SH interviews could only go forward if the SH had signed the official engagement consent forms. The responses were 100% ‘yes’ for the indication of signed consent forms prior to commencing with the interview. The civil society one-on-one structure interviews are attached as Annex 12. Figure 43 and 44 provide demographic insights into Civil Society SH Interviewees based on gender and age group. The gender division graph shows that 67% of the respondents are women, while 33% are men, with no participants identifying as "Other" or choosing "Prefer Not to Say." This indicates a significant female predominance among civil society SHs. The age group distribution reveals that the largest share, 53%, belongs to the 46-60 years category, followed by 20% in the 31-45 years group and 13% in the >60 years category. A smaller portion, 13%, represents the 20-30 years group. These findings highlight that civil society SHs are predominantly middle-aged individuals, with a notable representation of women, underscoring the critical role of experienced professionals in civil society engagements.

Figure 43. Gender Diversion for Civil Society SHs responding to one-on-one interviews

Figure 44. Age group diversion for Civil Society SHs responding to one-on-one interviews

We asked civil society SH to rank six identified based on perceived importance which are the primary barriers to innovation in food safety that they as SHs encounter and have impact (Figure 45). The barrier ranked as the most critical (1st) is "C. Costs", highlighting financial constraints as the predominant challenge in food safety implementation. "D. Lack of Awareness" ranks as the 2nd most significant barrier, indicating the need for enhanced education and knowledge dissemination. "B. Regulation" occupies the 3rd position, reflecting concerns regarding regulatory complexities and compliance burdens. "A. Lack of Collaboration" is ranked 4th, pointing to gaps in SH cooperation and coordination. The 5th ranked barrier, "E. Lack of Dissemination to Small/Traditional Producers", underscores difficulties in effectively reaching smaller SH. Finally, "F. Resistance to Change" ranks as the 6th and least critical barrier.

Figure 45. Innovation Barriers ranked by Civil Society SHs responding to one-on-one interviews

Summary of Civil Society SH Responses on Food Safety Knowledge Exchange:

Knowledge Exchange Preferences:

- **Up-to-date information:** SHs want access to new scientific developments on food safety innovations.
- **Innovation platform:** They desire a platform where innovators can showcase themselves and solutions, aiding small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in identifying relevant solutions.
- **Accessibility and curation:** Easy access to a curated database of innovators and their solutions was seen as valuable.

Challenges in Knowledge Access:

- **Time constraints:** SHs struggle to keep up with the rapid pace of innovation in areas like DNA technology.
- **Information overload:** Finding relevant information from various industry databases can be time-consuming.

Desired Knowledge Exchange Platforms:

- **Database of innovators:** This was the most frequently requested feature.
- **Events calendar:** A calendar highlighting relevant conferences and workshops, particularly international ones, was desired.
- **Consultant directory:** A directory of consultants specializing in food safety was seen as helpful.

Educational and Training Preferences:

- **Differentiated formats:** SHs indicated a preference for diverse formats depending on the target audience.
- **Scholars:** Prefer access to in-depth scientific papers and reports.
- **Factory managers:** Favor face-to-face workshops for knowledge exchange and problem-solving.
- **Online options:** Online training with live interaction and readily accessible video resources were also seen as valuable.

Community of Practice (CoP) Expectations:

- **Limited time:** SHs acknowledge their busy schedules and emphasize the need for engaging platforms that respect their time investment.
- **Targeted outreach:** They desire content tailored to their specific needs and delivered in their preferred language.
- **Networking and knowledge sharing:** SHs emphasized the value of CoPs in facilitating:
 - Company networking.
 - Sharing of best practices.
 - Problem-solving collaboration.
 - Building trust within the food ecosystem for data sharing.

Desired CoP Outcomes:

- **Measurable food safety improvement:** SHs seek a platform that demonstrates a clear impact on food safety within the CoP.
- **Enhanced food systems and safety:** They hope to contribute to a more secure and efficient food system overall.
- **Empowerment and support:** SHs see the CoP as a vehicle for mutual support and knowledge exchange.

3. Face-to Face Workshop: WORLD Cafe Event

On May 1st, at the International Association for Food Protection conference held in Geneva, Switzerland, ILSI Europe successfully organized a World Café SH Engagement session. The event was conducted in collaboration with and with the generous support of the CATALYSE Project EU partners. This interactive session provided a dynamic platform for SHs to engage in meaningful discussions, share insights, and explore key issues related to food protection and safety. The initiative highlighted the commitment of ILSI Europe and CATALYSE Project EU to fostering collaboration and driving progress in food safety research and SH involvement on an international scale. The format of world café setting and questions is depicted in Figure 46.

Figure 46. World Café SH engagement Setting and Questions at IAFP event

Question 1: Understanding of Food Safety Theme: What are the ways in which one can be able to reach individuals or groups of individuals more effectively?

The four main target groups

- Actors (with experts and laymen) within the chain from production to trade of food
- Suppliers and service providers of food companies
- Policy people
- Consumers (and their risk groups) and citizens

Collaborative output:

- ✓ Collective communication: For good communication we should bring all actors together; Good to have cross-activity meetings. e.g.: Have more interaction between legislator and industry (MZ: create a role play in which they have to play each others role)
- ✓ Define Definitions: Clarity on basic definitions of food safety and it’s aspects in general; In discussions it is very relevant to clearly define definitions (what is risk, risk assessment, etc.); We should distinguish “perception” (that is someone’s good right) and “misunderstanding”. There are however facts, and that is without perception. The basic aspects are often forgotten and need to be repeated (MZ: make games to detect things that are wrong (did you see all the errors))
- ✓ Risks Communication: But “facts” also have uncertainty. We (and also the authorities) should dare to give an estimation of the risk but also be clear and transparent in the uncertainty. Convince policy makers of “emerging risks”

- ✓ Indicative Language Use: Instructions in different languages, include different cultures.
 - More in pictograms like NutriScore (A/B/C/D/E) - advantage to language barriers and overload of information
 - Better/clearer labelling of products to guide consumers like for RTE / RTH
- ✓ Social Media Approach: To reach big groups and the community - short simple videos – Social media/TIKTOK; Videos / Social Media / TIKTOK - show easy clear examples of good behaviour + clarity of information, avoid misunderstanding that leads to mistrust; Let people more appreciate quality; What would be good messages: “food safety is a shared responsibility”; “Love your food and food will love you”; “Give the good example in clips”
- ✓ Awareness to all: Also in (small) FBO there is lack of awareness of issues at stake (like STEC in flour, people are not aware these issues occur or occurred); Also educate the retailers
- ✓ Adapt organizational practices: Take the example of the health and safety departments of organisations: they have changed our culture in working; The FDA has made very good teaching to comply with FDA regulation. There is always a “preventive control person” “well educated” in the company
- ✓ Build Trust: Visible trust between organisations – e.g.: CDC/FDA; Built trust and know who to talk to, engage people
- ✓ Start Educating at an Early Age: Consumer education in school and adapt language to easy be understood;
 - Early in education educate about preparation, good diet, eating and preparing e.g. vegetables, Cooking classes at school
- ✓ Let the science speak: Better teach scientist to communicate

Question 2: Tech-Enabled Theme: Which recent promising technological breakthroughs deserve to be acknowledged and implemented to facilitate Food Safety?

Collaborative Output is summarized below:

New diagnostic tech:

- ✓ Sensor tech: monitor changes of parameters (T, pH)
 - For packaging it is quite new
 - cold chain management
 - presence of pathogens
- ✓ Printing lateral flow devices
 - it is for health now, but not for food yet

- ✓ Untargeted screening: lab measurement of contaminants & ingredients
 - against adulteration, for fingerprinting
 - using AI to decide if a sample is significantly different
 - AI metabolomics
- ✓ *S. aureus* various strains producing different toxins - use AI to classify these
- ✓ Sero-Seq (CRISPR): less biased reading of Salmonella
- ✓ Miniaturised devices for diagnostics (portable, automated, quicker, on-site)
 - DNA based – for olive oil
 - Allergenicity tests

New production tech

- ✓ Material sciences: intelligent active surfaces
 - not used for food yet
- ✓ Research is happening, lot of cool stuff but these don't find their place in industry applications (in many cases these are known for some time, but still not used widely):
 - radiation, plasma
 - radio frequency (RF) heating
 - active smart packaging
 - hydrogen water
 - phage, lysin
 - hyperbaric storage
 - pulsed UV
 - UHP (ultra high pressure treatment): for emerging pathogens
 - PEF (Pulsed Electric Field Processing): mainly quality driven
 - minimal processing

AI and data

- ✓ AI for predictions, prioritisation, recall, traceability
 - generative AI - understanding patterns
 - AI for risk assessment for specific products (training on past data) or facilities
 - also in combination with sensors
 - AI for data collection
- ✓ Food safety will become dynamic: adapting to actual risks related to actual raw materials and actual processes
- ✓ Put data in a usable format
 - supply chain data - vast amount, but not used
 - forecast on raw materials (e.g., mycotoxin forecast)
 - making changes to technology (e.g., reducing energy) - it would need data and AI
- ✓ Use the same data for other purposes (+ metadata)
 - WGS, source attribution
- ✓ Knowledge is missing how to interpret data

- Lot of hidden data – data sharing would be vital
- ✓ We shall be cautious with tech-enabled control
 - new information always emerges on challenges/drawbacks
 - reliability of AI is a question

Other

- ✓ Solutions decreasing food waste are needed, and they are coming
- ✓ Traceability, blockchain
 - Lack of training
 - Reliable guidelines needed
 - Lack of leadership initiative

Barriers

- ✓ Regulators & consumers shall be involved in the process
- ✓ Industry involvement
- ✓ Trade-offs
- ✓ Lock-in: current methods are accepted and affordable, so new tech shall show significant economic advantage

Needs/ideas of participants

- ✓ No accessibility to innovations
 - it would be nice to have a community and/or a platform where if a question is asked, solution/answer follows quickly
- ✓ There is a need for Scientific & Regulatory watch service
 - maybe augmented by AI
 - ANSES: ChatGPT trained on papers - newsletter on a hazards
- ✓ Leaving old path, be open for innovations
- ✓ Borrow from other domains
 - ESA/NASA
 - Pharma industry innovations come to food, but food has different standards
 - Also, on the contrary, food industry wants to get out of food: high added value, functional food is a trend
- ✓ We need to handle differences between EU vs Global vs Developing countries

Question 3: FARM-TO-FORK RISKS THEME: Given that climate change and environmental degradation are driving concerns of the future, we need to make supply chain more sustainable, which of the following challenges is the most challenging in your experience:

- ✓ Allergenicity in relation to the evolution of protein diversification
- ✓ Heavy metals
- ✓ Toxic phytochemicals (in plants) or biological plant protection products
- ✓ (New) chemical and microbial process contaminants

- ✓ Mycotoxins due to protein diversification in protein sources and global warming
- ✓ Spread of antibiotic resistance
- ✓ Food ingredients and products based on by-products
- ✓ Reformulations of food products with alternative raw materials or less salt, sugar and fat
- ✓ New sustainable processing methods

Collaborative Output is summarized below:

Risks:

- ✓ WATER: concerns were raised about the security of clean water. Concerning to feed people in the global food supply chain indicates the Food Safety Culture is very fragmented. Regulation creates food waste, and later how to deal with the food we have. Commodities are different in different parts of the world. We need a dynamic risk assessment / more flexibility. Contamination of waters because of flooding (example: oysters could not be consumed). There must be a link between water storage / too much flooding. RAINFALL: water shortage for farming,
- ✓ MYCOTOXINS: increasing due to climate change
- ✓ FOODS: reliance on a few crops
- ✓ SECURITY: supply of food due to heavy weather events (rescue /safe)
- ✓ ANTIBIOTIC RESITANCE: no way out, heavy threat, pathogen evolution, How pathogens will behave all the time / we will run out of controls risk to not produce enough food,
- ✓ FUNGAL PATHOGENS: we do not have anti-fungal agents.
- ✓ EMERGING PATHOGENS: Which pathogens would come through? Example: norovirus in Sri Lanka
- ✓ CLIMATE CHANGE: risks with certain pathogen groups, , Eg., Listeria, maybe more issues with groups.
- ✓ LOSS OF BIODIVERSITY
- ✓ ECONOMICAL CHALLENGES
- ✓ REAL RISKS: Novel foods, Novel toxins, Food safety may cause huge issues with food waste / loss; this gives issues with food security

Issues with the F2F strategy/ Food Industry

- ✓ Uptake of new technologies by the food industry,
- ✓ Mild processing techniques, like HPP, PEF

- ✓ The economy is driving the food system; everything else is secondary
- ✓ We can now bring co-benefits to have food security
- ✓ Distrust over the EU Green deal: suspect it to fail; Companies cannot work with it
- ✓ There seems a question about EU's decision on GMOs and Pesticide use
- ✓ CRISPR-CAS is the answer to all our problems, but being aware of unintended consequences / use the cautionary principle
- ✓ We see evidence of issues, but we have no consensus, mainly between government and citizens.
- ✓ Relevance of digital tools in this field, there is a need for tools to evaluate; we do not need risk management / risk negotiation. To be compliant is black or white. How to balance this to have safe food and low food loss

Healthy & Sustainable foods/ The consumer

- ✓ Consumers have a lack of education, Lack of consumer perception. Consumers cannot see the difference between what real risk and a hazard is. For example, the use of alternative names for GMOs to convince consumers
- ✓ Too much waste is a big hurdle to sustainability
- ✓ Unhealthy food composition leads to obesity – whereas healthy and sustainable foods have a direct relationship to affordability.
- ✓ Balance food safety and sustainability
- ✓ Relevance to IFST produced a factsheet on processed foods

TRUST:

Very interesting information came to the surface considering trust in the table discussions. And distrust was a major concern for SHs.

- ✓ A SH implied that the food system is all about the economy, this implies distrust of the industry and its supportive partners (policy & science)

- ✓ Another SH suggested that politics is not reliable because they change course with upcoming elections, this implies that the industry cannot set direction because politics changes focus.
- ✓ Multiple SHs had distrust in consumers as they were obstructing new developments and/or not sufficiently educated to make informed decisions.

On the other hand, one SH had full trust in that CRISPR-CAS would solve all our issues in our supply chain from farm to fork.

QUESTION 4: TREND RISKS THEME: What are the trend risks you have faced already? What did you need to evaluate the risk?...

Collaborative Output is summarized below:

Highlighted Trends:

- ✓ Novel foods (cultured meat, insects, plant-based foods)
- ✓ AI/machine learning-based data analysis

Ideas for information in link library:

- ✓ pipelines that are available for data mining, genome sequencing
- ✓ overview food safety associated regulations (in different countries, globally)
- ✓ guidance for industry for food-hazard associations (raw ingredients, composite products)
- ✓ pathway root to market: what are the hurdles a SME has to tackle before market launch (HACCP, legal requirements, food testing, how to evaluate when a food is a novel food)
- ✓ overview validated rapid methods (detection, enumeration, characterization)
- ✓ education on what does a test result means: market access requires certain tests (micro, chemical, maybe allergy) and how to interpret a test outcome.

QUESTION 5: PATHOGEN CONTROL TABLE: What could be useful action to increase the knowledge on pathogen control?

Collaborative Output is summarized below:

- ✓ **Pathogen Awareness:**
 - Educate individuals on the origins of pathogens.
 - Emphasize the necessity of hand washing.
 - Increase awareness about what and where to control to prevent overlooked areas.
 - Implement strategies to prevent cross-contamination.
 - Provide tools for environmental monitoring and data visualization, such as heatmaps.
- ✓ **Rapid Detection Methods:**
 - Develop and adopt quick pathogen detection technologies.
 - Cost-Effective Solutions and Address the affordability issues of current methods for producers.

- Develop and promote cost-effective methods for pathogen detection and control.
- Advocate for technologies that deliver results within 30 minutes as opposed to 3 days
- ✓ **Problem Solving Skills:** Enhance knowledge of problem-solving techniques in pathogen control.
- ✓ **Specialized Training:**
 - Ensure personnel are trained to interpret detection results accurately.
 - Provide basic informational materials and training on Good Manufacturing Practices (GMP) and Good Hygiene Practices (GHP).
 - Operational Procedures:
 - Standard Operational Procedures trainings and implement simple decision-making tools for workers cleaning transport vehicles, such as 'tick or cross' and 'go/no-go' systems.
 - Conduct open sessions for training, including online trainings and webinars.
 - Utilize AI to provide auto-translation during webinars to accommodate diverse participants.
 - Expand education and outreach programs to increase awareness and knowledge about pathogen control.
 - Implement compulsory training programs in food safety for all relevant personnel.
- ✓ **Language adaptation and simplification** of training material based on target group, translate all related documentation.
- ✓ **Training for all level of operational team** Increase training for farmers, who generally have less access to formal training.
- ✓ **Consumer Information:** Offer guidance on handling at home of specific products like raw pet food to end consumers.
- ✓ **Industry Practices:** Ensure post-cleaning environmental rapid analytical checks are conducted to assess the area for potential pathogen presence.
- ✓ **Data Information Sharing:**
 - Establish a platform for sharing information on risks and hazards associated with food safety
 - Share industrial fact sheets and success stories
 - Share experience in food safety between industry and small scale manufacturer (anonymously)
 - Document and disseminate what strategically important.
 - Foster a non-competitive environment to encourage open information sharing.
 - Research studies Dissemination and Share findings from shelf-life studies
- ✓ **Simplification of Regulations:**
 - Simplify regulations and tailor training materials to be educational.
 - Host webinars to clarify new regulations and simplify compliance procedures.
- ✓ **Problem Resolution:**
 - Anonymously share solutions to common food safety problems to protect privacy.
- ✓ **Support for Small Businesses:**
 - Provide dedicated support documentation, particularly for start-ups and new companies.
- ✓ **Industry Collaboration:**

- Build networks tailored to different SH groups and
- adapt information to various knowledge levels in operational team
- Facilitate communication between food business operators and raw material providers.
- Organize factory visits and on-site training across different sectors within the value chain to share knowledge both horizontally and vertically.
- ✓ **Continuous Updates:**
 - Distribute a monthly or weekly newsletter by a neutral party to keep SHs informed about external developments.
- ✓ **Engaging SHs:**
 - Encourage active participation by using real industry case studies.
 - Clearly define the goals and targets of pathogen control efforts.
 - Ensure open and transparent communication throughout all levels and across the entire value chain.
 - Engage all SHs in discussions and decisions.
 - Training and Consultancy: Provide training and support from expert consultants to enhance understanding and implementation of pathogen control.
 - Accessibility of Information: Promote open access to knowledge, especially when such resources are otherwise unavailable.
- ✓ **Addressing Emerging Challenges:** Raise awareness about potential new pathogens and the rationale for prioritizing them
- ✓ **Global Vision:** Adopt a global perspective in strategies, such as using spores to protect crops.
- ✓ **Collaborative Advocacy:**
 - Encourage small industries to collaborate and lobby within associations to leverage collective benefits.
 - Emphasize the necessity of prompt action in implementing pathogen control measures.
 - Support from Associations: Utilize associations to foster a pre-competitive environment that facilitates sharing of knowledge and resources.
 - Knowledge Sharing: Foster a culture of sharing knowledge, challenges, and solutions to learn collectively.
 - Partnerships: Develop more partnerships to collaboratively address problems and integrate learning from various solutions.
 - Collaboration: Strengthen efforts to work together across different sectors and disciplines.
- ✓ **Risk Communication:** Effectively communicate risk management strategies to all SHs involved.
- ✓ **Consumer Awareness:** Ensure consumers understand the importance of pathogen control throughout the food supply chain.
- ✓ **HACCP Implementation:**
 - Implement Hazard Analysis and Critical Control Points (HACCP) from farm to fork, extending even to seed level and within the restaurant industry.
 - Make HACCP principles accessible to small producers
 - Breaking down the guidelines to suit smaller operations.
 - Providing information specific to their needs.
 - Adapting the principles to local production processes and crop types.
 - PRE-HACCP for Small Producers

- Develop preliminary HACCP guidelines tailored for small-scale producers to adopt before full HACCP implementation.
- Make HACCP norms readily available and accessible online for easy reference and adherence.
- Translate HACCP guidelines into multiple languages to ensure comprehension and implementation across diverse cultural and geographical regions.
- ✓ **Risk Visualization:** Utilize visual tools to illustrate the risks associated with pathogens and demonstrate effective control measures.
- ✓ **Risk Perception:** Discuss and align on how risk perception is handled, particularly how proactive measures can be taken rather than waiting for guidance from authorities.
- ✓ **Education for Manufacturers:**
 - Educate manufacturers specifically in the nuances of food safety to enhance compliance and awareness.
 - Focus on both educating and building the capacity of teams to manage food safety effectively.
 - Distinguishing Hazards and Risks: Teach SHs to differentiate between hazards (potential sources of harm) and risks (likelihood and severity of harm), and tailor control measures to their specific operations.
- ✓ **Information Accessibility:** Ensure critical food safety information is readily available to all SHs.
- ✓ **Designated Responsibility:**
 - Mandate that at least one person per organization is specifically trained in food safety to oversee compliance and education.
 - Assign and mandate specific roles for risk management within organizations to ensure accountability.
- ✓ **Cross-Sector Communication:** Facilitate robust communication strategies across all sectors of the food value chain to ensure cohesive risk management.
- ✓ **Understand the different between the hazard and the risk**
- ✓ **Language and Cultural Challenges:**
 - Address language barriers and cultural differences to engage all employees in food safety practices, emphasizing collective responsibility.
- ✓ **Make food safety as culture in company**
- ✓ **Guidelines and Compliance:** Provide clear guidelines to help SHs meet regulatory requirements, such as those concerning acrylamide levels.
- ✓ **FDA Model Adoption:** Consider adopting models like the FDA's framework for proactive risk management as a standard for guiding food safety practices.

QUESTION 6: CLEAN PRODUCTION THEME: What did you see as best practice in cleaning & hygiene practices?

Collaborative Output is summarized below:

Understanding of clean production is the removal of pathogens. Clean production was correlated to clean label choice of sanitizing agents (e.g., in organic, not the same compounds are allowed). The key point for clean production was evaluated to be training of the personnel. The validation of clean production was also considered to be a matter of perception, one being visual validation being a subjective point of view and second having cleaning monitors consisting of trends and

indicators being a subjective point of view. Clean production also a matter of consideration to retail and distributors and not only food business operators (FBOs).

Emphasis was made of balancing cleaning vs production. It is crucial to adhere to the original design and specifications during production, while adjusting hygiene practices as needed without altering the product, provided that all necessary parameters were considered during the product design stage. It is important to reconfirm procedures whenever there are modifications in practices, production volumes, or any other relevant changes. Best practices were identified as maintaining and monitoring the efficacy of cleaning procedures, scheduling production based on allergen risks and avoiding shared production lines. It was indicated that best practices come from continuous improvement.

Whilst discussing the competency of sanitation and inherent expectations on clean production, it was inclined towards human behavioural aspects in Food Safety culture. Key points discussed were cross contamination between processing environment and production, ensuring verification of effectiveness. The conversation landed to defining required cleanliness, what is the recognized target, how to ensure they have reached the target and communicating the definition of good enough by visual inspection. The answer to these was simple, defining acceptable and non-acceptable.

The later discussion diverted to focusing on good practices in transportation and logistics (lorries, truck, packaging etc.). Segregation of food materials (washed/unwashed fruits & vegetables) is an important aspect when there are unavoidable circumstances of dirt/dust interference. On the other hand, considering the PSCA – Primary Salmonella Control Area (2010, PEM Guidelines Almond Board of California) for this purpose. In addition, clean practices are also related to the context in use of several materials and its purpose, for example, water fit for purpose approach.

Steering up the conversation to novel foods and cleaning regime, there seemed to be a lack of knowledge for specific risks. A risk of shared production lines in RTE vs non-RTE foods. An unclear idea for cleaning regime for copackers and logistics companies. In conclusion, an undefined path in the processes of regulatory approvals for innovative solutions.

4. PANEL DISCUSSION at ILSI Europe Symposium:

On November 27, 2024, at the ILSI Europe Symposium, the CATALYSE Project EU, in collaboration with the FoodSafeR Project, organized a special panel session featuring distinguished experts in the field of food safety. The panel included Dr. Michele Suman from Barilla, Italy, and visiting faculty at UCSC Italy, Hermann Broll from the BfR, Germany, and Oonagh Mc Nerney from IRIS Technology. The session delivered a comprehensive tripartite discussion focusing on strategies to navigate food safety innovations and the critical factors shaping advancements in the field. The event provided valuable insights into the evolving landscape of food safety, fostering collaboration and knowledge exchange among SHs and industry leaders.

Panel Question 1: Which external factors drive innovation in food safety:

- ✓ **Climate Change and Globalization:** Michele highlighted how climate change, globalization, and geopolitical scenarios influence food safety regulations.
- ✓ **Regulatory Frameworks:** Hermann emphasized that regulation provides a structure for innovations brought by the industry. He mentioned key drivers like the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and the EU Green Deal, which promote sustainable practices, including alternative proteins and green technologies.
- ✓ **Tech-Driven Safety Solutions:** Oonagh pointed out that external pressures compel the industry to adopt technology-driven food safety measures.
- ✓ **Industry Challenges with Regulation:** Hermann noted that industries often perceive regulation as a burden, particularly in areas like genetically modified (GM) products. However, he emphasized that fulfilling regulatory requirements ensures predictability and approval, which is highly valued by businesses.

Panel Question 2: Which recent innovations need broader implementation?

- ✓ **Ethical AI and Reliable Data Access:** The ethical use of AI is crucial for reliable data access and decision-making in food safety. There is a need for curated, trustworthy data to effectively address food safety challenges.
- ✓ **AI in Risk Assessment (RA):** AI and automation have the potential to enhance the risk assessment process, making it faster and more efficient. They could support risk assessors by generating scientific opinions and expediting evaluations. Efforts are underway to explore AI applications in this field.
- ✓ **New Genomic Techniques (NGTs):** Innovations like NGTs are enabling the modification of plants and microorganisms for healthier and higher-yielding products. These advancements are prompting the development of new regulatory frameworks to accommodate them.
- ✓ **Automation in Analysis:** Automation and robotics in laboratory analyses improve repeatability and efficiency compared to manual handling. Increased automation in food safety testing is seen as a way to streamline processes.
- ✓ **Reservations About Automation:** While automation offers many benefits, concerns remain about its application in specific analytical methods. For example, labeling products with "may contain allergens" due to imprecise automated methods can create confusion rather than clarity for consumers.

Panel Question 3: Role of AI and other digital technologies can facilitate the experts to advance Food Safety management?

- ✓ **Digital Product Passports and Trust in the Food System:** Digital product passports can enhance consumer trust by showcasing integrity and traceability in the food value chain, ensuring consumers know and trust what they are purchasing.

- ✓ **Traceability and Energy Challenges:** AI and blockchain technologies offer promising solutions for traceability, such as digital passports for genetically modified (GM) products. However, the energy consumption and computing costs associated with these technologies pose significant challenges, highlighting the need for innovation in energy-efficient data centers.
- ✓ **Blockchain and Sustainability:** Blockchain can improve traceability, but its energy demands are substantial. Sustainability considerations are also driving the push for reducing animal studies, which regulators are working to replace with non-animal methodologies (NAMs) and other innovations.
- ✓ **Advancements in Screening Techniques:** Rapid, non-traditional screening methods, supported by AI and technologies like infrared analysis, are becoming more accurate and efficient, significantly surpassing capabilities from a decade ago.
- ✓ **Collaboration and Digital Community Platforms:** Digital tools and platforms can foster collaboration among SHs in food safety. A platform-based approach could bring actors and users together, offering scalability and a lasting legacy. Examples include creating a secure, LinkedIn-like space for food safety professionals to share expertise and activate community engagement. These platforms should integrate AI and data-sharing tools while prioritizing human expertise and collaboration.
- ✓ **Vision for Sustainable Digital Integration:** A focus on using digital solutions sustainably involves reducing energy use, promoting scalability, and building tools that outlast individual projects, ensuring they create lasting impacts on food safety management systems.

PANEL QUESTION 4: Is there a certain practice that would benefit from more harmonization?

- ✓ **Harmonized Risk Assessment (RA):** A harmonized approach to RA dossiers across companies is essential, ensuring all rules are grounded in scientific evidence. Risk assessors advocate for uniformity in methodologies and ISO standards to standardize practices while allowing the use of diverse, standardized technologies.
- ✓ **Risk Prioritization and Pragmatic Testing:** A more pragmatic approach to risk prioritization is needed to determine when specific tests are necessary. Scientists and regulators often prioritize risks differently, underscoring the need for alignment between scientific and regulatory priorities.
- ✓ **Synergies in Digital Platforms:** Harmonization could extend to creating a unified digital ecosystem. A single, integrated platform combining data and interfaces from various projects (e.g., Foodsafer and WholyFood) would enhance usability and foster collaboration while minimizing overwhelm for users.
- ✓ **Collaboration Between SHs:** Effective food safety management requires interaction and open collaboration between risk assessors, industry experts, and other SHs. Industry

involvement brings specialized expertise, and working together can lead to better outcomes despite potential restrictions or challenges.

- ✓ European Project Clusters as Collaborative Incubators: European projects provide a strong framework for collaboration. Clustered projects allow SHs to reflect on progress, identify synergies, and maximize efficiency during working group developments.

Harmonizing these practices, while fostering flexibility, collaboration, and digital innovation, would significantly advance food safety management.

5. SH engagement on concerns in food safety extracted from workshop organized by FIAB:

This is a short summary related to food industry concerns on food safety at national level (Spain) and on which work is being carried out:

- ✓ Alerts: communication of alerts. There has been a change in the integrated management system (RASFF-Rapid Alert System for Food and Feed). At national level we have a mirror system of the European one (SCIRI). The RASFF wanted to make the format of the alerts uniform. Before, it was AESAN that sent the alerts, but now in Spain it has to be the autonomous communities that upload the alerts in pdf format to the RASFF. AESAN now sends a daily email with an Excel file with new notifications (as well as other notifications that are not alerts, such as border rejections, or information or news). If there is a level 1 alert (product produced in Spain and with risk for the consumer) for example, listeria in meat, if it has been something at the level of a small local shop, AESAN does not publish it. If it is something bigger, they publish it on their website, those that they consider to be of general interest. 1st the manufacturer is warned that an alert is going to be raised so that they can withdraw it, if AESAN publishes it before, the customer finds out at the same time as the manufacturer. So Communication failures.
- ✓ Allergens: There are no thresholds for most allergens in European legislation (with the exception of gluten and sulphites) since the European Commission prefers to wait for the completion of the work in progress in the Codex on allergen labelling. Is going very slowly and there are authorities that want precautionary labelling of allergens to be as minimal as possible without taking into account the risk assessment and the type of sector.. There are no standardised testing methods.
- ✓ Pathogenic microorganisms: listeria issue, they are going to change the criteria. The food safety criterion “Listeria monocytogenes not detected in 25 g” should apply to all situations where those foods are placed on the market during their shelf-life and for which the producing food business operator has not been able to demonstrate, to the satisfaction of the competent authority, that the level of Listeria monocytogenes will not exceed the limit of 100 cfu/g throughout their shelf-life. Therefore, operators consider it necessary to establish harmonized useful shelf-life studies that are valid for all the competent authorities. Food safety culture. All along the chain, from the first operator to the last, everyone must be familiar with food safety concepts. This also applies to top

management. This high-level training requires concrete tools. The operator has to have the same ability to tell the senior manager to use the measures. FIAB elaborated a good practice guide.

- ✓ Artificial intelligence. SMEs have a harder time training workers and integrating it.
- ✓ Smart packaging and active materials. Balance food safety, sustainability, cost. There must be government support

6. Interactive Questionnaires at In-person workshops and online webinars SH engagements:

- ✓ **Which is the most concerned food safety topic?**

The 6 concepts specified in the strategic and innovation plan for Food Safety published by Flanders Food (<https://www.flandersfood.com/en/world-class-food-production/food-safety>) are transversal themes that come back in the each action. The 6 concepts are:

1. [Understanding](#) - Create understanding and appreciation of food safety
2. [Tech-enabled](#) - Incorporate technology into a food-safe work environment
3. [Farm to fork risks](#) - Make food safety more sustainable and connected
4. [Trend risks](#) - Create support for demand-driven food safety problems
5. [Pathogen control](#) - Monitor the presence and growth of pathogenic microorganisms
6. [Clean production](#) - Monitor hygiene to control food safety

We anonymously asked 77 SH at various engagements during in-person workshops and online webinars to identify the most concerned food safety themes identified by Flanders' Food.

As depicted in the Figure 47 below, Pathogen Control is the most concerning topic, with the highest number of SH responses (around 30). New Trends and Its Risks is the second most significant concern, with approximately 20 responses. Understanding Food Safety with SHs follows as the third concern, garnering around 15 responses. New Technologies in Food Safety Innovations and Farm-to-Fork Risks received moderate concern, each with roughly 10 and 8 responses, respectively. Achieving Clean Production is the least concerning, with around 5 responses. This prioritization highlights that SHs place significant importance on controlling pathogens and addressing emerging trends and risks in food safety.

Figure 47. Which is the most concerned food safety topic responses from in-person workshops and webinars, N=77

- ✓ **Which specific innovations do you see as most facilitating for addressing current food safety concerns?**

Figure 48. Which specific innovations do you see as most facilitating for addressing current food safety concerns? responded at various in-person workshops and online webinars; N=91

We recognized top seven innovation recognized by SH mentioned in 'Table 6' from the online survey. To further understand the importance and to get a better understanding of SH perspectives. This graph shown in Figure 48 highlights the innovations that 91 SHs see as most helpful for addressing current food safety concerns at in-person workshops and online webinars organized by CATALYSE project. Identify sources of contamination is the top innovation, with the highest number of responses (~40). Predictive models rank second, slightly below, with ~37 responses. New tech for risks prevention follows

closely, with around 30 responses. Tech in monitoring microorganisms and AI tools received moderate support (~29, 27 responses respectively each). Up-cycling food waste and New cleaning procedures are seen as less significant, receiving ~11 and ~9 responses, respectively. The results emphasize the importance of technologies that identify contamination sources, predictive models, and prevention technologies in tackling food safety challenges.

✓ **Prioritized topics for topics/courses by SHs:**

We further recognized top 12 topics/courses prioritized by SH mentioned in ‘Table 9’ and further asked SH attending in-conference session at the EFFoST international conference on 14th November 2024 to choose their top 5 topics/courses in Food Safety, a total of 26 SHs responded to this interactive question at the session. The graph depicted in Figure

Figure 49. Prioritized Topics for Training/Courses by SH at in-person workshop; N=26

49 highlights the prioritized topics for training or courses as identified by SHs, the SHs were asked to select top 5 of these options. Food Safety Regulations and Compliance is the top priority receiving the highest number of responses (~14). It is closely followed by Emerging Risks and New tools for monitoring and detecting hazards each receiving ~13 responses. The Study of digital solutions and their potential with ~12 responses. Topics such as Food Safety Culture and Interpretation of hazards, risks, probability, and severity received moderate interest (~10 responses). Areas like Sanitation and Hygiene Design in Food Processing, Quality Control in Food Production, and HACCP and process validation also gathered substantial support (~9 responses each). However, Food Fraud and Food Labeling and Packaging Compliance are seen as lower priorities, receiving minimal responses (~2-3). This suggests SH place the greatest value on regulatory compliance, emerging risks, and technological advancements for food safety training.

STRENGTHS and WEAKNESS from the above reported SH Engagements:

Strengths: The SH outreach process exhibited several significant strengths:

- ✓ **Extensive Network Reach**
The consortium leveraged its wide network to connect with relevant SHs effectively. This facilitated a comprehensive outreach process that ensured diverse representation.
- ✓ **SH Group Representation**
A notable strength was the inclusion of appropriate SH groups, ensuring that insights and perspectives from all key participants were considered.
- ✓ **Consistency of Responses**
The repetition of answers among SHs provided a level of validation, confirming the reliability of the data collected.
- ✓ **Language Accessibility**
To enhance accessibility, consortium partners conducted interviews in multiple European languages, including Ukrainian, German, Spanish, French, Portuguese, and Dutch. This linguistic flexibility improved participation and convenience, particularly among local and SME SHs.

Weaknesses: Despite these strengths, the process also revealed certain limitations:

- ✓ Variation in Interviewers
The use of different interviewers may have introduced inconsistencies in data collection, potentially impacting the reliability and comparability of responses.
- ✓ **Lack of Statistical Analysis**
A key weakness identified was the absence of statistical analysis on the collected results. This limits the ability to draw robust, data-driven conclusions or identify patterns within the SH responses.
- ✓ **Underrepresentation of Gender Diversity**
The representation of SHs identifying as ‘other’ genders was reported to be less than 1%, highlighting a significant imbalance and lack of inclusivity within the study sample.

NEXT STEPS and Conclusions:

The SH Engagement process conducted with the consortium provided valuable insights and highlighted key pathways to strengthen collaborative efforts. A robust network enabled comprehensive outreach and representation across diverse SH groups, fostering validation through repeated perspectives and enhanced accessibility via multilingual support.

However, identified limitations, such as inconsistencies in interviews, a lack of statistical analysis, and minimal representation of gender diversity, underline areas for improvement to ensure inclusivity and data rigor in future engagements.

The next steps emphasize collective decision-making with the consortium to **adapt findings** for building a **Community of Practice (CoP)**. The current report gives raw conclusions from each of the above-mentioned engagements from which the consortium partners will contribute towards the developing the next version of this report that will comprise of:

- ✓ Core conclusions of the needs and priorities in the field of food safety innovations recognized by SHs
- ✓ Collaborative decision on the final chapters to be the basis of the CoP model
- ✓ List of innovations that address the concerns in food safety that can be facilitated by CATALYSE CoP
- ✓ Educational material to be taken in consideration to build the CoP model

Followed by this, the consortium considers priority actions that include:

- ✓ **Opening the CoP** – Establishing a dedicated platform to encourage SH collaboration, knowledge sharing, and actionable insights.
- ✓ **Expanding the Community** – Broadening outreach to include underrepresented groups and SHs, ensuring greater diversity and a more holistic representation.

By addressing identified weaknesses and implementing these strategic next steps, the engagement process can evolve into a sustainable, inclusive, and impactful model for building long-term partnerships and collaborative communities.

ANNEXES

Table of Annexes	
Annex 1	Stakeholder engagement online surveys – English language
Annex 2	Stakeholder engagement online surveys – Spanish language
Annex 3	Stakeholder engagement online surveys – German language
Annex 4	Stakeholder engagement online surveys – Ukrainian language
Annex 5	Stakeholder engagement online surveys – Portuguese language
Annex 6	Stakeholder engagement online surveys – Italian language
Annex 7	Stakeholder engagement online surveys – Finnish language
Annex 8	Stakeholder engagement ‘Consent Form’ for one-on-one structured Interviews
Annex 9	Industry Stakeholder Structured Interview Questionnaire
Annex 10	Academic Stakeholder Structured Interview Questionnaire
Annex 11	Policymaker / Public Authority Stakeholder Structured Interview Questionnaire
Annex 12	Civil Society Stakeholder Structured Interview Questionnaire

ANNEX 1: Stakeholder engagement online surveys – English language

CATALYSE EU PROJECT SURVEY (Copy)

Hello and thank you for participating in our survey! We are interested in your honest opinions and experiences. Your responses will remain confidential, and the survey should take approximately 15 minutes.

This survey's purpose is to understand the main needs in terms of food safety information/knowledge topics widely applied by end-users (official control authorities, food business operators, food safety risks assessors, etc.).

Nowadays food safety knowledge and innovation ecosystems are insufficiently connected. This is why our main goal is to create a network in the area of innovation in food safety for knowledge exchange between end-users and innovation ecosystems. This will include dissemination of public events, papers and reports, and the creation of an on-line collaborative space including the availability of materials for training and education. If you would like to know more about the project and it's reach please do not hesitate to contact our communications team at _____

This would not be possible without your help 😊

THANK YOU FOR YOUR COLLABORATION!

* Required

DISCLAIMER

This Survey Contains Three Parts. The survey will close on 1st October 2024.

By filling this survey, you consent to your answers being used by CATALYSE EU project partners for research purposes. The survey results will be handled anonymously, any information given will be treated confidential. While we hope you will participate, you are under no obligation to do so. Feel free to withdraw at any time without the need to provide us with any reasons.

1. Do you agree? *

- Yes, I would like to participate in this survey
- No, I prefer not to participate in this survey

2. Please indicate your gender *

- Woman
- Man
- Other
- Prefer not to say

3. Please indicate which age group you belong to? *

- 20-30 yrs
- 31-45 yrs
- 46-60 yrs
- >60 yrs

4. To which stakeholder group would you allocate yourself? *

- Academia / Research Institute
- Industry
- Policymaker / Public Authorities
- Civil Society
- Other

5. Please specify if you chose "other" in the above question

6. If you identify as an Industry Stakeholder, please specify your domain

- Primary Producers
- Food / Equipment Processor
- Laboratory Services
- B2B Consultancy
- Logistics Company
- Non-profit Organization
- Food Safety Technology Provider
- Other

7. Please specify, if you chose "other" in the above question

8. If you identify as a Policymaker / Public Authorities, please specify your domain

- Policymakers / national level (e.g. Ministry) and possibly also international level (e.g. European Commission)
- Public Authorities / authorities responsible for (national, regional) risk management in the Member States
- Public Authorities / authorities responsible for risk assessment in the Member States
- Public Authorities / international authorities: EFSA, ECHA, EMA, ...
- Other

9. Please specify, if you chose "other" in the above question

10. Please specify your work expertise in case you don't work with food

11. In relation to your work, could you please indicate which food groups you primarily work with? Please check all the options that apply:

- Fresh fruits and vegetables
- Grains and cereals
- Dairy products
- Beverages
- Meats and Poultry
- Fish and Seafood
- Processed and packaged foods
- Ingredients
- Plant-based Foods
- Other

12. Please specify, if you chose "other" in the above question

PART A

PLEASE INDICATE ACCORDING TO YOUR POINT OF VIEW THE LEVEL OF CONCERN REGARDING:

13. Control measures in food safety with pathogenic and spoilage microorganisms and their applications: *

- Very low concern
- Low concern
- Medium concern
- High concern

14. Please specify the target of your concern

15. Control measures in food safety with chemical risks and their applications: *

- Very low concern
- Low concern
- Medium concern
- High concern

16. Please specify the target of your concern

17. Control measures in food safety with allergens and their applications: *

- Very low concern
- Low concern
- Medium concern
- High concern

18. Please specify the target of your concern

19. Rapid detection methods for pathogenic and spoilage microorganisms: *

- Very low concern
- Low concern
- Medium concern
- High concern

20. Please specify in which field you see the need of improvement of these methods

21. Rapid detection methods for chemical substances: *

- Very low concern
- Low concern
- Medium concern
- High concern

22. Please specify in which field you see the need of improvement of these methods

23. Rapid detection methods for allergens compounds: *

- Very low concern
- Low concern
- Medium concern
- High concern

24. Please specify in which field you see the need of improvement of these methods

25. Hygienic design recommendations and best shared practices: *

- Very low concern
- Low concern
- Medium concern
- High concern

26. Please specify in which field you see the need of improvement of these practices

27. Food supply chain: traceability and transparency: *

- Very low concern
- Low concern
- Medium concern
- High concern

28. How satisfied are you at "Country Level" in regards to Food Supply Chain - Traceability and Transparency? *

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	----

29. While mentioning your satisfaction, which "Country" were you referring to? *

30. Packaging innovations in relation to materials: *

- Very low concern
- Low concern
- Medium concern
- High concern

31. Packaging innovations in relation to process of packaging: *

- Very low concern
- Low concern
- Medium concern
- High concern

32. Packaging innovations in relation to active packaging: *

- Very low concern
- Low concern
- Medium concern
- High concern

33. How satisfied are you with the food safety of your organization? Please rate the satisfaction level: *

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	----

34. Does your organization/entity/you use big data and/or artificial intelligence tools applied for food safety? *

- Yes
- No

35. If yes, which AI tools do you use?

If no, why? Are you interested in learning about more AI tools and it's applications in food safety? *

36. Do you have other concerns related to food safety and innovation? *

- Yes
- No

37. If yes, could you state which concerns are you referring to?

38. Do you recognise the value of attending training to improve the safety and quality of the products in your area? *

Yes

No

39. If yes, what specific aspects do you believe should be prioritized?
If no, what barriers or challenges influence your perspective? *

PART B: RECENT INNOVATION & SOLUTIONS THAT NEED MORE ADOPTION

40. Please select 5 areas where you have recently observed innovations or solutions that address critical needs and need to be adopted more frequently/by more stakeholders

*

Please select 5 options.

- New technologies for hazards and risk prevention
- Identifying the sources of contamination along the food chain
- Developments in monitoring and detecting hazards along the food chain (e.g. use of sensors, rapid detection methods for pathogenic microorganisms, mycotoxins, chemical contaminants, etc.)
- Contribution to the Whole Genome Sequencing (WGS) for the safety of food productions
- New and alternatives ingredients or solutions improving the safety of the final product (e.g. plant/ microorganisms/protein sources/ precision fermentations)
- Alternatives to conventional preservation methods
- Predictive and modelling tools (e.g., Developing predictive toxicology, predictive microbiology)
- Application of nanotechnologies to food productions
- Novelties on hurdle technology applied to food productions
- New alternative food matrices (e.g. insects, in vitro-meat, food-by-products)
- New analytical methods and regulatory needs for new food matrices
- Up-cycling Food Waste into valuable resources
- Innovation in food packaging solutions and labelling for reduction/prevention of food waste and promotion of sustainability
- New cleaning processes and hygiene procedures applying modern solutions
- Digital solutions to increase food chain transparency, safety and traceability
- New standards and logistics applied to food productions
- New solutions for safe storage and transport systems
- Better understanding and mitigation of antibiotic-resistant bacteria
- In silico and in vitro methods applied for sustainable safe food systems
- Artificial intelligence tools for improving food safety control in food chain Other
-

PART C: NETWORK & COMMUNITY OF PRACTICE

In the Horizon call, it is expected to create tailor-made communication materials summarizing, sharing and presenting, existing best practices and innovations that are close to implementation into practice, but not sufficiently known by end-users.

41. In which type/format of training would you like to receive the information? *

Virtual/Physical Symposia in "classroom"

Hands-on courses

On site sessions

Applied training session

Webinars

Self-learning courses

Other

42. Please specify other training formats or material you would prefer

43. What topics would you prioritize for training/courses? *

Please select 3 options.

- Processing Environment Monitoring
- Allergen Management Best Practices (FAO/WHO Reports 2022)
- Food Microbiological Analysis and Techniques
- Food Safety Regulations and Compliance
- Quality Control in Food Production
- Sanitation and Hygiene Design in Food Processing
- Food Labeling and Packaging Compliance
- New tools for monitoring and detecting hazards
- Study of digital solutions and their potential in improving food safety
- New and alternative solutions/technologies for improving the final products (nanotechnologies, new ingredients, natural antimicrobial substances)
- Quantitative Microbiology
- Quantitative Microbiological Risk Assessments (QMRA)
- Interpretation of hazards, risks, probability, severity
- Qualitative Sampling and Testing: Methods & Statistics
- HACCP and process validation: Tools for monitoring and detecting hazards
- Other

DO YOU WISH TO BECOME A MEMBER OF THE CATALYSE COMMUNITY OF PRACTICE (CoP)?

As part of CATALYSE, we are establishing a Europe-wide community of practice (CoP) with thematic chapters on specific topics/technologies through a digital platform to facilitate interaction, dissemination of relevant knowledge and regulations, educational materials and relevant events. This CoP will be a dynamic forum to promote knowledge transfer and uptake of food safety knowledge and innovation through:

1. Collaborating with a diverse network of food system stakeholders including researchers, industry, end-users and policymakers.
2. Accessing cutting-edge knowledge and resources on food safety and innovation.
3. Contributing to the advancement of food safety practices and technologies.
4. Engaging in meaningful discussions and exchange ideas with peers through physical and online meetings.
5. Staying informed about relevant events and educational materials.

Participation in the CoP will not only benefit professional development, but will also contribute to the collective effort to improve food safety across Europe.

By filling the fields below, you consent to your personal data being processed by CATALYSE partners to keep you informed about the project and invite you to the Community of Practice, in compliance with GDPR rules. Your personal data won't be used in the survey analysis. You can contact us info@ilsieurope.be at all times to have your information changed or deleted. You can find ILSI Europe full Privacy Policy at <https://ilsieurope.eu/wp-content/uploads/sites/3/2021/05/Privacy-Policy-industry-non-industry-members-19.03.2021.pdf>

44. Please fill your **NAME** and **SURNAME** if you would like to join the CATALYSE Community of Practice:

45. Please fill your **EMAIL** for contact purposes, if you would like to join the CATALYSE Community of Practice:

46. Please fill the name of your **ORGANIZATION / AFFILIATION**, if you would like to join the CATALYSE Community of Practice:

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ANNEX 2: Stakeholder engagement online surveys - Spanish language

ENCUESTA PROYECTO UE CATALYSE - PARTICIPACIÓN DE STAKEHOLDERS (ES)

Gracias por participar en nuestra encuesta. Nos interesan sus opiniones y experiencias. Sus respuestas serán confidenciales y la encuesta le llevará aproximadamente entre 15 minutos.

El objetivo de esta encuesta es conocer las principales necesidades en materia de información/conocimiento sobre seguridad alimentaria ampliamente aplicados por los usuarios finales (autoridades oficiales de control, operadores de empresas alimentarias, evaluadores de riesgos para la seguridad alimentaria, etc.).

En la actualidad, los ecosistemas de conocimiento e innovación en seguridad alimentaria no están suficientemente conectados. Por ello, nuestro principal objetivo es crear una red en el ámbito de la innovación en seguridad alimentaria para el intercambio de conocimientos entre usuarios finales y ecosistemas de innovación. Esto incluirá la difusión de actos públicos, documentos e informes, y la creación de una plataforma de colaboración en línea que incluya la disponibilidad de materiales para la formación y la educación. Si desea saber más sobre el proyecto y su alcance, no dude en ponerse en contacto con nuestro equipo de comunicación en catalyse.eu@gmail.com.

Esto no sería posible sin su ayuda, ¡GRACIAS POR SU COLABORACIÓN!

* Required

DECLARACIÓN LEGAL

Esta encuesta consta de tres partes. La encuesta se cerrará el 1 de octubre de 2024.

Al rellenar esta encuesta, da su consentimiento para que sus respuestas sean utilizadas por los socios del proyecto CATALYSE UE con fines de investigación. Los resultados de la encuesta se tratarán de forma anónima y cualquier información facilitada se tratará de forma confidencial. Aunque nos gustaría contar con su participación, no tiene ninguna obligación de hacerlo. Puede abandonar la encuesta en cualquier momento sin necesidad de darnos ningún motivo.

1

¿Está de acuerdo? *

Sí, me gustaría participar en esta encuesta.

No, prefiero no participar en esta encuesta.

2

Por favor indique su género *

- Mujer
- Hombre
- Otro
- Prefiero no decirlo

3

Por favor indique a qué grupo de edad pertenece *

- 20-30 años
- 31-45 años
- 46-60 años
- >60 años
- Prefiero no decirlo

4

Indique a cuál de los siguientes grupos pertenece *

- Academia / Centro de Investigación
- Industria
- Responsable político / Autoridades Públicas
- Sociedad civil
- Other

5

Si se identificó en el grupo de Industria, por favor especifique su grupo

- Productores Primarios
- Alimento / Ingredientes / Equipo Procesador
- Servicios de laboratorio
- Consultoría B2B
- Logística
- Organización sin ánimo de lucro
- Proveedor de Tecnología en Seguridad Alimentaria
- Other

6

Si se identificó en el grupo de Responsable político/ Autoridades públicas, por favor especifique su grupo

- Responsable político / nivel nacional (Ministerio) y/o nivel internacional (Comisión Europea).
- Autoridades públicas / autoridades responsables (nacional, regional) de gestión de riesgos.
- Autoridades públicas /autoridades responsables de la evaluación de riesgos.
- Autoridades públicas / autoridades internacionales: EFSA, ECHA, EMA,
- Other

7

Por favor, especifique su experiencia laboral en caso de que no trabaje en el sector agroalimentario

8

En relación con su trabajo, ¿podría indicar con qué grupos de alimentos trabaja principalmente? Por favor marque todas las opciones que necesite:

- Frutas y verduras
- Granos y cereales
- Productos lácteos
- Bebidas
- Carnes y Aves de corral
- Pescado y Mariscos
- Alimentos procesados y empaquetados
- Ingredientes
- Alimentos de origen vegetal
- Other

PARTE A

POR FAVOR INDIQUE, DE ACUERDO CON SU PUNTO DE VISTA, EL NIVEL DE INTERÉS ACERCA DE:

9

Medidas de control en seguridad alimentaria con microorganismos patógenos y alterantes y sus aplicaciones: *

- Muy bajo
- Bajo
- Medio
- Alto

10

Por favor explique el motivo de su interés

11

Medidas de control en seguridad alimentaria con riesgos químicos y sus aplicaciones: *

- Muy bajo
- Bajo
- Medio
- Alto

12

Por favor explique el motivo de su interés

13

Medidas de control en seguridad alimentaria con alérgenos y sus aplicaciones: *

- Muy bajo
- Bajo
- Medio
- Alto

14

Por favor explique el motivo de su interés

15

Métodos rápidos de detección de microorganismos patógenos y de descomposición: *

- Muy bajo
- Bajo
- Medio
- Alto

16

Por favor especifique en qué campo ve la necesidad de mejorar estos métodos

17

Métodos rápidos de detección de sustancias químicas: *

- Muy bajo
- Bajo
- Medio
- Alto

18

Por favor especifique en qué campo ve la necesidad de mejorar estos métodos

19

Métodos de detección rápida de compuestos alérgenos: *

Muy bajo

Bajo

Medio

Alto

20

Por favor especifique en qué campo ve la necesidad de mejorar estos métodos

21

Recomendaciones de diseño higiénico y mejores prácticas compartidas: *

Muy bajo

Bajo

Medio

Alto

22

Por favor especifique en qué campo ve la necesidad de mejorar estas prácticas

23

Cadena de suministro alimentario: trazabilidad y transparencia: *

- Muy bajo
- Bajo
- Medio
- Alto

24

Innovación en packaging en relación a materiales: *

- Muy bajo
- Bajo
- Medio
- Alto

25

Innovación en packaging en relación al proceso de embalaje: *

- Muy bajo
- Bajo
- Medio
- Alto

26

Innovación en packaging en relación con envases activos: *

- Muy bajo
- Bajo
- Medio
- Alto

27

¿Su organización o usted utiliza herramientas de big data y/o inteligencia artificial aplicadas a seguridad alimentaria? *

Sí

No

28

En caso afirmativo, ¿Qué herramientas de IA utiliza?

Si no las utiliza, ¿Por qué? ¿Está interesado en conocer más herramientas de IA y sus aplicaciones en seguridad alimentaria? *

29

¿Qué tan satisfecho está con la seguridad alimentaria de su organización? Por favor califique el nivel de satisfacción:

1=Menos satisfecho y 10=Muy satisfecho *

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	----

30

¿Qué tan satisfecho está usted a "nivel país" con respecto a la seguridad alimentaria?

1=Menos satisfecho y 10=Muy satisfecho *

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	----

31

¿Al mencionar su satisfacción, a qué "país" se refería? *

32

¿Tiene otras preocupaciones relacionadas con la seguridad alimentaria y la innovación? *

Sí

No

33

En caso afirmativo, ¿podría indicar a qué preocupaciones se refiere?

34

¿Encuentra el valor en asistir a capacitaciones para mejorar la seguridad y calidad de los productos?

*

Sí

No

35

En caso afirmativo, ¿qué aspectos específicos cree que deberían priorizarse?

En caso negativo, ¿qué barreras o desafíos influyen en su perspectiva? *

PARTE B

INNOVACIÓN RECIENTE Y SOLUCIONES CON NECESIDAD DE ADOPCIÓN

36

Seleccione cinco áreas en las que haya observado recientemente innovaciones o soluciones que aborden necesidades críticas y necesiten ser adoptadas con mayor frecuencia/por más partes interesadas. *

Please select at most 5 options.

- Nuevas tecnologías para la prevención de peligros y riesgos
- Identificar las fuentes de contaminación a lo largo de la cadena alimentaria
- Avances en el seguimiento y detección de peligros a lo largo de la cadena alimentaria (por ejemplo, uso de sensores, y métodos de detección rápida para microorganismos patógenos, micotoxinas, contaminantes químicos, etc.)
- Contribución a la Secuenciación del Genoma Completo (WGS) para la seguridad de las producciones de alimentos
- Ingredientes o soluciones nuevas y alternativas que mejoran la seguridad del producto final (por ejemplo, plantas/microorganismos/fuentes de proteínas/fermentaciones de precisión)
- Alternativas a los métodos de conservación convencionales
- Herramientas de predicción y modelización (p.ej, toxicología predictiva, microbiología predictiva)
- Aplicación de nanotecnologías a la producción de alimentos
- Novedades en tecnología de obstáculos aplicada a la producción de alimentos
- Nuevas matrices alimentarias alternativas (insectos, carne in vitro, subproductos alimentarios)
- Nuevos métodos analíticos y necesidades regulatorias para nuevas matrices alimentarias
- Reciclaje de desperdicio alimentario en recursos utilizables.
- Innovación en soluciones de envasado y etiquetado de alimentos para la reducción/prevenición del desperdicio de alimentos y promoción de sostenibilidad.
- Nuevos procesos de limpieza y procedimientos de higiene aplicando soluciones innovadoras
- Soluciones digitales para aumentar la transparencia, la seguridad y la trazabilidad de la cadena alimentaria
- Nuevas normas y logística aplicadas a las producciones alimentarias
- Nuevas soluciones para sistemas de almacenamiento y transporte seguros
- Mejor comprensión y mitigación de las bacterias resistentes a los antibióticos
- Métodos In silico e In vitro aplicados para sistemas alimentarios sostenibles y seguros.
- Herramientas de inteligencia artificial para mejorar el control de la seguridad alimentaria en la cadena alimentaria

Other

PARTE C: RED Y COMUNIDAD DE PRÁCTICAS

En el proyecto CATALYSE, se espera la creación de materiales de comunicación a medida que resuman, compartan y difundan las mejores prácticas y las innovaciones existentes que están a punto de ponerse en práctica, pero que no son suficientemente conocidas por los usuarios finales.

37

¿En qué formato de formación le gustaría recibir la información? *

- Charla o conferencia virtual o física
- Cursos prácticos
- Sesiones presenciales
- Sesiones de capacitación aplicadas
- Seminarios web
- Cursos de autoaprendizaje
- Other

38

Por favor especifique otros formatos o materiales de capacitación que prefiera

39

¿Qué temas priorizaría para la capacitación/cursos? *

Please select at most 5 options.

- Monitoreo del entorno de procesamiento
- Mejor Prácticas en Gestión de Alérgenos (FAO/OMS Informes 2022)
- Análisis y técnicas microbiológicas de los alimentos
- Normativa y cumplimiento de la seguridad alimentaria
- Control de calidad en la producción de alimentos
- Saneamiento y diseño higiénico en el procesado de alimentos
- Etiquetado y envasado de alimentos
- Nuevas herramientas de vigilancia y detección de peligros
- Estudio de soluciones digitales y su potencial en la mejora de la seguridad alimentaria
- Soluciones/tecnologías nuevas y alternativas para mejorar los productos finales (nanotecnologías, nuevos ingredientes, sustancias antimicrobianas naturales)
- Microbiología cuantitativa
- Evaluaciones cuantitativas del riesgo microbiológico (QMRA)
- Interpretación de peligros, riesgos, probabilidad, gravedad.
- Muestreo y pruebas cualitativas: Métodos y estadísticas
- APPCC y validación de procesos: Herramientas de control y detección de peligros
- Cultura de la seguridad alimentaria
- Fraude alimentario
- Riesgos emergentes
- Escaneado del horizonte
- Seguros y seguridad alimentaria
- Other

DESEA FORMAR PARTE DE LA COMUNIDAD DE PRÁCTICAS (CoP) DEL PROYECTO CATALYSE?

Como parte de CATALYSE, estamos estableciendo una comunidad de prácticas (CoP) a escala europea con capítulos temáticos sobre temas/tecnologías específicos a través de una plataforma digital para facilitar la interacción, la difusión de conocimientos y regulaciones pertinentes, materiales educativos y eventos relevantes. Esta CoP será un foro dinámico para promover la transferencia de conocimientos y la asimilación de los conocimientos y la innovación en materia de seguridad alimentaria a través de:

1. La colaboración con una red diversa de partes interesadas del sistema alimentario, incluidos investigadores, industria, usuarios finales y responsables políticos.
2. El acceso a conocimientos y recursos de vanguardia sobre seguridad alimentaria e innovación.
3. Contribuir al avance de las prácticas y tecnologías de seguridad alimentaria.
4. Participar en debates significativos e intercambiar ideas con compañeros a través de reuniones físicas y en línea.
5. Mantenerse informado sobre eventos relevantes y materiales educativos.

La participación en la CoP no sólo beneficiará al desarrollo profesional, sino que también contribuirá al esfuerzo colectivo para mejorar la seguridad alimentaria en toda Europa.

Puede rellenar el formulario de inscripción para formar parte de la CoP de CATALYSE después de enviar esta Encuesta.

Los socios de CATALYSE EU le agradecen su tiempo y esfuerzo.

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ANNEX 3: Stakeholder engagement online surveys – German language

UMFRAGE ZUM EU-Projekt "CATALYSE" – EINBEZUG DER STAKEHOLDER (GERMAN)

Guten Tag und vielen Dank, dass Sie an unserer Umfrage teilnehmen! Wir sind an Ihren ehrlichen Meinungen und Erfahrungen interessiert. Ihre Antworten werden vertraulich behandelt, und die Umfrage sollte etwa 15 Minuten dauern.

Ziel dieser Umfrage ist es, den Bedarf an wichtigen Informationen und Wissen zu Themen der Lebensmittelsicherheit bei den Endnutzern zu ermitteln (d. h. bei amtlichen Kontrollbehörden, Lebensmittelunternehmen, Fachpersonen im Bereich der Überprüfung der Lebensmittelsicherheit usw.).

Bisher sind Wissen und Innovationsökosysteme im Bereich der Lebensmittelsicherheit nur unzureichend vernetzt. Deshalb besteht unser Hauptziel darin, ein Netzwerk im Bereich der Innovation in der Lebensmittelsicherheit zu schaffen, das den Wissensaustausch zwischen Endnutzern und Innovationsökosystemen fördert. Dazu gehören öffentlichen Veranstaltungen, die Verbreitung von Fachartikeln und Berichten sowie die Schaffung einer OnlineKooperationsplattform, die auch Materialien für die Aus- und Weiterbildung bereitstellt. Wenn Sie mehr über das Projekt und dessen Reichweite erfahren möchten, zögern Sie nicht, unser Kommunikationsteam zu kontaktieren: catalyse.eu@gmail.com.

Ohne Ihren Beitrag wäre diese Umfrage nicht möglich.

VIELEN DANK FÜR IHRE MITARBEIT!

* Required

HAFTUNGSAUSSCHLUSS

Diese Umfrage besteht aus drei Teilen. Die Umfrage wird am 1. Oktober 2024 geschlossen. Mit dem Ausfüllen dieser Umfrage erklären Sie sich damit einverstanden, dass Ihre Antworten von den Projektpartnern von CATALYSE EU zu Forschungszwecken verwendet werden. Die Umfrageergebnisse werden anonymisiert, alle Angaben werden vertraulich behandelt. Wir hoffen, dass Sie sich an der Umfrage beteiligen, Sie sind jedoch nicht dazu verpflichtet. Sie können die Teilnahme jederzeit ohne Angabe von Gründen beenden.

1

Sind Sie einverstanden? *

- Ja, ich möchte an dieser Umfrage teilnehmen
- Nein, ich möchte nicht an dieser Umfrage teilnehmen

2

Bitte geben Sie Ihr Geschlecht an: *

- Frau
- Mann
- Anderes
- Dazu möchte ich keine Angaben machen

3

Bitte geben Sie an, zu welcher Altersgruppe Sie gehören: *

- 20-30 Jahre
- 31-45 Jahre
- 46-60 Jahre
- >60 Jahre
- Dazu möchte ich keine Angaben machen

4

Welcher Stakeholder-Gruppe würden Sie sich zuordnen? *

- Hochschulen / Forschungsinstitute
- Industrie
- Politik/Behörden
- Zivilgesellschaft
- Other

5

Wenn Sie "Industrie" gewählt haben, geben Sie bitte Ihren Bereich an:

- Primärerzeuger
- Verarbeitung Lebensmittel / Zutaten / Ausrüstung
- Labor-Dienstleistungen
- B2B-Beratung
- Logistikunternehmen
- Gemeinnützige Organisation
- Anbieter von Lebensmittelsicherheitstechnologie
- Other

6

Wenn Sie "Politik/Behörden" gewählt haben, geben Sie bitte Ihren Bereich an:

- Politische Entscheidungsträger nationale Ebene (z. B. Ministerium) und ev. auch internationale Ebene (z. B. Europäische Kommission)
- Behörde, die in Mitgliedstaat für das (nationale, regionale) Risikomanagement zuständig ist
- Behörde, die in Mitgliedstaat für die Risikobewertung zuständig ist
- Internationale Behörde: EFSA, ECHA, EMA
- Other

7

Bitte geben Sie Ihr Fachgebiet an, falls Sie nicht mit Lebensmitteln arbeiten:

8

Könnten Sie in Bezug auf Ihre Arbeit bitte angeben, mit welchen Lebensmittelgruppen Sie hauptsächlich arbeiten? Bitte kreuzen Sie alle Optionen an, die auf Sie zutreffen:

- Frisches Obst und Gemüse
- Körner und Getreide
- Milchprodukte
- Getränke
- Fleisch und Geflügel
- Fisch und Meeresfrüchte
- Verarbeitete und verpackte Lebensmittel
- Inhaltsstoffe
- Pflanzliche Lebensmittel
- Other

TEIL A**BITTE GEBEN SIE AN, WIE GROSS IHRER MEINUNG NACH DIE BEDENKEN SIND:**

9

Kontrollmassnahmen im Bereich der Lebensmittelsicherheit mit pathogenen und schädlichen Mikroorganismen und deren Anwendung: *

- Sehr geringe Bedenken
- Geringe Bedenken
- Mittlere Bedenken
- Grosse Bedenken

10

Bitte geben Sie an, worüber Sie besorgt sind

11

Kontrollmassnahmen für die Lebensmittelsicherheit betreffend chemische Risiken und deren Umsetzung: *

- Sehr geringe Bedenken
- Geringe Bedenken
- Mittlere Bedenken
- Grosse Bedenken

12

Bitte geben Sie an, worüber Sie besorgt sind:

13

Kontrollmassnahmen im Bereich der Lebensmittelsicherheit betreffend Allergene und deren Umsetzung:

*

- Sehr geringe Bedenken
- Geringe Bedenken
- Mittlere Bedenken
- Grosse Bedenken

14

Bitte geben Sie an, worüber Sie besorgt sind:

15

Verfahren zum schnellen Nachweis pathogener und schädlicher Mikroorganismen: *

- Sehr geringe Bedenken
- Geringe Bedenken
- Mittlere Besorgnis
- Grosse Bedenken

16

Bitte geben Sie an, in welchem Bereich Sie Verbesserungsbedarf bei diesen Methoden sehen:

17

Verfahren zum schnellen Nachweis chemischer Stoffe: *

- Sehr geringe Bedenken
- Geringe Bedenken
- Mittlere Bedenken
- Grosse Bedenken

18

Bitte geben Sie an, in welchem Bereich Sie Verbesserungsbedarf bei diesen Methoden sehen:

19

Verfahren zum schnellen Nachweis allergener Stoffe *

- Sehr geringe Bedenken
- Geringe Bedenken
- Mittlere Bedenken
- Grosse Bedenken

20

Bitte geben Sie an, in welchem Bereich Sie Verbesserungsbedarf bei diesen Methoden sehen:

21

Empfehlungen für ein hygienegerechtes Konzept und bewährte gemeinsame Praktiken: *

- Sehr geringe Bedenken
- Geringe Bedenken
- Mittlere Bedenken
- Grosse Bedenken

22

Bitte geben Sie an, in welchem Bereich Sie Verbesserungsbedarf bei diesen Praktiken sehen:

23

Lebensmittelversorgungskette: Rückverfolgbarkeit und Transparenz: *

- Sehr geringe Bedenken
- Geringe Bedenken
- Mittlere Bedenken
- Grosse Bedenken

24

Verpackungsinnovationen in Bezug auf Materialien: *

- Sehr geringe Bedenken
- Geringe Bedenken
- Mittlere Bedenken
- Grosse Bedenken

25

Verpackungsinnovationen in Bezug auf den Verpackungsprozess: *

- Sehr geringe Bedenken
- Geringe Bedenken
- Mittlere Bedenken
- Grosse Bedenken

26

Verpackungsinnovationen in Bezug auf aktive Verpackungen: *

- Sehr geringe Bedenken
- Geringe Bedenken
- Mittlere Bedenken
- Grosse Bedenken

27

Nutzt Ihr Unternehmen oder nutzen Sie selbst Big Data und/oder Tools der künstlichen Intelligenz für die Lebensmittelsicherheit? *

- Ja
- Nein

28

Wenn ja, welche KI-Tools verwenden Sie?

Wenn nein, warum nicht? Sind Sie daran interessiert, mehr über KI-Tools und ihre Anwendungen in der Lebensmittelsicherheit zu erfahren? *

29

Wie zufrieden sind Sie mit der Lebensmittelsicherheit in Ihrer Organisation? Bitte bewerten Sie den Grad der Zufriedenheit

*1 = am wenigsten zufrieden und 10 = sehr zufrieden **

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
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30

Wie zufrieden sind Sie auf "Landesebene" mit der Lebensmittelsicherheit? *

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	----

31

Auf welches "Land" beziehen Sie sich bei Ihrer Zufriedenheit? *

32

Haben Sie andere Anliegen in Bezug auf Lebensmittelsicherheit und Innovation? *

- Ja
- Nein

33

Wenn ja, könnten Sie angeben, auf welche Bedenken Sie sich beziehen?

34

Sind Ihrer Meinung nach Schulungen zur Verbesserung der Sicherheit und Qualität der Produkte in Ihrem Bereich hilfreich? *

- Ja
- Nein

35

Wenn ja, welche spezifischen Aspekte sollten Ihrer Meinung nach vorrangig behandelt werden? Wenn nein, welche Hindernisse oder Herausforderungen sprechen dagegen? *

TEIL B: AKTUELLE INNOVATIONEN UND LÖSUNGEN, DIE VERMEHRT ANGEWENDET WERDEN SOLLTEN

36

Bitte wählen Sie 5 Bereiche aus, in denen Sie in letzter Zeit Innovationen oder Lösungen beobachtet haben, die wichtige Bedürfnisse angehen und häufiger/von mehr Stakeholdern angewendet werden sollten

*

Please select at most 5 options.

- Neue Technologien für Gefahren und Risikoprävention
- Identifizierung der Kontaminationsquellen entlang der Lebensmittelkette
- Entwicklungen bei der Überwachung und Erkennung von Gefahren entlang der Lebensmittelkette (z. B. Einsatz von Sensoren, Verfahren zum schnellen Nachweis pathogener Mikroorganismen, von Mykotoxinen, chemischen Kontaminanten usw.)
- Beitrag zum Whole Genome Sequencing (WGS) für die Sicherheit der Lebensmittelproduktion
- Neue und alternative Zutaten oder Lösungen, die die Sicherheit des Endprodukts verbessern (z. B. Pflanzen/Mikroorganismen/Proteinquellen/Präzisionsfermentationen)
- Alternativen zu herkömmlichen Konservierungsmethoden
- Vorhersage- und Modellierungsinstrumente (z. B. Entwicklung der prädiktiven Toxikologie, prädiktive Mikrobiologie)
- Anwendung von Nanotechnologien in der Lebensmittelproduktion
- Neuerungen beim Hürdenkonzept in der Lebensmittelproduktion
- Neue alternative Lebensmittel-Matrizen (z. B. Insekten, In-vitro-Fleisch, Lebensmittel-Nebenerzeugnisse)
- Neue Analysemethoden und regulatorische Anforderungen für neue Lebensmittel-Matrizen
- Upcycling von Lebensmittelabfällen in wertvolle Ressourcen
- Innovation bei Lebensmittelverpackungslösungen und Etikettierung zur Verringerung/Vermeidung von Lebensmittelabfällen und zur Förderung der Nachhaltigkeit
- Neue Reinigungs- und Hygieneverfahren mit modernen Lösungen
- Digitale Lösungen für mehr Transparenz, Sicherheit und Rückverfolgbarkeit in der Lebensmittelkette
- Neue Normen und Logistik in der Lebensmittelproduktion
- Neue Lösungen für sichere Lager- und Transportsysteme
- Besseres Verständnis und Eindämmung von antibiotikaresistenten Bakterien
- In-silico- und In-vitro-Methoden für nachhaltig sichere Lebensmittelsysteme
- Werkzeuge der künstlichen Intelligenz zur Verbesserung der Lebensmittelsicherheitskontrolle in der Lebensmittelkette

Other

TEIL C: NETZWERK UND "COMMUNITY OF PRACTICE"

Im Rahmen des CATALYSE-Programms sollen massgeschneiderte Kommunikationsmaterialien erstellt werden, in denen bewährte Verfahren und Innovationen, die kurz vor der Umsetzung in die Praxis stehen, aber bei den Endnutzern nicht ausreichend bekannt sind, zusammengefasst, weitergegeben und vorgestellt werden.

37

In welcher Form/in welchem Format möchten Sie die Informationen erhalten? *

Virtuelle/physische Symposien im "Klassenzimmer"

Praktische Kurse

Sitzungen vor Ort

Angewandte Schulungseinheiten

Webinare

Kurse zum Selbststudium

Other

38

Bitte geben Sie andere Schulungsformate oder Materialien an, die Sie bevorzugen

39

Welche Themen würden Sie bei Schulungen/Kursen vorrangig behandeln? *

Please select at most 5 options.

- Überwachung der Verarbeitungsumgebung
- Bewährte Praktiken des Allergenmanagements (FAO/WHO Berichte 2022)
- Mikrobiologische Lebensmittelanalysen und -techniken
- Vorschriften zur Lebensmittelsicherheit und zu deren Einhaltung
- Qualitätskontrolle in der Lebensmittelproduktion
- Hygienegerechte Konzepte in der Lebensmittelverarbeitung
- Konformität der Lebensmittelkennzeichnung und -verpackung
- Neue Instrumente zur Überwachung und Erkennung von Gefahren
- Studie über digitale Lösungen und deren Potenzial zur Verbesserung der Lebensmittelsicherheit
- Neue und alternative Lösungen/Technologien zur Verbesserung der Endprodukte (Nanotechnologien, neue Inhaltsstoffe, natürliche antimikrobielle Substanzen)
- Quantitative Mikrobiologie
- Quantitative mikrobiologische Risikobewertungen (QMRA)
- Interpretation von Gefahren, Risiken, Wahrscheinlichkeiten, Schweregrad
- Qualitative Stichproben und Tests: Methoden und Statistik
- HACCP und Prozessvalidierung: Instrumente zur Überwachung und Erkennung von Gefahren
- Kultur der Lebensmittelsicherheit
- Lebensmittelbetrug
- Aufkommende Risiken
- Horizon Scanning
- Versicherungen und Lebensmittelsicherheit
- Other

MÖCHTEN SIE MITGLIED DER COMMUNITY OF PRACTICE CATALYSE (CoP) WERDEN?

Co-funded by the
European Union

Im Rahmen von CATALYSE bauen wir eine europaweite Community of Practice (CoP) mit thematischen Kapiteln zu bestimmten Themen/Technologien über eine digitale Plattform auf, um die Interaktion, die Verbreitung von relevantem Wissen und Vorschriften, Bildungsmaterialien und relevanten Veranstaltungen zu erleichtern. Diese CoP wird ein dynamisches Forum zur Förderung des Wissenstransfers und der Übernahme von Wissen und Innovationen im Bereich der Lebensmittelsicherheit sein:

1. Zusammenarbeit mit einem breit gefächerten Netzwerk von Stakeholdern des Lebensmittelsystems, einschließlich Forschenden, Industrie, Endverbrauchern und politischen Entscheidungsträgern.
2. Zugang zu aktuellem Wissen und neuen Ressourcen im Bereich Lebensmittelsicherheit und Innovation.
3. Beitrag zur Weiterentwicklung von Verfahren und Technologien der Lebensmittelsicherheit.
4. Teilnahme an lehrreichen Diskussionen und Austausch von Ideen mit Gleichgesinnten bei Treffen in Präsenz und online.
5. Auf dem Laufenden bleiben über relevante Veranstaltungen und Bildungsmaterialien.

Die Teilnahme an der CoP kommt nicht nur der beruflichen Entwicklung zugute, sondern trägt auch zu den gemeinsamen Anstrengungen zur Verbesserung der Lebensmittelsicherheit in ganz Europa bei.

Sie können das Anmeldeformular für die Teilnahme an der CATALYSE CoP ausfüllen,

nachdem Sie diese Umfrage eingereicht haben. Die Partner von CATALYSE EU danken Ihnen

für Ihre Zeit und Ihre Bemühungen.

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Microsoft Forms

ANNEX 4: Stakeholder engagement online surveys – Ukrainian language

ОПИТУВАННЯ ПРОЄКТУ CATALYSE EU - ЗАЛУЧЕННЯ СТЕЙКХОЛДЕРІВ

Привіт і спасибі вам за участь у нашому опитуванні! Ми зацікавлені у ваших чесних думках та досвіді. Ваші відповіді залишатимуться конфіденційними, а опитування триватиме приблизно 17-19 хвилин.

Мета цього опитування полягає в тому, щоб зрозуміти основні потреби в інформації/темах із безпечності харчових продуктів, що широко застосовують кінцеві споживачі (офіційні органи контролю, оператори фуд-бізнесів, оцінювачі ризиків, пов'язані з продуктами харчування тощо).

Сьогодні екосистеми знань з безпечності харчових продуктів та інноваційні екосистеми недостатньо пов'язані. Ось чому наша головна мета — створити мережу в галузі інновацій у сфері безпечності харчових продуктів для обміну знаннями між кінцевими споживачами та інноваційними екосистемами. Вона включатиме поширення публічних подій, документів і звітів, а також створення онлайн-платформи для співпраці, що включатиме матеріали для навчання та освіти. Якщо ви хочете дізнатися більше про проєкт та його охоплення, будь ласка, зв'яжіться з нашою комунікаційною командою за адресою catalyse.eu@gmail.com

Це б не було можливим без вашої допомоги

ДЯКУЄМО ВАМ ЗА СПІВПРАЦЮ!

* Required

ДИСКЛЕЙМЕР

Це опитування має три частини. Опитування закриють 1-го жовтня 2024 р. Заповнюючи його, ви погоджуєтесь, що ваші відповіді використовуватимуть партнери проєкту CATALYSE EU для дослідницьких цілей. Результати опитування оброблятимуть анонімно, будь-яка надана інформація буде конфіденційною. Хоча ми й сподіваємося на вашу участь, ви не зобов'язані цього робити. Не соромтеся припинити в будь-який момент без необхідності повідомляти нам причини.

1. Чи даєте свою згоду на це? *

- Так, я би хотів_ла взяти участь у цьому опитуванні
- Ні, я вважаю за краще не брати участь у цьому опитуванні

2. Будь ласка, вкажіть свій гендер *

- Жінка
- Чоловік
- Інше
- Не хочу вказувати

3. Вкажіть, будь ласка, до якої вікової групи ви належите? *

- 20-30 років
- 31-45 років
- 46-60 років
- >60 років
- Не хочу вказувати

4. До якої групи стейкхолдерів ви б віднесли себе? *

- Академічне середовище / Дослідницький інститут
- Промисловість
- Політик / Представник органів державної влади
- Громадянське суспільство
- Інша група

5. Якщо визначаєте себе як представника промисловості, будь ласка, уточніть свою галузь

- Первинні виробники
- Харчування / Інградієнти / Обладнання
- Лабораторні послуги
- B2B консультації
- Логістична компанія
- Некомерційна організація
- Провайдер технологій для безпеки харчових продуктів
- Інша галузь

6. Якщо визначаєте себе як політика / представника органів державної влади, будь ласка, вкажіть свою галузь

- Політики / національний рівень (наприклад, міністерство) і можливо також міжнародний рівень (наприклад, Європейська комісія)
- Представники державних органів влади / органів, відповідальних за (національне, регіональне) управління ризиками в державах-членах
- Представники державних органів влади / органів, відповідальних за оцінку ризиків в державах-членах

Представники державних органів влади / міжнародних органів: EFSA, ECHA, EMA, ... Інші

7. Будь ласка, вкажіть свій досвід роботи, якщо ви не працюєте з продуктами харчування

8. Стосовно вашої роботи, чи могли б ви вказати, з якими групами продуктів харчування працюєте здебільшого? Будь ласка, укажіть усі варіанти, що стосуються вас:

- Свіжі фрукти та овочі
- Зерно та крупи
- Молочна продукція
- Напої
- М'ясо та птиця
- Риба та морепродукти
- Оброблені і упаковані харчові продукти
- Інгредієнти
- Рослинні продукти харчування
- Інше

ЧАСТИНА А

БУДЬ ЛАСКА, УКАЖІТЬ ВІДПОВІДНО ДО ВАШИХ ПОГЛЯДІВ РІВЕНЬ ЗАНЕПОКОЄННЯ ЩОДО ТАКИХ ТЕМ:

9. Заходи контролю патогенних мікроорганізмів та мікроорганізмів псування у сфері безпеки харчових продуктів та їхнє застосування: *

- Дуже низький рівень занепокоєння
- Низький рівень занепокоєння
- Середній рівень занепокоєння
- Високий рівень занепокоєння

10. Будь ласка, вкажіть причину вашого занепокоєння

11. Заходи контролю хімічних ризиків у сфері безпеки харчових продуктів та їхнє застосування: *

- Дуже низький рівень занепокоєння
- Низький рівень занепокоєння
- Середній рівень занепокоєння
- Високий рівень занепокоєння

12. Будь ласка, вкажіть причину вашого занепокоєння

13. Заходи контролю алергенів у сфері безпеки харчових продуктів та їхнє застосування: *

- Дуже низький рівень занепокоєння
- Низький рівень занепокоєння
- Середній рівень занепокоєння
- Високий рівень занепокоєння

14. Будь ласка, вкажіть причину вашого занепокоєння

15. Методи швидкого виявлення патогенних мікроорганізмів та мікроорганізмів псування: *

- Дуже низький рівень занепокоєння
- Низький рівень занепокоєння
- Середній рівень занепокоєння
- Високий рівень занепокоєння

16. Будь ласка, вкажіть, у якій галузі ви бачите потребу в удосконаленні цих методів

17. Методи швидкого виявлення хімічних речовин: *

- Дуже низький рівень занепокоєння
- Низький рівень занепокоєння
- Середній рівень занепокоєння
- Високий рівень занепокоєння

18. Будь ласка, вкажіть, у якій галузі ви бачите потребу в удосконаленні цих методів

19. Методи швидкого виявлення сполук алергенів: *

- Дуже низький рівень занепокоєння
- Низький рівень занепокоєння
- Середній рівень занепокоєння
- Високий рівень занепокоєння

20. Будь ласка, вкажіть, у якій галузі ви бачите потребу в удосконаленні цих методів

21. Рекомендації щодо гігієнічного дизайну та найкращі спільні практики: *

- Дуже низький рівень занепокоєння
- Низький рівень занепокоєння
- Середній рівень занепокоєння
- Високий рівень занепокоєння

22. Будь ласка, вкажіть, у якій галузі ви бачите потребу в удосконаленні цих практик

23. Ланцюг постачання харчових продуктів: відстежуваність і прозорість: *

- Дуже низький рівень занепокоєння
- Низький рівень занепокоєння
- Середній рівень занепокоєння
- Високий рівень занепокоєння

24. Інновації в матеріалах пакування: *

- Дуже низький рівень занепокоєння
- Низький рівень занепокоєння
- Середній рівень занепокоєння
- Високий рівень занепокоєння

25. Інновації в процесах пакування: *

- Дуже низький рівень занепокоєння
- Низький рівень занепокоєння
- Середній рівень занепокоєння
- Високий рівень занепокоєння

26. Інновації в активному пакуванні: *

- Дуже низький рівень занепокоєння
- Низький рівень занепокоєння
- Середній рівень занепокоєння
- Високий рівень занепокоєння

27. Чи використовуєте ви або ваша організація великі дані (Big Data) та/або інструменти штучного інтелекту у сфері безпеки харчових продуктів? *

- Так
- Ні

28. Якщо так, то які інструменти ШІ використовуєте?

Якщо ні, чому? Чи цікаво вам дізнатися більше про інструменти штучного інтелекту та їхнє застосування у сфері безпеки харчових продуктів? *

29. Наскільки ви задоволені безпекою харчових продуктів у вашій організації? Будь ласка, оцініть рівень:

1=менш задоволений і 10=Дуже задоволений

*

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	----

30. Наскільки ви задоволені безпекою харчових продуктів на рівні країни?

*1=менш задоволений і 10=Дуже задоволений **

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	----

31. Яку країну ви мали на увазі, коли відповідали на попереднє запитання? *

32. Чи є у вас інші побоювання, пов'язані з безпекою харчових продуктів та інноваціями?

*

- Так
- Ні

33. Якщо так, чи могли б ви вказати, що саме маєте на увазі?

34. Чи визнаєте ви цінність відвідувати навчання для вдосконалення безпеки та якості продуктів у вашому регіоні? *

Так

Ні

35. Якщо так, то яким конкретним аспектам, на вашу думку, слід віддати пріоритет? Якщо ні, то які перешкоди чи виклики впливають на вашу точку зору? *

ЧАСТИНА В:

ОСТАННІ ІННОВАЦІЇ ТА РІШЕННЯ, ЯКІ ПОТРІБНО БІЛЬШЕ ВВОДИТИ

36. Будь ласка, виберіть 5 напрямків, де ви нещодавно спостерігали інновації чи рішення, що спрямовані на вирішення критичних проблем та які потрібно частіше вводити стейкхолдерам/більшій кількості стейкхолдерів *

Please select at most 5 options.

- Нові технології для запобігання небезпекам і ризикам
- Виявлення джерел забруднення в харчовому ланцюгу
- Розвиток моніторингу та виявлення небезпек у харчовому ланцюзі (наприклад, використання датчиків, методи швидкого виявлення патогенних мікроорганізмів, мікотоксинів, хімічних забрудників тощо)
- Внесок у повногеномне секвенування (WGS) для безпеки харчових виробництв
- Нові та альтернативні інгредієнти або рішення, що підвищують безпечність кінцевого продукту (наприклад, рослини/ мікроорганізми/джерела білку/прецизійна ферментація)
- Альтернативи конвенційним методам зберігання
- Інструменти прогнозування і моделювання (наприклад, розвиток прогнозної токсикології, прогнозної мікробіології)
- Застосування нанотехнологій у харчових виробництвах
- Новинки технології бар'єрів у харчових виробництвах
- Нові альтернативні харчові матриці (наприклад, комахи, м'ясо з пробірки, харчові відходи)
- Нові аналітичні методи та нормативні потреби для нових харчових матриць
- Переробка харчових відходів у цінні ресурси
- Інноваційні рішення для пакування харчових продуктів і маркування для зменшення харчових відходів (або їхнього уникнення) та сталого розвитку
- Нові процеси очищення та гігієнічні процедури із застосуванням сучасних рішень
- Цифрові рішення для підвищення прозорості, безпеки та відстеження харчового ланцюга
- Нові стандарти та логістика для харчових виробництв
- Нові рішення для безпечних систем зберігання і транспортування
- Краще розуміння та пом'якшення впливу бактерій, стійких до антибіотиків
- In silico та in vitro методи для стійких безпечних харчових систем
- Інструменти штучного інтелекту для покращення контролю безпечності харчових продуктів у харчовому ланцюзі
- Other

ЧАСТИНА C: МЕРЕЖА ТА ФАХОВА СПІЛЬНОТА

У програмі CATALYSE ми очікуємо створити спеціалізовані комунікаційні матеріали, що підсумують та покажуть найкращі практики та інновації, близькі до впровадження в практику, але які недостатньо відомі кінцевим користувачам.

37. У якому типі/форматі навчання ви б хотіли отримати цю інформацію? *

- Віртуальні/офлайн симпозиуми в «класній кімнаті»
- Практичні курси
- Сесії на місцях
- Прикладна навчальна сесія
- Вебінари
- Курси самонавчання
- Other

38. Будь ласка, вкажіть інші формати навчання або матеріали, яким би ви надали перевагу

39. Яким темам ви б віддали пріоритет для навчання/курсів? *

Please select at most 5 options.

- Моніторинг середовища обробки
- Найкращі практики роботи з алергенами (Звіти FAO/WHO 2022)
- Мікробіологічні аналіз і техніки продуктів харчування
- Положення щодо безпечності продуктів харчування та дотримання вимог
- Контроль якості продуктів харчування
- Санітарія та гігієнічний дизайн в обробці продуктів харчування
- Маркування продуктів та дотримання вимог до пакування
- Нові інструменти для моніторингу та виявлення небезпек
- Вивчення цифрових рішень та їхнього потенціалу в покращенні безпечності продуктів харчування
- Нові та альтернативні рішення/технології для покращення кінцевих продуктів (нанотехнології, нові інгредієнти, природні протимікробні речовини)
- Кількісна мікробіологія
- Кількісна оцінка мікробіологічного ризику (QMRA)
- Інтерпретація небезпек, ризиків, ймовірності, тяжкості
- Якісний відбір проб і тестування: методи та статистика
- HACCP і процес перевірки: інструменти для моніторингу та виявлення небезпек
- Культура безпеки продуктів харчування
- Харчове шахрайство
- Нові ризики, що з'являються
- Сканування горизонту
- Страхування та безпечність продуктів харчування
- Other

ЧИ БАЖАЄТЕ ВИ ДОЛУЧИТИСЯ ДО ФАХОВОЇ СПІЛЬНОТИ CATALYSE (CoP)?

Як частина CATALYSE, ми встановлюємо загальноєвропейську фахову спільноту (CoP) з тематичними розділами з конкретних тем/технологій через цифрову платформу, щоб сприяти взаємодії та розповсюджувати актуальні знання і постанови, навчальні матеріали й актуальні заходи. Ця фахова спільнота буде динамічним форумом, що сприятиме передачі й засвоєнню знань та інновацій з безпечності харчових продуктів через:

1. Співпрацю з різноманітною мережею стейкхолдерів харчової системи, що включає дослідників, представників індустрії, кінцевих користувачів та політиків.
2. Доступ до передових знань і ресурсів з безпечності харчових продуктів та інновацій.
3. Сприяння вдосконаленню практик і технологій безпечності харчових продуктів.
4. Участь у змістовних дискусіях та обмін ідеями з колегами через фізичні та онлайн-зустрічі.
5. Поінформованість про актуальні події та навчальні матеріали.

Участь у фаховій спільноті не лише посприяє професійному розвитку, але й також стане частиною колективного зусилля для покращення безпечності харчових продуктів у Європі.

Ви може заповнити реєстраційну форму для приєднання до фахової спільноти CATALYSE після відправлення опитувальника. Партнери CATALYSE EU дякують вам за ваші час та зусилля.

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ANNEX 5: Stakeholder engagement online surveys – Portuguese language

INQUÉRITO DO PROJETO CATALYSE EU - ENVOLVIMENTO DE stakeholders (PT)

Olá, agradecemos desde já a sua participação no nosso inquérito! Estamos interessados nas suas opiniões e experiências! As suas respostas permanecerão confidenciais e este questionário demorará aproximadamente 15 minutos a ser respondido.

O objetivo deste inquérito é compreender as principais necessidades em termos de informação/conhecimento sobre questões de segurança alimentar relevantes para diferentes utilizadores (autoridades oficiais de controlo, operadores de empresas do setor alimentar, avaliadores dos riscos de segurança alimentar, etc.).

Atualmente os ecossistemas de conhecimento e de inovação em questões de segurança alimentar não estão suficientemente ligados. O nosso objetivo é criar uma rede na área da inovação em segurança alimentar para a troca de conhecimentos entre os utilizadores finais e os ecossistemas de inovação, incluindo a divulgação de eventos públicos, partilha de artigos científicos e relatórios, bem como a criação de uma plataforma colaborativa online que incluirá materiais educativos e de formação. Se desejar mais informações sobre o projeto, não hesite em contactar a nossa equipa de comunicação: catalyse.eu@gmail.com

Este projeto não será possível sem a sua colaboração!

OBRIGADA!

* Required

Declaração de exoneração de responsabilidade

Este inquérito é constituído por três partes e irá encerrar no dia 1 de outubro de 2024.

Ao preencher este inquérito consente que as suas respostas sejam usadas pelos parceiros do projeto CATALYSE EU para fins de investigação. Os resultados serão tratados de forma anónima e qualquer informação fornecida será tratada confidencialmente. Embora esperemos que participe, não tem qualquer obrigação de o fazer. Pode desistir do inquérito em qualquer altura, sem ter de nos dar qualquer justificação.

1

Concorda? *

Sim, eu gostaria de participar neste inquérito

Não, prefiro não participar

2

Por favor indique seu género *

- Mulher
- Homem
- Outro
- Prefiro não dizer

3

Por favor indique a sua faixa etária? *

- 20-30 anos
- 31-45 anos
- 46-60 anos
- >60 anos
- Prefiro não dizer

4

Em que grupo de stakeholders se inclui? *

- Academia / Instituto de investigação
- Indústria
- Decisores políticos / Autoridades públicas
- Sociedade civil
- Other

5

Se na resposta 4 assinalou "indústria", por favor especifique a área

- Setor primário
- Alimentos / Ingredientes / Equipamento de processamento
- Serviços laboratoriais
- Consultoria B2B
- Empresa de logística
- Organização sem fins lucrativos
- Fornecedor de tecnologias de segurança alimentar
- Other

6

Se na resposta 4 assinalou "decisores políticos / autoridades públicas", por favor especifique o seu domínio

- Decisores políticos / nível nacional (por exemplo: Ministério) ou nível internacional (por exemplo: Comissão Europeia)
- Autoridades públicas / autoridades responsáveis pela gestão (nacional, regional) dos riscos nos Estados-Membros
- Autoridades públicas/autoridades responsáveis pela avaliação de riscos nos Estados-Membros
- Autoridades públicas/autoridades internacionais: EFSA, ECHA, EMA, ...
- Other

7

Caso não trabalhe com alimentos, especifique por favor a sua experiência profissional

8

Caso a sua atividade se relacione com alimentos, indique quais os principais grupos com que trabalha? Assinale todas as opções aplicáveis:

- Frutas frescas e vegetais
- Grãos e cereais
- Laticínios
- Bebidas
- Carnes e Aves
- Peixe e Marisco
- Alimentos processados e embalados
- Ingredientes
- Alimentos à base de plantas
- Other

PARTE A

INDIQUE, DE ACORDO COM O SEU PONTO DE VISTA, O SEU NÍVEL DE PREOCUPAÇÃO RELATIVAMENTE A:

9

Medidas de controlo microbiano e segurança alimentar: *

- Preocupação muito baixa
- Preocupação baixa
- Preocupação média
- Preocupação alta

10

Por favor, especifique qual o principal motivo da sua preocupação

11

Medidas de controlo de riscos químicos e segurança alimentar: *

- Preocupação muito baixa
- Preocupação baixa
- Preocupação média
- Preocupação alta

12

Por favor, especifique qual o principal motivo da sua preocupação

13

Medidas de controlo de alergénios e segurança alimentar: *

- Preocupação muito baixa
- Preocupação baixa
- Preocupação média
- Preocupação alta

14

Por favor, especifique qual o principal motivo da sua preocupação

15

Métodos rápidos de deteção de microrganismos patogénicos e de deterioração: *

- Preocupação muito baixa
- Preocupação baixa
- Preocupação média
- Preocupação alta

16

Por favor, especifique em que área considera necessário melhorar estes métodos

17

Métodos rápidos de deteção de substâncias químicas: *

- Preocupação muito baixa
- Preocupação baixa
- Preocupação média
- Preocupação alta

18

Por favor, especifique em que área considera necessário melhorar estes métodos

19

Métodos rápidos de deteção de compostos alergénios: *

- Preocupação muito baixa
- Preocupação baixa
- Preocupação média
- Preocupação alta

20

Por favor, especifique em que área considera necessário melhorar estes métodos

21

Recomendações de design higiénico e de boas práticas de higiene: *

- Preocupação muito baixa
- Preocupação baixa
- Preocupação média
- Preocupação alta

22

Por favor, especifique em que área considera necessário melhorar estes métodos

23

Cadeia de abastecimento alimentar: rastreabilidade e transparência: *

- Preocupação muito baixa
- Preocupação baixa
- Preocupação média
- Preocupação alta

24

Inovações em materiais de embalagem: *

- Preocupação muito baixa
- Preocupação baixa
- Preocupação média
- Preocupação alta

25

Inovações no processo de embalagem: *

- Preocupação muito baixa
- Preocupação baixa
- Preocupação média
- Preocupação alta

26

Inovações em embalagens ativas: *

- Preocupação muito baixa
- Preocupação baixa
- Preocupação média
- Preocupação alta

27

A sua organização utiliza ferramentas de big data e/ou de inteligência artificial (IA) aplicadas à segurança dos alimentos? *

- Sim
- Não

28

Em caso afirmativo, quais ferramentas de IA utiliza?

Se não, por quê? Está interessado em saber mais sobre ferramentas de IA e as suas aplicações na segurança alimentar? *

29

Quão satisfeito está com a segurança alimentar da sua organização? Avalie o nível de satisfação:

*1=Menos satisfeito e 10 = Muito satisfeito **

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	----

30

Qual é o seu grau de satisfação com a segurança alimentar a "nível nacional"?

*1=Menos satisfeito e 10 = Muito satisfeito **

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	----

31

Ao mencionar a sua satisfação, a que "país" se refere? *

32

Tem outras preocupações relacionadas com a segurança alimentar e com a inovação? *

- Sim
- Não

33

Em caso afirmativo, pode indicar a que preocupações se refere?

34

Reconhece o valor da participação em ações de formação para melhorar a segurança e a qualidade dos produtos na sua área? *

Sim

Não

35

Se sim, a que aspetos específicos considera que deve ser dada prioridade?
Em caso negativo, que obstáculos ou desafios influenciam a sua perspetiva? *

PARTE B:

INOVAÇÃO RECENTE & SOLUÇÕES QUE PRECISAM DE MAIOR ADOÇÃO

36

Selecione 5 áreas em que observou recentemente inovações ou soluções que respondem a necessidades críticas e que devem ser adoptadas com maior frequência/por mais partes interessadas *

Please select at most 5 options.

- Novas tecnologias para prevenção de perigos e riscos
- Identificação de fontes de contaminação ao longo da cadeia alimentar
- Desenvolvimentos na monitorização e deteção de perigos ao longo da cadeia alimentar (por exemplo, utilização de sensores, métodos de deteção rápida de microrganismos patogénicos, micotoxinas, contaminantes químicos, etc.)
- Contributos da Sequenciação Completa do Genoma (WGS) para a segurança alimentar
- Ingredientes ou soluções novas e alternativas que melhorem a segurança do produto final (por exemplo, plantas/microrganismos/fontes de proteínas/fermentações de precisão)
- Alternativas aos métodos convencionais de conservação
- Ferramentas de previsão e modelização (por exemplo, desenvolvimento de toxicologia preditiva, microbiologia preditiva)
- Aplicação de nanotecnologias na produção de alimentos
- Tecnologias de barreira inovadoras aplicada à produção de alimentos
- Matrizes alimentares novas/alternativas (por exemplo, insetos, carne in vitro, subprodutos alimentares)
- Métodos analíticos e necessidades de regulamentação para novas matrizes alimentares
- Transformação de resíduos alimentares em recursos de valor
- Inovação em soluções de embalagem e rotulagem de géneros alimentícios para redução/prevenção do desperdício alimentar e promoção da sustentabilidade
- Novos processos de limpeza e procedimentos de higiene utilizando soluções modernas
- Soluções digitais para aumentar a transparência, segurança e rastreabilidade da cadeia alimentar
- Novos padrões e logística aplicados à produção de alimentos
- Novas soluções para sistemas de armazenamento e transporte seguros
- Melhor compreensão e mitigação de bactérias resistentes a antibióticos
- Métodos in sílico e in vitro aplicados a sistemas alimentares seguros e sustentáveis
- Ferramentas de inteligência artificial para melhorar o controlo da segurança alimentar na cadeia alimentar
- Other

PARTE C: REDE & COMUNIDADE DE PRÁTICA

No projeto CATALYSE é esperada a criação de materiais de comunicação personalizados que resumam, partilhem e apresentem as melhores práticas existentes e inovações com possibilidade de implementação em contexto real, mas não suficientemente conhecidas pelos utilizadores finais.

37

Qual o tipo/formato de formação em que gostaria de receber a informação? *

Simpósios físicos em "sala de aula" ou virtuais

Cursos práticos

Formação à medida

Sessão de formação aplicada

Seminários on-line

Cursos de autoaprendizagem

Other

38

Especifique outros formatos ou materiais de formação da sua preferência

39

A que temas daria prioridade para a formação/cursos? *

Please select at most 5 options.

- Monitorização do ambiente de processamento
- Boas Práticas de Gestão de Alergénios (Relatórios FAO/OMS 2022)
- Técnicas e análises microbiológicas de alimentos
- Regulamentação e Conformidade em Segurança Alimentar
- Controlo da Qualidade na Produção de Alimentos
- Design de Higiene e Limpeza no Processamento de Alimentos
- Conformidade com Rotulagem e Embalagem de Alimentos
- Novas ferramentas para monitorizar e detetar perigos
- Estudo de soluções digitais e do seu potencial na melhoria da segurança alimentar
- Soluções/tecnologias novas e alternativas para melhoria dos produtos finais (nanotecnologias, novos ingredientes, substâncias antimicrobianas naturais)
- Microbiologia Quantitativa
- Avaliação quantitativa dos riscos microbiológicos (QMRA)
- Interpretação de perigos, riscos, probabilidade, gravidade
- Amostragem e Testes Qualitativos: Métodos e estatísticas
- HACCP e validação de processos: Ferramentas de monitorização e deteção de perigos
- Cultura de Segurança Alimentar
- Fraude Alimentar
- Riscos emergentes
- Monitorização de Tendências Futuras
- Seguros e Segurança Alimentar
- Other

DESEJA TORNAR-SE MEMBRO DA COMUNIDADE DE PRÁTICA (CoP) DO CATALYSE UE?

Como parte do CATALYSE UE, estamos a criar uma comunidade de prática (CoP) à escala europeia com capítulos temáticos sobre tópicos/tecnologias específicos através de uma plataforma digital para facilitar a interação, a divulgação de conhecimentos e regulamentos, materiais educativos e eventos relevantes. Esta CoP será um fórum dinâmico para promover a transferência de conhecimentos e a adoção de conhecimentos e inovação em matéria de segurança alimentar através de:

1. Colaboração com uma rede diversificada de intervenientes no sistema alimentar, incluindo investigadores, indústria, utilizadores finais e decisores políticos.
2. Acesso a conhecimentos e recursos de ponta sobre segurança alimentar e inovação.
3. Contribuição para o avanço das práticas e tecnologias de segurança alimentar.
4. Participação em debates construtivos e troca de ideias com os seus pares através de reuniões físicas e online.
5. Informação sobre eventos relevantes e materiais educativos.

A participação na CoP não só beneficiará o seu desenvolvimento profissional, como também contribuirá para o esforço coletivo de melhorar a segurança alimentar em toda a Europa.

Pode preencher o formulário de registo para aderir à CoP (CATALYSE EU) após a submissão deste inquérito. Os parceiros do CATALYSE EU agradecem o seu tempo e esforço.

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ANNEX 6: Stakeholder engagement online surveys – Italian language

Sondaggio sul progetto CATALYSE

Salve e grazie per aver partecipato al nostro sondaggio! Siamo interessati alle vostre opinioni ed esperienze sincere. Le vostre risposte rimarranno riservate e il sondaggio dovrebbe durare circa 10-12 minuti.

Lo scopo di questo sondaggio è quello di comprendere le principali esigenze in termini di informazioni/conoscenze sulla sicurezza alimentare ampiamente applicate dagli utenti finali (autorità di controllo ufficiali, operatori del settore alimentare, valutatori dei rischi per la sicurezza alimentare, ecc.)

Oggi gli ecosistemi della conoscenza e dell'innovazione in materia di sicurezza alimentare non sono sufficientemente collegati. Per questo motivo, il nostro obiettivo principale è creare una rete nell'area dell'innovazione della sicurezza alimentare per lo scambio di conoscenze tra utenti finali ed ecosistemi dell'innovazione. Ciò comprenderà la diffusione di eventi pubblici, documenti e relazioni, e la creazione di una piattaforma collaborativa on-line che includa la disponibilità di materiali per la formazione e l'istruzione. Se desiderate saperne di più sul progetto e sulla sua portata, non esitate a contattare il nostro team di comunicazione all'indirizzo catalyse.eu@gmail.com.

Non sarebbe possibile senza il vostro aiuto 😊

GRAZIE PER LA VOSTRA COLLABORAZIONE!

*Obbligatoria

DISCLAIMER

Questo sondaggio è composto da tre parti. Compilando questo sondaggio, acconsentite all'utilizzo delle vostre risposte da parte dei partner del progetto CATALYSE EU a scopo di ricerca. I risultati del sondaggio saranno gestiti in modo anonimo e tutte le informazioni fornite saranno trattate in modo confidenziale. Ci auguriamo che partecipiate, ma non siete obbligati a farlo. Sentitevi liberi di ritirarvi in qualsiasi momento senza doverci fornire alcuna motivazione.

* Required

1. Sei d'accordo? *

- Sì, desidero partecipare a questo sondaggio
- No, preferisco non partecipare a questo sondaggio

2. Indicare il proprio genere *

- Donna
- Uomo
- Altro
- Preferisco non rispondere

3. Indica la fascia d'età a cui appartieni *

- 20-30 anni
- 31-45 anni
- 46-60 anni
- >60 anni
- Preferisco non rispondere

4. In quale gruppo di stakeholder ti collocheresti? *

- Accademia/Istituto di ricerca
- Industria
- Politici/Autorità pubbliche
- Società civile
- Other

5. Se vi identificate come stakeholder del settore, specificate il vostro dominio

- Produttori primari
- Alimenti / Ingredienti / Processore di apparecchiature
- Servizi di laboratorio
- Consulenza B2B
- Società di logistica
- Organizzazione non profit
- Fornitore di tecnologie per la sicurezza alimentare
- Other

6. Se vi identificate come responsabili politici / Autorità pubbliche, specificate il vostro dominio

- Politico / livello nazionale (es. Ministero) e possibilmente anche livello internazionale (es. Commissione Europea)
- Autorità pubbliche / autorità responsabili della gestione del rischio (nazionale, regionale) negli Stati Membri
- Autorità pubbliche / autorità responsabili della valutazione del rischio negli Stati membri

Autorità pubbliche / autorità internazionali: EFSA, ECHA, EMA, ...

Other

7. Si prega di specificare la vostra esperienza lavorativa nel caso in cui non si lavori con gli alimenti

8. In relazione al suo lavoro, potrebbe indicare con quali gruppi alimentari lavora principalmente? Selezionare tutte le opzioni che si riferiscono a lei:

- Frutta e verdura fresca
- Grani e cereali
- Prodotti lattiero-caseari
- Bevande
- Carni e Pollame
- Pesce e Frutti di mare
- Alimenti trasformati e confezionati
- Ingredienti
- Alimenti a base vegetale
- Other

PARTE A**INDICARE, SECONDO IL VOSTRO PUNTO DI VISTA, IL LIVELLO DI PREOCCUPAZIONE PER QUANTO RIGUARDA:**

9. Misure di controllo della sicurezza alimentare con microrganismi patogeni e di deterioramento e loro applicazioni: *

- Preoccupazione molto bassa
- Preoccupazione bassa
- Preoccupazione media
- Preoccupazione elevata

10. Si prega di specificare l'obiettivo del vostro interesse

11. Misure di controllo nella sicurezza alimentare con rischio chimico e loro applicazioni: *

- Preoccupazione molto bassa
- Preoccupazione bassa
- Preoccupazione media
- Preoccupazione elevata

12. Si prega di specificare l'obiettivo del vostro interesse

13. Misure di controllo nella sicurezza alimentare con allergeni e loro applicazioni: *

- Preoccupazione molto bassa
- Preoccupazione bassa
- Preoccupazione media
- Preoccupazione elevata

14. Si prega di specificare l'obiettivo del vostro interesse

15. Metodi di rilevamento rapido di microrganismi patogeni e di deterioramento: *

- Preoccupazione molto bassa
- Preoccupazione bassa
- Preoccupazione media
- Preoccupazione elevata

16. Si prega di specificare in quale campo si vede la necessità di migliorare questi metodi

17. Metodi di rilevamento rapido di sostanze chimiche: *

- Preoccupazione molto bassa
- Preoccupazione bassa
- Preoccupazione media
- Preoccupazione elevata

18. Si prega di specificare in quale campo si vede la necessità di migliorare questi metodi

19. Metodi di rilevamento rapido dei composti allergenici: *

- Preoccupazione molto bassa
- Preoccupazione bassa
- Preoccupazione media
- Preoccupazione elevata

20. Si prega di specificare in quale campo si vede la necessità di migliorare questi metodi

21. Raccomandazioni di progettazione igienica e migliori pratiche condivise: *

- Preoccupazione molto bassa
- Preoccupazione bassa
- Preoccupazione media
- Preoccupazione elevata

22. Si prega di specificare in quale campo si vede la necessità di migliorare queste pratiche

23. Filiera alimentare: tracciabilità e trasparenza *

- Preoccupazione molto bassa
- Preoccupazione bassa
- Preoccupazione media
- Preoccupazione elevata

24. Innovazioni nell'imballaggio in relazione ai materiali: *

- Preoccupazione molto bassa
- Preoccupazione bassa
- Preoccupazione media
- Preoccupazione elevata

25. Innovazioni nel campo dell'imballaggio in relazione al processo di confezionamento: *

- Preoccupazione molto bassa
- Preoccupazione bassa
- Preoccupazione media

Preoccupazione elevata

26. Innovazioni di packaging in relazione agli imballaggi attivi: *

- Preoccupazione molto bassa
- Preoccupazione bassa
- Preoccupazione media
- Preoccupazione elevata

27. La vostra organizzazione o voi stessi utilizzate strumenti di big data e/o intelligenza artificiale applicati alla sicurezza alimentare? *

- Sì
- No

28. Se sì, quali strumenti di IA utilizzate?

Se no, perché? Siete interessati a conoscere altri strumenti di IA e le loro applicazioni nella sicurezza alimentare? *

29. Quanto è soddisfatto della sicurezza alimentare della sua organizzazione? La preghiamo di valutare il livello di soddisfazione: *

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	----

Poco soddisfatto

Molto soddisfatto

30. Quanto siete soddisfatti a "livello di Paese" per quanto riguarda la sicurezza alimentare? *

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	----

Poco soddisfatto

Molto soddisfatto

31. Parlando della sua soddisfazione, a quale "Paese" si riferiva? *

32. Avete altre preoccupazioni relative alla sicurezza e all'innovazione alimentare? *

- Sì
- No

33. In caso affermativo, può indicare a quali preoccupazioni si riferisce?

34. Riconosce l'utilità di frequentare corsi di formazione per migliorare la sicurezza e la qualità dei prodotti nella sua zona? *

Sì

No

35. Se sì, quali aspetti specifici ritenete debbano essere prioritari?
Se no, quali barriere o sfide influenzano la vostra prospettiva? *

PARTE B: INNOVAZIONI RECENTI E SOLUZIONI CHE NECESSITANO DI MAGGIORE ADOZIONE

36. Selezionate 5 aree in cui avete recentemente osservato innovazioni o soluzioni che rispondono a esigenze critiche e che devono essere adottate più frequentemente/da un maggior numero di stakeholder *

Please select 5 options.

- Nuove tecnologie per la prevenzione dei pericoli e dei rischi
- Identificazione delle fonti di contaminazione lungo la catena alimentare
- Sviluppi nel monitoraggio e nel rilevamento dei pericoli lungo la catena alimentare (ad esempio, uso di sensori, metodi di rilevamento rapido di microrganismi patogeni, micotossine, contaminanti chimici, ecc.)
- Contributo al sequenziamento dell'intero genoma per la sicurezza delle produzioni alimentari.
- Ingredienti o soluzioni nuove e alternative che migliorano la sicurezza del prodotto finale (ad es. piante/microrganismi/fonti proteiche/ fermentazioni di precisione)
- Alternative ai metodi di conservazione convenzionali
- Strumenti predittivi e di modellazione (ad esempio, sviluppo della tossicologia predittiva, microbiologia predittiva)
- Applicazione delle nanotecnologie alle produzioni alimentari
- Novità sulle tecnologie ad ostacoli applicate alle produzioni alimentari
- Nuove matrici alimentari alternative (ad es. insetti, carne in vitro, sottoprodotti alimentari)
- Nuovi metodi analitici ed esigenze normative per le nuove matrici alimentari
- Up-cycling dei rifiuti alimentari in risorse preziose
- Innovazione nelle soluzioni di confezionamento ed etichettatura degli alimenti per la riduzione/prevenzione dei rifiuti alimentari e la promozione della sostenibilità
- Nuovi processi di pulizia e procedure igieniche che applicano soluzioni moderne
- Soluzioni digitali per aumentare la trasparenza, la sicurezza e la tracciabilità della catena alimentare
- Nuovi standard e logistica applicata alle produzioni alimentari
- Nuove soluzioni per sistemi di stoccaggio e trasporto sicuri
- Migliore comprensione e mitigazione dei batteri resistenti agli antibiotici
- Metodi in silico e in vitro applicati per sistemi alimentari sicuri e sostenibili
- Strumenti di intelligenza artificiale per migliorare il controllo della sicurezza alimentare nella catena alimentare
- Other

PARTE C: RETE E COMUNITÀ DI PRATICA

Nel programma CATALYSE si prevede di creare materiali di comunicazione su misura che riassumano, condividano e presentino le migliori pratiche e le innovazioni esistenti che sono prossime all'implementazione nella pratica, ma non sono sufficientemente conosciute dagli utenti finali.

37. In quale tipo/formato di formazione desidera ricevere le informazioni? *

- Convegni virtuali/fisici "in classe"
- Corsi pratici
- Sessioni in loco
- Sessione di formazione applicata
- Webinar
- Corsi di autoapprendimento
- Other

38. Si prega di specificare altri formati o materiali di formazione che si preferiscono

39. A quali argomenti dareste la priorità per i corsi di formazione? *

- Monitoraggio dell'ambiente di lavorazione
- Migliori pratiche di gestione degli allergeni (Rapporti FAO/OMS 2022)
- Analisi e tecniche microbiologiche degli alimenti
- Regolamenti e conformità in materia di sicurezza alimentare
- Controllo di qualità nella produzione alimentare
- Progettazione igienico-sanitaria nella lavorazione degli alimenti
- Conformità dell'etichettatura e del confezionamento degli alimenti
- Nuovi strumenti per il monitoraggio e l'individuazione dei pericoli
- Studio delle soluzioni digitali e del loro potenziale nel migliorare la sicurezza alimentare
- Soluzioni/tecnologie nuove e alternative per il miglioramento dei prodotti finali (nanotecnologie, nuovi ingredienti, sostanze antimicrobiche naturali)
- Microbiologia quantitativa
- Valutazioni quantitative del rischio microbiologico
- Interpretazione di pericoli, rischi, probabilità, gravità
- Campionamento e test qualitativi: Metodi e statistiche
- HACCP e convalida dei processi: Strumenti per il monitoraggio e l'individuazione dei pericoli
- Cultura della sicurezza alimentare
- Frodi alimentari
- Rischi emergenti
- Scansione dell'orizzonte
- Assicurazione e sicurezza alimentare
- Other

DESIDERATE DIVENTARE MEMBRI DELLA COMUNITÀ DI PRATICHE DI CATALYSE?

Nell'ambito di CATALYSE, stiamo creando una comunità di pratica (CdP) a livello europeo con capitoli tematici su argomenti/tecnologie specifiche attraverso una piattaforma digitale per facilitare l'interazione, la diffusione di conoscenze e normative rilevanti, materiali didattici ed eventi pertinenti. Questa CdP sarà un forum dinamico per promuovere il trasferimento di conoscenze e l'adozione di conoscenze e innovazioni in materia di sicurezza alimentare attraverso:

1. La collaborazione con una rete eterogenea di soggetti interessati al sistema alimentare, tra cui ricercatori, industria, utenti finali e responsabili delle politiche.
2. L'accesso a conoscenze e risorse all'avanguardia in materia di sicurezza alimentare e innovazione.
3. Contribuendo al progresso delle pratiche e delle tecnologie di sicurezza alimentare.
4. Partecipare a discussioni significative e scambiare idee con i colleghi attraverso incontri fisici e online.
5. Rimanere informati su eventi e materiali didattici rilevanti.

La partecipazione alla CdP non solo favorirà lo sviluppo professionale, ma contribuirà anche allo sforzo collettivo per migliorare la sicurezza alimentare in Europa.

È possibile compilare il modulo di registrazione per entrare a far parte della CdP CATALYSE dopo aver inviato questo sondaggio.

I partner di CATALYSE EU vi ringraziano per il vostro tempo e i vostri sforzi.

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Microsoft Forms

ANNEX 7: Stakeholder engagement online surveys – Finnish language

CATALYSE EU -PROJEKTIN SIDOSRYHMÄ-KYSELY (FIN)

Kiitos osallistumisestasi kyselyymme! Olemme kiinnostuneita rehellisistä mielipiteistäsi ja kokemuksistasi. Vastauksesi käsitellään luottamuksellisesti. Kyselyyn vastaamiseen kuluu aikaa noin 15 minuuttia.

Tämän kyselyn tarkoituksena on ymmärtää elintarviketurvallisuuden parissa työskentelevien tietotarpeita. Kyselyn kohderyhmää ovat esimerkiksi elintarvikkeiden valvonnan, teollisuuden ja riskinarvioinnin parissa työskentelevät.

Elintarviketurvallisuustieto ja innovaatioekosysteemit eivät nykyisin kohtaa riittävästi. Tähän tarpeeseen pyrimme projektissamme vastaamaan elintarviketurvallisuuteen liittyvien innovaatioiden levittämiseen erikoistuneella verkostolla. Verkostossa voidaan jakaa esimerkiksi tapahtumakutsuja, artikkeleita sekä raportteja, sekä perustetaan erityinen alan koulutukseen liittyvä sivusto. Jos haluat lisää tietoa projektista, voit olla yhteydessä viestintätiimiimme: catalyse.eu@gmail.com.

Kiitos paljon avustasi!

* Required

VASTUUVAPAUCLAUSEKE

Tämä kysely koostuu kolmesta osasta. Kyselyyn voi vastata 1.10.2024 asti.

Vastaamalla kyselyyn suostut siihen, että CATALYSE EU -projektikumppanit voivat käyttää vastauksiasi tutkimus-tarkoituksiin. Kyselyn vastaukset käsitellään anonyymisti, ja kaikkea annettua tietoa käsitellään luottamuksellisesti. Kyselyyn vastaaminen on vapaaehtoista. Voit halutessasi peruuttaa osallistumisesi kyselyyn koska tahansa kyselyn aikana kertomatta meille syytä.

1

Suostumus osallistua kyselyyn: *

Kyllä, haluan osallistua tähän kyselyyn

Ei, en halua osallistua tähän kyselyyn

2

Sukupuoli *

Nainen

Mies

Muu

En halua vastata

3

Mihin ikäryhmään kuulut *

- 20–30 vuotta
- 31–45 vuotta
- 46–60 vuotta
- yli 60 vuotta
- En halua vastata

4

Mikä ryhmä kuvaa parhaiten taustaasi *

- Yliopisto tai tutkimusorganisaatio
- Elintarviketeollisuus
- Julkinen hallinto ja muut viranomaiset
- Kansalaiset
- Other

5

Mikäli työskentelet elintarviketeollisuudessa, valitse itsellesi sopivin ala

- Alkutuotanto
- Elintarviketeollisuus tai elintarviketeollisuuden laitteistojen tuottajat
- Laboratoriot
- B2B-konsultointi
- Logistiikka
- Yhdistykset ja muut voittoa tavoittelemattomat organisaatiot
- Elintarviketurvallisuusalan teknologioiden tuottajat
- Other

6

Mikäli työskentelet julkisessa hallinnossa, valitse itsellesi sopivin ala

- Kansallisen tai kansainvälisen tason päättäjät (esim. ministeriöt, Euroopan komissio)
- Kansallisen tai alueellisen tason riskinhallintaviranomaiset
- Kansallisen tai alueellisen tason riskinarviointiviranomaiset
- Kansainvälisen tason viranomaiset (esim. EFSA, ECHA, EMA)
- Other

7

Mikäli et työskentele elintarvikkeiden parissa, kuvaile työnkuvaasi:

8

Minkä elintarvikeryhmien kanssa työskentelet ensisijaisesti? Valitse kaikki sopivat ryhmät.

- Tuoreet hedelmät ja vihannekset
- Viljat ja viljatuotteet
- Maitotuotteet
- Juomat
- Liha ja siipikarjanliha
- Kala- ja äyriäistuotteet
- Käsitellyt ja pakatut elintarvikkeet
- Raaka-aineet
- Kasvispohjaiset elintarvikkeet
- Other

OSA A

Arvioi kuinka suureen huoleen seuraavat ilmiöt antavat mielestäsi aihetta:

9

Patogeenien ja pilaajamikrobien aiheuttaman elintarviketurvallisuusriskien hallintatoimenpiteet ja niiden soveltaminen *

- Hyvin vähäinen huolen taso
- Vähäinen huolen taso
- Keskiverto huolen taso
- Suuri huolen taso

10

Mistä olet erityisesti huolestunut?

11

Kemiallisten elintarviketurvallisuusriskien hallintatoimenpiteet ja niiden soveltaminen *

- Hyvin vähäinen huolen taso
- Vähäinen huolen taso
- Keskiverto huolen taso
- Suuri huolen taso

12

Mistä olet erityisesti huolestunut?

13

Allergeenien aiheuttamien elintarviketurvallisuusriskien hallintatoimenpiteet ja niiden soveltaminen

*

- Hyvin vähäinen huolen taso
- Vähäinen huolen taso
- Keskiverto huolen taso
- Suuri huolen taso

14

Mistä olet erityisesti huolestunut?

15

Pikamenetelmät patogeenien ja pilaajamikrobien havaitsemiselle *

- Hyvin vähäinen huolen taso
- Vähäinen huolen taso
- Keskiverto huolen taso
- Suuri huolen taso

16

Miten näitä menetelmiä tulisi parantaa?

17

Pikamenetelmät kemiallisten aineiden havaitsemiselle *

- Hyvin vähäinen huolen taso
- Vähäinen huolen taso
- Keskiverto huolen taso
- Suuri huolen taso

18

Miten näitä menetelmiä tulisi parantaa?

19

Pikamenetelmät allergeenien havaitsemiselle *

- Hyvin vähäinen huolen taso
- Vähäinen huolen taso
- Keskiverto huolen taso
- Suuri huolen taso

20

Miten näitä menetelmiä tulisi parantaa?

21

Elintarvikehygieniaa edistävät suunnittelusuositukset ja parhaat käytännöt: *

- Hyvin vähäinen huolen taso
- Vähäinen huolen taso
- Keskiverto huolen taso
- Suuri huolen taso

22

Miten näitä menetelmiä tulisi parantaa?

23

Elintarvikeketju: jäljitettävyys ja läpinäkyvyys: *

- Hyvin vähäinen huolen taso
- Vähäinen huolen taso
- Keskiverto huolen taso
- Suuri huolen taso

24

Pakkausmateriaaleihin liittyvät innovaatiot: *

- Hyvin vähäinen huolen taso
- Vähäinen huolen taso
- Keskiverto huolen taso
- Suuri huolen taso

25

Pakkausprosessiin liittyvät pakkausmenetelmän innovaatiot *

- Hyvin vähäinen huolen taso
- Vähäinen huolen taso
- Keskiverto huolen taso
- Suuri huolen taso

26

Aktiiviseen pakkaamiseen liittyvät pakkausmenetelmän innovaatiot: *

- Hyvin vähäinen huolen taso
- Vähäinen huolen taso
- Keskiverto huolen taso
- Suuri huolen taso

27

Käytätkö itse tai käyttäkö organisaatiosi tekoälyä tai big data -sovelluksia elintarviketurvallisuuteen liittyen? *

Kyllä

Ei

28

Jos kyllä, mitä tekoälytyökaluja käytät(te)?

Jos ei, miksi? Oletko kiinnostunut oppimaan lisää tekoälytyökaluista ja niiden käytöstä elintarviketurvallisuudessa? *

29

Kuinka tyytyväinen olet edustamasi tahon elintarviketurvallisuuteen? Arvioi tyytyväisyyden taso :

Asteikolla 1 = huono, 10 = hyvä

*

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
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30

Kuinka tyytyväinen olet yleiseen elintarviketurvallisuuteen maatasolla (esim. Suomessa) ?

Asteikolla 1 = huono, 10 = hyvä

*

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	----

31

Mitä "maata" tarkoittit edellisessä kysymyksessä? *

32

Tuleeko sinulle vielä mieleen muita elintarviketurvallisuuden innovaatioihin liittyviä asioita? *

Kyllä

Ei

33

Jos kyllä, voit kommentoida tähän:

34

Onko mielestäsi koulutus tärkeää oman alasi elintarvikkeiden turvallisuuden ja laadun varmistamiseksi? *

Kyllä

Ei

35

Jos kyllä, mitkä asiat olisi mielestäsi asetettava etusijalle?
Jos ei, mitkä esteet tai haasteet vaikuttavat näkökulmaasi? *

OSA B: UUDET, EI VIELÄ KÄYTÖSSÄ OLEVAT INNOVAATIOIJA RATKAISUT

36

Valitse 5 teemaa, joihin liittyviä innovaatioita tai kriittisiin tarpeisiin vastaavia ratkaisuja tulisi ottaa laajemmin käyttöön elintarviketurvallisuuteen liittyen

*

Please select at most 5 options.

- Uudet elintarvikevaarojen ja riskien ehkäisyyn tarkoitetut teknologiat
- Kontaminaatiolähteiden tunnistaminen elintarvikeketjussa
- Elintarvikeketjun vaarojen seurantaan ja tunnistamiseen liittyvä kehitys (esim. sensorien käyttö, patogeenisten organismien, mykotoksiinien ja kemiallisten kontaminanttien tunnistamisen pikamenetelmät)
- Kokogenomisekvensointi (WGS) -tekniikoiden käyttö elintarviketuotannon turvallisuuden edistämiseksi
- Uudet ja vaihtoehtoiset ainesosat tai ratkaisut, jotka lisäävät lopputuotteen turvallisuutta (esim. kasvipäriset valmisteet, mikro-organismit, proteiiniinlähteet, solumaatalous)
- Vaihtoehdot perinteisille säilöntämenetelmille
- Ennusteiden ja mallien laskemiseen käytetyt työkalut (esim. toksikologisten tai mikrobiologisten ennustemallien kehittämisessä)
- Nanoteknologian soveltaminen elintarviketuotantossa
- Hurdle-konseptin kehitys elintarviketuotannossa
- Uudet vaihtoehtoiset elintarvikkeet (esim. hyönteiset, keinoliha, elintarviketuotannon sivutuotteet)
- Uudet tutkimusmenetelmät ja lainsäädäntötarpeet uusille elintarvikkeille
- Elintarvikejätteen kierrättäminen uusiksi resursseiksi
- Uudet elintarvikepakkaus- ja pakkausmerkintäratkaisut, jotka vähentävät ruokajätettä ja edistävät kestäviä ratkaisuja
- Uudet menetelmät puhdistukseen
- Digitaaliset ratkaisut elintarvikeketjun läpinäkyvyyden, turvallisuuden ja jäljitettävyyden lisäämiseen
- Uudet elintarvikeketjun standardit ja logistiikkaratkaisut
- Uudet varastointi- ja kuljetusratkaisut
- Antibioottiresistenttien bakteerien parempi ymmärtäminen ja vaikutusten vähentäminen
- In-silico ja in-vitro menetelmien hyödyntäminen kestävässä ruokajärjestelmässä
- Tekoälytyökalujen käyttö elintarvikeketjun turvallisuuden valvonnan parantamisessa
- Other

OSA C: VERKOSTOT

Catalyse-projektissa luodaan sidosryhmien tarpeisiin räätälöityjä viestintämateriaaleja sellaisista hyvistä käytännöistä ja innovaatioista, jotka ovat jo olemassa, mutta eivät vielä laajasti käytössä.

37

Missä muodossa haluaisit saada nämä koulutusmateriaalit? *

- Luentosymposiumi hybridiosallistumismahdollisuudella
- Kurssit, jotka sisältävät käytännön harjoittelua
- Paikan päällä tapahtuva koulutus
- Soveltava käytännön koulutus
- Webinaarit
- Itseopiskelukurssit
- Other

38

Tähän voit kommentoida muita mahdollisia koulutusmuotoja tai materiaaleja, joita haluaisit

39

Mitä aiheita toivoisit koulutuksiin? *

Please select at most 5 options.

- Tuontantoympäristön seuranta
- Allergeenien hallinnan parhaat käytännöt (FAO/WHO raportit 2022)
- Elintarvikkeiden mikrobiologinen tutkimus ja menetelmät
- Elintarviketurvallisuuksäädökset ja niiden noudattaminen
- Laadunvalvonta elintarviketuotannossa
- Puhdistus ja hygieeninen suunnittelu elintarviketuotannossa
- Elintarvikkeiden pakkaamiseen ja pakkausmerkintöihin liittyvien säädösten noudattaminen
- Uudet työkalut ja menetelmät vaarojen seurantaan ja havaitsemiseen
- Digitaaliset ratkaisut ja niiden mahdollisuudet edistää elintarviketurvallisuuutta
- Uudet ja vaihtoehtoiset ratkaisut/teknologiat lopputuotteiden parantamiseen (nanoteknologia, uudet ainesosat, luonnolliset antimikrobiset aineet)
- Kvantitatiivinen mikrobiologia
- Kvantitatiivinen mikrobiologinen riskinarviointi
- Vaarojen, riskin, todennäköisyyden ja vakavuuden tulkinta
- Kvalitatiivinen näytteenotto ja analysointi: menetelmät ja tilastolliset analyysit
- HACCP ja prosessien validointi: menetelmät vaarojen seurantaan ja havaitsemiseen
- Elintarviketurvallisuuuskulttuuri
- Petokset elintarvikeketjussa
- Uudet, kehitymässä olevat riskit
- Tulevaisuuden kehityksen tutkailu (horizon scanning)
- Vakuutukset ja
- Other

HALUATKO LIITTYÄ CATALYSE-PROJEKTIN SIDOSRYHMÄVERKOSTOON (COMMUNITY OF PRACTICE)?

Osana CATALYSE-projektia perustamme Euroopan laajuisen elintarviketurvallisuuden alan toimijoiden verkoston (Community of Practice, CoP). Se sisältää tiettyihin aiheisiin/teknologioihin keskittyviä teemaosioita digitaalisella alustalla. Verkoston tarkoituksena on edistää vuorovaikutusta, asiaankuuluvan tiedon ja lainsäädännön, koulutusmateriaalien sekä tapahtumatietojen levittämistä, ja tätä kautta edistää osaamisen siirtoa sekä elintarviketurvallisuusalan uuden tiedon ja innovaatioiden käyttöönottoa. Dynaaminen CoP-foorumi tavoittelee:

1. Yhteistyötä elintarvikejärjestelmän sidosryhmien monipuolisen verkoston kanssa, mukaan lukien tutkijat, teollisuus, loppukäyttäjät ja päätöksentekijät.
2. Elintarviketurvallisuutta ja innovaatioita koskevan huippuosaamisen ja resurssien hyödyntämistä.
3. Elintarviketurvallisuuskäytäntöjen ja -tekniikoiden kehityksen edistämistä.
4. Keskusteluja ja ajatustenvaihtoa oman alan kollegojen kanssa paikan päällä tai verkossa toteutettavissa tapaamisissa.
5. Tiedotusta oman alan tapahtumista ja koulutusmateriaaleista

Osallistuminen CoP:iin hyödyttää ammatillista kehitystäsi ja edistää yhteistä pyrkimystä parantaa elintarviketurvallisuutta kaikkialla Euroopassa.

Voit täyttää rekisteröintilomakkeen CATALYSE CoP:iin liittymistä varten tämän kyselyn lähettämisen jälkeen. CATALYSE EU:n konsortion jäsenet kiittävät lämpimästi ajastasi ja vaivannäöstäsi.

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ANNEX 8: Stakeholder engagement 'Consent Form' for one-on-one structured Interviews

Grant Agreement:101136754 – Ref. Ares (2023)7542280 - 07/11/2023

Co-funded by the European Union

CATALYSE EU-Project CONSENT FORM (structured interviews)

WHO WE ARE:

CATALYSE EU-project focuses on understanding the needs and priorities and barriers and levers in Food Safety application innovations. It will further implement these understandings to develop a live Community of Practice based on knowledge exchange, education, and training. The CATALYSE Stakeholder Engagement will connect a number of organizations that are relevant for the three key areas identified: Policy (policymakers, incl. authorities and governmental organizations), Society (end-users, incl. industry and country authorities) and Science (innovators, incl. academia and innovative SMEs). Within CATALYSE, ILSI Europe is responsible for Work Package 2 (WP2), dealing with the management of stakeholder engagement and qualitatively analyze the information to reach a conclusive report that can create as basis for the development and deployment of CATALYSE Community of Practice.

Find out more about CATALYSE on the project's website: <https://thecatalyseproject.eu>

WHY WE ARE TALKING TO YOU:

We want you to participate in our research because your experience and your understanding is important. In this study we would like to ask you questions about your needs and priorities food safety innovative applications, barriers and levers for improvement in knowledge exchange, training and courses. You will be asked to participate in interviews organized by ILSI Europe, one of CATALYSE's project partners, about your experience as a stakeholder/end-user/practitioner.

* Required

GENERAL Information

TIME INVOLVEMENT:

The interview will take between 40-50 minutes. This research study may take up to approximately 3 years after your participation.

RISKS AND BENEFITS:

There are no direct risks for you that we know of. Your decision whether or not to participate in this study will not be reported to, nor will it affect your participation in, other CATALYSE events and activities. However, your participation and expertise is of great value for the project.

PAYMENT:

You will not receive any reimbursement, in cash or in kind, as payment for your participation.

RIGHTS:

Your participation is voluntary and you have the right to refuse to participate and to withdraw your participation, at any time without any consequences. You have the right to refuse to answer particular questions during the interview. Your name and contact data will always be confidential, will never be public, findable or accessible, and, unless you specifically request otherwise, you will never be identified. You will be always the owner of data and samples collected.

DATA/SAMPLING Information

USE OF DATA:

The materials and data collected will be anonymized and then become part of studies that may be presented at scientific or professional meetings or published in scientific or professional journals for communication and dissemination purposes of the CATALYSE project. Personal data will only be processed for the purpose of scheduling the interview and being contacted by the CATALYSE consortium for events in the future (if you consent to this processing in the next steps). The processing of personal data is subject to the Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council (GDPR).

DATA STORAGE, PROTECTION, RETENTION AND DESTRUCTION:

Data will be stored securely on separate hard drives with an access key and on the private institutional ILSI Europe Microsoft Office 365 OneDrive (Microsoft protects the Microsoft Office 365 OneDrive from viruses and data piracy and makes periodic back-ups), in ILSI Europe's servers located in Europe. Anonymized and aggregated data (summary of the interview) derived during this study will be made publicly available, as part of scientific publications, educational material, and project reports. This data will be archived in a research data repository and will be publicly accessible for at least 10 years. Personal Data shall be retained until data derived from sampling, surveys, questionnaires or interviews are published. By default, all Personal Data shall be destroyed after a period 36 months of the finalization of CATALYSE project.

CONTACT Information

CATALYSE CONTACT INFORMATION:

If you have any questions, concerns or complaints about this research, its procedures, risks and benefits, contact the Project Coordinator Prof. Daniela Bassi at daniela.bassi@unicatt.it

ETHICS CONTACT:

ETHICS CONTACT: If you are not satisfied with how this study is being conducted, or if you have any concerns, complaints, or general questions about the research or your rights as a participant, please contact us at catalyse.eu@gmail.com , we will forward you to the ethics mentor for CATALYSE project who will be independent of the research team.

STAKEHOLDER CONSENT

Co-funded by the European Union

I confirm that I have read and understood the information about the research project presented on the previous sections.

I confirm that by sharing the contact information I have had the opportunity to ask questions about the research project and that these have been answered satisfactorily.

I understand that my participation is voluntary and I am free to withdraw at any time without giving a reason and without any adverse consequences. I understand that if I withdraw, information I provided that has already been processed (e.g. summarized or analyzed) may be kept by the CATALYSE project. This provision does not include my personal data.

I give consent to be audiotaped/videotaped during this study for transcription purposes only.

I consent to the processing of my personal information for the purposes explained to me.

I understand that such information will be held in accordance with all applicable data protection legislation and in strict confidence, unless disclosure is required by law or professional obligation.

I give consent for data resulting from this study to be presented at scientific or professional meetings or published in scientific or professional journals for communication and dissemination purposes.

By default, your identity (name and contact data) will not be retained after conclusion of the interview, unless you give explicit consent and wish to reveal your identity.

I understand how the findings and results of the research project will be written up and published. I agree to take part in this research project.

1

Please tick your consent preferences below: *

- Yes, I consent
- No, I do not consent

2

Please indicate your FIRST NAME & LAST NAME: *

3

If you consent, please indicate your email address for contact purposes:

CONTINUED STAKEHOLDER SUPPORT CONSENT

In the course of the CATALYSE project, the CATALYSE consortium members will provide the opportunity to stay engaged with the project in the form of workshops, seminars, or other activities that align with your interests and expertise. We would like to request your consent to be contacted for future events organized by our project partners.

If you consent to being contacted, your contact details will be shared with the consortium members, who will treat your personal data with the same care as we do. You can withdraw your consent to being contacted at any time and without providing reasons. Your personal data for this purpose will only be retained for the duration of the project.

If you do not consent, you can still participate in the interview.

4

Please tick your consent preferences below: *

- Yes, I consent
- No, I do not consent

5

If you consent, please indicate your FIRST & LAST NAME below: *

6

If you consent, please indicate your email address for contact purposes:

This content is neither created nor endorsed by Microsoft. The data you submit will be sent to the form owner.

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ANNEX 9: Industry Stakeholder Structured Interview Questionnaire

INDUSTRY - Stakeholder Interview Guide

Hello and thank you for participating in Stakeholder Engagement Interviews for CATALYSE EU. We are interested in your honest opinions and experiences through the following in-depth conversation in the field of Food Safety Applications and Innovations. Your responses will remain confidential and the interview is scheduled for 40-50 minutes.

This interview's purpose is to understand the main needs in terms of food safety information/knowledge topics widely applied by end-users (official control authorities, food business operators, food safety risks assessors, etc.).

Nowadays food safety knowledge and innovation ecosystems are insufficiently connected. This is why our main goal is to create a network in the area of innovation in food safety for knowledge exchange between end-users and innovation ecosystems. This will include dissemination of public events, papers and reports, and the creation of an on-line collaborative platform including the availability of materials for training and education. If you would like to know more about the project and its reach please do not hesitate to contact our communications team at catalyse.eu@gmail.com

This would not be possible without your help 😊

THANK YOU FOR YOUR COLLABORATION!

* Required

DEMOGRAPHIC QUESTIONNAIRE

general information required below

1. Please indicate the name of the interviewer (a member of CATALYSE consortium) *

2. Please indicate if the stakeholder has signed the consent form? *

Yes

No

3. Please indicate your gender: *

from here on, please ask the questions to the stakeholder as suited for the conversation

Woman

Man

Other

Prefer not to say

4. Please indicate which age group do you fall under? *

20-30

31-45

46-60

>60

5. Please indicate your expertise in the field of food science and technology: *

6. Please specify your industry domain: *

Primary producers

Food / Ingredients / Equipment processor

Laboratory Services

B2B Consultancy

Logistics company

Non-Profit Organization

Food Safety Technology Provider

Other

BLOCK A : Understanding Needs and Priorities

Food Safety Innovative Applications, Barriers and Levers for Improvement

7. What are the key challenges you face in the development of innovative food safety solutions? Explain the background of these challenges, and why they persist? *

8. List in order of importance which are the primary barriers to innovation in food safety that you encounter and their impact (among the ones I indicate now) :

- A. Lack of Collaboration
- B. Regulation
- C. Costs
- D. Lack of Awareness
- E. Lack of Dissemination to Small/Traditional Producers
- F. Resistance to Change

*

please write the chronology of importance with the letters (e.g. D, C, F, E, A, B)

9. What factors do you consider limiting the resolution of barriers in food safety? What actions would be facilitating progress in these areas? *
- (follow-up of the previous answer)

10. What specific innovations do you see as most promising for addressing current food safety concerns? *

BLOCK B: Community of Practice (CoP) Recruitment

Briefly introduce the concept of the Community of Practice (CoP) and specificity of it related to CATALYSE.

The Catalyst working model "Collect – Translate – Facilitate – Educate" will become alive through building up specific CoP, easily accessible and open for the entire food ecosystem. As part of CATALYSE, we are establishing a Europe-wide community of practice (CoP) with thematic chapters on specific topics/technologies through a digital platform to facilitate interaction, dissemination of relevant knowledge and regulations, educational materials and relevant events.

Explain the potential benefits of joining the CoP for stakeholders (e.g., networking, collaboration, access to resources).

CoP: This CoP will be a dynamic forum to promote knowledge transfer and uptake of food safety knowledge and innovation through:

1. Collaborating with a diverse network of food system stakeholders including researchers, industry, end-users and policymakers.
2. Accessing cutting-edge knowledge and resources on food safety and innovation.
3. Contributing to the advancement of food safety practices and technologies.
4. Engaging in meaningful discussions and exchange ideas with peers through physical and online meetings.
5. Staying informed about relevant events and educational materials.

Participation in the CoP will not only benefit professional development, but will also contribute to the collective effort to improve food safety across Europe.

11. The 6 concepts specified in the strategic and innovation plan for Food Safety published by Flanders Food (<https://www.flandersfood.com/en/world-class-food-production/food-safety>) are transversal themes that come back in the each action. The 6 concepts are:

1. **Understanding** - Create understanding and appreciation of food safety
2. **Tech-enabled** - Incorporate technology into a food-safe work environment
3. **Farm to fork risks** - Make food safety more sustainable and connected
4. **Trend risks** - Create support for demand-driven food safety problems
5. **Pathogen control** - Monitor the presence and growth of pathogenic microorganisms
6. **Clean production** - Monitor hygiene to control food safety

From the 6 FF themes ask which ones are most important, does it align with the above barriers and levers?

12. **EDUCATION AND TRAINING** : What kind of knowledge exchange platform, format and content would be most effective for future educational resources or training programs? *

13. **CoP** : Which is the best approach that the CoP should adopt to reach out to the smallest of producers in the food industry? *

14. **CoP:** What impact do you expect from the CoP of Catalyse? *

CLOSING

To end on a friendly note

Thank the stakeholder once again for their participation

Provide information on how they can access the final report – *January 2025 on CATALYSE website*

Stay informed about project progress and qualitative interpretation of these interactions:

Online Workshops

- 10th October 2024
- 10th DECEMBER 2024

In-person Workshops

- 1st May 2024 – IAFP conference (Geneva, CH)
- 22nd October 2024 – Food Revolution (Parma, IT)

Encourage Stakeholder to join Community of Practice:

Participation in the CoP will not only benefit professional development, but will also contribute to the collective effort to improve food safety across Europe. This CoP will be a dynamic forum to promote knowledge transfer and uptake of food safety knowledge and innovation; Commence activities from June 2025.

If the stakeholder would like to join CATALYSE EU Community of Practice please click on the following link: <https://bit.ly/CATALYSECoPRegistration>

Ask the participant for names of other experts to interview/connect with.

THANK YOU FOR YOUR COLLABORATION!

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ANNEX 10: Academic Stakeholder Structured Interview Questionnaire

ACADEMIA - Stakeholder Interview Guide

Hello and thank you for participating in Stakeholder Engagement Interviews for CATALYSE EU. We are interested in your honest opinions and experiences through the following in-depth conversation in the field of Food Safety Applications and Innovations. Your responses will remain confidential and the interview is scheduled for 40-50 minutes.

This interview's purpose is to understand the main needs in terms of food safety information/knowledge topics widely applied by end-users (official control authorities, food business operators, food safety risks assessors, etc.).

Nowadays food safety knowledge and innovation ecosystems are insufficiently connected. This is why our main goal is to create a network in the area of innovation in food safety for knowledge exchange between end-users and innovation ecosystems. This will include dissemination of public events, papers and reports, and the creation of an on-line collaborative platform including the availability of materials for training and education. If you would like to know more about the project and its reach please do not hesitate to contact our communications team at catalyse.eu@gmail.com

This would not be possible without your help 😊

THANK YOU FOR YOUR COLLABORATION!

* Required

DEMOGRAPHIC QUESTIONNAIRE

general information required below

1. Please indicate the name of the interviewer (a member of CATALYSE consortium) *

2. Please indicate if the stakeholder has signed the consent form? *

Yes

No

3. Please indicate your gender: *

from here on, please ask the questions to the stakeholder as suited for the conversation

Woman

Man

Other

Prefer not to say

4. Please indicate which age group do you fall under? *

- 20-30
- 31-45
- 46-60
- >60

5. Please indicate which Academic Institution you belong to? *

6. Please indicate your expertise in the field of food science and technology: *

BLOCK A : Understanding Needs and Priorities

Food Safety Innovative Applications, Barriers and Levers for Improvement

7. What are the key challenges you face in the development of innovative food safety solutions? Explain the background of these challenges, and why they persist? *

8. List in order of importance which are the primary barriers to innovation in food safety that you encounter and their impact (among the ones I indicate now) :

- A. Lack of Collaboration
- B. Regulation
- C. Costs
- D. Lack of Awareness
- E. Lack of Dissemination to Small/Traditional Producers
- F. Resistance to Change

*

please write the chronology of importance with the letters (e.g. D, C, F, E, A, B)

9. What factors do you consider limiting the resolution of barriers in food safety? What actions will be most facilitating for progress in each of these areas? *
(follow-up of the previous answer)

10. What specific innovations do you see as most promising for addressing current food safety concerns? *

BLOCK B: Community of Practice (CoP) Recruitment

Briefly introduce the concept of the Community of Practice (CoP) and specificity of it related to CATALYSE.

The Catalyst working model "Collect – Translate – Facilitate – Educate" will become alive through building up specific CoP, easily accessible and open for the entire food ecosystem. As part of CATALYSE, we are establishing a Europe-wide community of practice (CoP) with thematic chapters on specific topics/technologies through a digital platform to facilitate interaction, dissemination of relevant knowledge and regulations, educational materials and relevant events.

Explain the potential benefits of joining the CoP for stakeholders (e.g., networking, collaboration, access to resources).

CoP: This CoP will be a dynamic forum to promote knowledge transfer and uptake of food safety knowledge and innovation through:

1. Collaborating with a diverse network of food system stakeholders including researchers, industry, end-users and policymakers.
2. Accessing cutting-edge knowledge and resources on food safety and innovation.
3. Contributing to the advancement of food safety practices and technologies.
4. Engaging in meaningful discussions and exchange ideas with peers through physical and online meetings.
5. Staying informed about relevant events and educational materials.

Participation in the CoP will not only benefit professional development, but will also contribute to the collective effort to improve food safety across Europe.

11. The 6 concepts specified in the strategic and innovation plan for Food Safety published by Flanders Food (<https://www.flandersfood.com/en/world-class-food-production/food-safety>) are transversal themes that come back in the each action. The 6 concepts are:

1. **Understanding** - Create understanding and appreciation of food safety
2. **Tech-enabled** - Incorporate technology into a food-safe work environment
3. **Farm to fork risks** - Make food safety more sustainable and connected
4. **Trend risks** - Create support for demand-driven food safety problems
5. **Pathogen control** - Monitor the presence and growth of pathogenic microorganisms
6. **Clean production** - Monitor hygiene to control food safety

From the 6 FF themes ask which ones are most important, does it align with the above barriers and levers?

12. **EDUCATION AND TRAINING** : What type of knowledge exchange platforms, format and content would be most effective for future educational resources or training programs? *

13. **CoP** : Which is the best approach that the CoP should adopt to reach out to the smallest of producers in the food industry? *

14. **CoP:** What impact do you expect from the CoP of Catalyse? *

CLOSING

To end on a friendly note

Thank the stakeholder once again for their participation

Provide information on how they can access the final report – *January 2025 on CATALYSE website*

Stay informed about project progress and qualitative interpretation of these interactions:

Online Workshops

- 10th October 2024
- 10th DECEMBER 2024

In-person Workshops

- 1st May 2024 – IAFP conference (Geneva, CH)
- 22nd October 2024 – Food Revolution (Parma, IT)

Encourage Stakeholder to join Community of Practice:

Participation in the CoP will not only benefit professional development, but will also contribute to the collective effort to improve food safety across Europe. This CoP will be a dynamic forum to promote knowledge transfer and uptake of food safety knowledge and innovation; Commence activities from June 2025.

If the stakeholder would like to join CATALYSE EU Community of Practice please click on the following link: <https://bit.ly/CATALYSECoPRegistration>

Ask the participant for names of other experts to interview/connect with.

THANK YOU FOR YOUR COLLABORATION!

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ANNEX 11: Policymakers/ Public Authority Stakeholder Structured Interview Questionnaire

POLICYMAKERS / PUBLIC AUTHORITIES - Stakeholder Interview Guide

Hello and thank you for participating in Stakeholder Engagement Interviews for CATALYSE EU. We are interested in your honest opinions and experiences through the following in-depth conversation in the field of Food Safety Applications and Innovations. Your responses will remain confidential and the interview is scheduled for 40-50 minutes.

This interview's purpose is to understand the main needs in terms of food safety information/knowledge topics widely applied by end-users (official control authorities, food business operators, food safety risks assessors, etc.).

Nowadays food safety knowledge and innovation ecosystems are insufficiently connected. This is why our main goal is to create a network in the area of innovation in food safety for knowledge exchange between end-users and innovation ecosystems. This will include dissemination of public events, papers and reports, and the creation of an on-line collaborative platform including the availability of materials for training and education. If you would like to know more about the project and it's reach please do not hesitate to contact our communications team at catalyse.eu@gmail.com

This would not be possible without your help 😊

THANK YOU FOR YOUR COLLABORATION!

* Required

DEMOGRAPHIC QUESTIONNAIRE

general information required below

1. Please indicate the name of the interviewer (a member of CATALYSE EU consortium) *

2. Please indicate if the stakeholder has signed the consent form? *

Yes

No

3. Please indicate your gender: *

from here on, please ask the questions to the stakeholder as suited for the conversation

Woman

Man

Other

Prefer not to say

4. Please indicate which age group do you fall under? *

20-30

31-45

46-60

>60

5. Please indicate which Institution you belong to? *

6. Please indicate your expertise in the field of food science and technology: *

7. Please specify you domain in Policymakers / Public Authorities *

Policymakers / national level (e.g. Ministry) and possibly also international level (e.g. European Commission)

Public Authorities / authorities responsible for (national, regional) risk management in the Member States

Public Authorities / authorities responsible for risk assessment in the Member States

Public Authorities / international authorities: EFSA, ECHA, EMA, ...

Other

BLOCK A : Understanding Needs and Priorities

Food Safety Innovative Applications, Barriers and Levers for Improvement

8. What are the main concerns in food safety in your experience/organization? *

9. What are the key challenges you face in adopting or implementing innovative food safety solutions? *

follow-up this question by asking - **why? what may be the reason behind the existence of these challenges?**

10. List in order of importance which are the primary barriers to innovation in food safety that you encounter and their impact (among the ones I indicate now) :

A. Lack of Collaboration

B. Regulation

C. Costs

D. Lack of Awareness

E. Lack of Dissemination to Small/Traditional Producers

F. Resistance to Change

*

please write the chronology of importance with the letters (e.g. D, C, F, E, A, B)

11. What factors do you consider limiting the resolution of barriers in food safety? What actions might facilitate progress in each area? *

(follow-up of the previous answer)

12. What specific innovations do you see as most promising for addressing current food safety concerns? *

BLOCK B: Community of Practice (CoP) Recruitment

Briefly introduce the concept of the Community of Practice (CoP) and specificity of it related to CATALYSE.

The Catalyst working model "Collect – Translate – Facilitate – Educate" will become alive through building up specific CoP, easily accessible and open for the entire food ecosystem. As part of CATALYSE, we are establishing a Europe-wide community of practice (CoP) with thematic chapters on specific topics/technologies through a digital platform to facilitate interaction, dissemination of relevant knowledge and regulations, educational materials and relevant events.

Explain the potential benefits of joining the CoP for stakeholders (e.g., networking, collaboration, access to resources).

CoP: This CoP will be a dynamic forum to promote knowledge transfer and uptake of food safety knowledge and innovation through:

1. Collaborating with a diverse network of food system stakeholders including researchers, industry, end-users and policymakers.
2. Accessing cutting-edge knowledge and resources on food safety and innovation.
3. Contributing to the advancement of food safety practices and technologies.
4. Engaging in meaningful discussions and exchange ideas with peers through physical and online meetings.
5. Staying informed about relevant events and educational materials.

Participation in the CoP will not only benefit professional development, but will also contribute to the collective effort to improve food safety across Europe.

13. The 6 concepts specified in the strategic and innovation plan for Food Safety published by Flanders Food (<https://www.flandersfood.com/en/world-class-food-production/food-safety>) are transversal themes that come back in the each action. The 6 concepts are:

1. **Understanding** - Create understanding and appreciation of food safety
2. **Tech-enabled** - Incorporate technology into a food-safe work environment
3. **Farm to fork risks** - Make food safety more sustainable and connected
4. **Trend risks** - Create support for demand-driven food safety problems
5. **Pathogen control** - Monitor the presence and growth of pathogenic microorganisms
6. **Clean production** - Monitor hygiene to control food safety

From the 6 FF themes ask which ones are most important, does it align with the above barriers and levers?

14. **EDUCATION AND TRAINING** : What knowledge exchange platforms, format and content would be most effective for future educational resources or training programs? *

15. **CoP** : Which is the best approach that the CoP should adopt to reach out to the smallest of producers in the food industry? *

16. **CoP:** What impact do you expect from the CoP of Catalyse? *

CLOSING

To end on a friendly note

Thank the stakeholder once again for their participation

Provide information on how they can access the final report – *January 2025 on CATALYSE website*

Stay informed about project progress and qualitative interpretation of these interactions:

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- 10th October 2024
- 10th DECEMBER 2024

In-person Workshops

- 1st May 2024 – IAFP conference (Geneva, CH)
- 22nd October 2024 – Food Revolution (Parma, IT)

Encourage Stakeholder to join Community of Practice:

Participation in the CoP will not only benefit professional development, but will also contribute to the collective effort to improve food safety across Europe. This CoP will be a dynamic forum to promote knowledge transfer and uptake of food safety knowledge and innovation; Commence activities from June 2025.

If the stakeholder would like to join CATALYSE EU Community of Practice please click on the following link: <https://bit.ly/CATALYSECoPRegistration>

Ask the participant for names of other experts to interview/connect with.

THANK YOU FOR YOUR COLLABORATION!

This content is neither created nor endorsed by Microsoft. The data you submit will be sent to the form owner.

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ANNEX 12: Civil Society Stakeholder Structured Interview Questionnaire

CIVIL SOCIETY : Stakeholder Interview Guide

Hello and thank you for participating in Stakeholder Engagement Interviews for CATALYSE EU. We are interested in your honest opinions and experiences through the following in-depth conversation in the field of Food Safety Applications and Innovations. Your responses will remain confidential and the interview is scheduled for 30 minutes.

This interview's purpose is to understand the main needs in terms of food safety information/knowledge topics widely applied by end-users (official control authorities, food business operators, food safety risks assessors, etc.).

Nowadays food safety knowledge and innovation ecosystems are insufficiently connected. This is why our main goal is to create a network in the area of innovation in food safety for knowledge exchange between end-users and innovation ecosystems. This will include dissemination of public events, papers and reports, and the creation of an on-line collaborative platform including the availability of materials for training and education. If you would like to know more about the project and its reach please do not hesitate to contact our communications team at catalyse.eu@gmail.com

This would not be possible without your help 😊

THANK YOU FOR YOUR COLLABORATION!

* Required

DEMOGRAPHIC QUESTIONNAIRE

general information required below

1. Please indicate the name of the interviewer (a member of CATALYSE EU consortium) *

2. Please indicate if the stakeholder has signed the consent form? *

Yes

No

3. Please indicate your gender: *

from here on, please ask the questions to the stakeholder as suited for the conversation

Woman

Man

Other

Prefer not to say

4. Please indicate which age group do you fall under? *

- 20-30
- 31-45
- 46-60
- >60

5. Please indicate which Institution you belong to? *

6. Please indicate how is your work related to Food Safety Risks and Actions? *

BLOCK A : Understanding Needs and Priorities

Food Safety Innovative Applications, Barriers and Levers for Improvement

7. List in order of importance which are the primary barriers to innovation in food safety that you encounter and their impact (among the ones I indicate now) :

- A. Lack of Collaboration
- B. Regulation
- C. Costs
- D. Lack of Awareness
- E. Lack of Dissemination to Small/Traditional Producers
- F. Resistance to Change

*

please write the chronology of importance with the letters (e.g. D, C, F, E, A, B)

8. What actions would be most facilitating for progress in each area? *

if needed, only then assist with the following examples for support: needs, knowledge exchange, education/training, budget, human resources, scientific and technological support

BLOCK B: Community of Practice (CoP) Recruitment

Briefly introduce the concept of the Community of Practice (CoP) and specificity of it related to CATALYSE.

The Catalyst working model "Collect – Translate – Facilitate – Educate" will become alive through building up specific CoP, easily accessible and open for the entire food ecosystem. As part of CATALYSE, we are establishing a Europe-wide community of practice (CoP) with thematic chapters on specific topics/technologies through a digital platform to facilitate interaction, dissemination of relevant knowledge and regulations, educational materials and relevant events.

Explain the potential benefits of joining the CoP for stakeholders (e.g., networking, collaboration, access to resources).

CoP: This CoP will be a dynamic forum to promote knowledge transfer and uptake of food safety knowledge and innovation through:

1. Collaborating with a diverse network of food system stakeholders including researchers, industry, end-users and policymakers.
2. Accessing cutting-edge knowledge and resources on food safety and innovation.
3. Contributing to the advancement of food safety practices and technologies.
4. Engaging in meaningful discussions and exchange ideas with peers through physical and online meetings.
5. Staying informed about relevant events and educational materials.

Participation in the CoP will not only benefit professional development, but will also contribute to the collective effort to improve food safety across Europe.

9. **EDUCATION AND TRAINING** : What format and content would be most effective for future educational/information purposes? *

10. **CoP**: What impact do you expect from the CoP of Catalyse? *

CLOSING

To end on a friendly note

Thank the stakeholder once again for their participation

Provide information on how they can access the final report – *January 2025 on CATALYSE website*

Stay informed about project progress and qualitative interpretation of these interactions:

Online Workshops

- 10th October 2024
- 10th DECEMBER 2024

In-person Workshops

- 1st May 2024 – IAFP conference (Geneva, CH)
- 22nd October 2024 – Food Revolution (Parma, IT)

Encourage Stakeholder to join Community of Practice:

Participation in the CoP will not only benefit professional development, but will also contribute to the collective effort to improve food safety across Europe. This CoP will be a dynamic forum to promote knowledge transfer and uptake of food safety knowledge and innovation; Commence activities from June 2025.

If the stakeholder would like to join CATALYSE EU Community of Practice please click on the following link: <https://bit.ly/CATALYSECoPRegistration>

Ask the participant for names of other experts to interview/connect with.

THANK YOU FOR YOUR COLLABORATION!

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